

PhD Thesis

Niklas Breindahl, MD

Preparing for the NON-pharmacological Approach to Less Invasive Surfactant Administration (NONA-LISA) trial

*Improving training, procedural competency, and non-pharmacological comfort care
for the LISA procedure*

Supervisors: Lise Aunsholt, Martin Grønnebæk Tolsgaard, Tine Brink Henriksen

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Preface

The art of medicine is about doing the right thing in the right way. It is a misconception to assume that a procedure that is quickly performed and successful on the first attempt equals procedural quality. Often, procedural quality depends on more than one individual's performance to complete the procedure with little or no discomfort for the patient. This is also true for the Less Invasive Surfactant Administration (LISA) procedure.

This thesis represents a unique multinational collaboration within the field of neonatology spearheaded by the four highly specialised neonatal intensive care units in Denmark. The combined efforts of neonatologists, neonatal nurses, and parent representatives were integral to improving training, procedural competency, and non-pharmacological comfort care for the LISA procedure. This thesis underlines the value and importance of an interdisciplinary approach to improve one out of many medical procedures and healthcare research.

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To my co-supervisor, Martin G. Tolsgaard; thank you for consistently seeing my potential and challenging me to push beyond my limits.

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Thank you to the interdisciplinary research unit at the Department of Neonatal and Paediatric Intensive Care at Rigshospitalet and the NONA-LISA Research Group for their continuous support and sparring.

To my family, Sara and Aya, your unwavering support and understanding have been my greatest strength throughout this journey. Thank you for being a constant source of encouragement and always reminding me of what matters the most. Your belief in me has meant the world to me.

List of abbreviations

ALPS-Neo	Astrid Lindgren and Lund Children's Hospitals Pain and Stress Assessment Scale for Preterm and Sick Newborn Infants
AMV	Avoid Mechanical Ventilation trial
BIIP	The Behavioural Indicators of Infant Pain
BPD	Bronchopulmonary Dysplasia
CaLi	Caffeine and Less Invasive Surfactant Administration trial
CONSORT	Consolidated Standards of Reporting Trials Statement
CPAP	Continuous Positive Airway Pressure
CROSS	Consensus-Based Checklist for Reporting of Survey Studies
DMEC	Data Management and Ethical Committee
D-study	Decision Study
ETT	Endotracheal Tube
FINE	Family Infant Neurodevelopmental Education
FiO ₂	Fraction of Inspired Oxygen
G-study	Generalizability Study
INSURE	Intubation Surfactant Extubation
IQR	Interquartile Range
LISA	Less Invasive Surfactant Administration
LISA-AT	Less Invasive Surfactant Administration Assessment Tool
LISA-CUR	Less Invasive Surfactant Administration CURriculum
MIST	Minimally Invasive Surfactant Therapy
NICU	Neonatal Intensive Care Unit
NIDCAP	Newborn Individualised Developmental Care and Assessment Program
NINSAPP	Nonintubated Surfactant Application trial
NONA-LISA	NON-pharmacological Approach to LISA
OPTIMIST-A	cOllaborative Paired Trials Investigating Minimally Invasive Surfactant Therapy, trial A
PIPP	Premature Infant Pain Profile
PIPP-R	Premature Infant Pain Profile Revised
RDS	Respiratory Distress Syndrome
REDCap	Research Electronic Data Capture
SBT	Simulation-Based Training
SPIRIT	Standard Protocol Items: Recommendations for Interventional Trials

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STUDIES

This PhD thesis is based on the following three studies (referenced as *Studies I-III*) reported in four original papers (referenced as *Papers I-IV*). Papers I and III are published open-access, and Papers II and IV are under review. All papers are attached in the appendix.

Study I. Curriculum and assessment tool for less invasive surfactant administration: an international Delphi consensus study.

Paper I. Breindahl N., Tolsgaard M.G., Henriksen T.B. *et al.* Curriculum and assessment tool for less invasive surfactant administration: an international Delphi consensus study. *Pediatr Res* 94, 1216–1224 (2023). DOI: [10.1038/s41390-023-02621-2](https://doi.org/10.1038/s41390-023-02621-2).¹

Study II. Competency in the Less Invasive Surfactant Administration procedure: Validity evidence for the LISA-AT score.

Paper II. Breindahl N., Bay E.T., Heiring C. *et al.* Competency in the Less Invasive Surfactant Administration procedure: Validity evidence for the LISA-AT score. Submitted, under review.²

Study III. The NON-pharmacological Approach to Less Invasive Surfactant Administration (NONA-LISA) trial.

Paper III. Breindahl N., Henriksen T.B., Heiring C. *et al.* NON-pharmacological Approach Less Invasive Surfactant Administration (NONA-LISA) trial: protocol for a randomised controlled trial. *Pediatr Res* 96, 1084-1089 (2024). DOI: [10.1038/s41390-023-02998-0](https://doi.org/10.1038/s41390-023-02998-0).³

Paper IV. Breindahl N., Henriksen T.B., Heiring C. *et al.* Can Non-pharmacological Comfort Care Replace Fentanyl in LISA? The NONA-LISA Feasibility Study. Submitted, under review.⁴

SUMMARY

Introduction: Neonatal respiratory distress syndrome (RDS) develops during the first 24 hours of birth. Current guidelines identify Less Invasive Surfactant Administration (LISA) as the preferred method for surfactant administration in preterm infants before 30 completed weeks of gestation with RDS. However, there are no standardised requirements for LISA training or assessment of operator competence. Non-pharmacological comfort care and assessment of procedural pain are not standardised, and the use of analgesic or sedating premedication in LISA is debated.

Aims: This thesis aimed to describe the preparations for the NON-pharmacological Approach to Less Invasive Surfactant Administration (NONA-LISA) trial. Paper I aimed to obtain international expert consensus on a LISA curriculum (LISA-CUR) and assessment tool (LISA-AT) for training operators and assessing competence. Paper II aimed to evaluate validity evidence using Messick's framework. Paper III aimed to design a randomised controlled trial to investigate the effect of premedication for LISA. Paper IV aimed to assess the NONA-LISA trial's safety and feasibility.

Methods: Paper I collected expert opinions during a three-round iterative Delphi process to establish consensus, which was reported according to the CROSS checklist for reporting survey studies. Paper II included LISA experts and novices in a simulated setting and reported the five sources of validity evidence according to Messick's framework. Paper III was the protocol article for the NONA-LISA trial, which was reported according to the SPIRIT checklist for reporting trial protocols. Paper IV was the feasibility study preceding the NONA-LISA trial, which was reported according to the CONSORT checklist for reporting clinical trials.

Results: Paper I included 153 experts from 14 countries and achieved response rates of >80% in the subsequent rounds. In Delphi round 1, 44 items were identified for the LISA-CUR and 22 for the LISA-AT. In Delphi round 2, these numbers were reduced to 29 and 15, respectively, according to the predefined consensus threshold, and response anchors were established for the LISA-AT. In Delphi round 3, the experts almost unanimously agreed to accept the final LISA-CUR and LISA-AT.

Paper II included ten experts and 23 novices. Eight items on the original LISA-AT discriminated between expert and novice performances and constituted a modified assessment tool, ranging from 8 to 40 points. The modified LISA-AT had a high test-retest reliability, internal consistency, and good inter-rater reliability. The minimum passing score was established at 39/40 points, according

to the lowest quartile of the experts' performances. The novices needed a median [IQR] of 6 [5-7] attempts to reach the minimum passing score, ranging from 4 to 9 attempts.

Paper III developed the standardised approach to non-pharmacological comfort care and included a detailed description of the NONA-LISA trial design. The NONA-LISA trial is a multicentre, blinded, randomised, controlled trial, including infants who meet the LISA criteria. It compares intravenous premedication with isotonic saline to premedication with fentanyl 0.5-1.0 mcg/kg. The primary outcome is the need for invasive ventilation via an endotracheal tube (ETT) for a cumulated duration of 30 minutes or more within 24 hours of the LISA procedure.

Paper IV included 17 infants at the two founding NONA-LISA trial sites. A COMFORTneo score ≥ 14 performed during the procedure was observed in three of nine infants (33%) in the saline group and four of eight infants (50%) in the fentanyl group. Open-label fentanyl was administered intravenously to two infants from the saline group with a modified COMFORTneo score ≥ 14 . Otherwise, infants with increased COMFORTneo scores were managed by pausing the procedure and adjusting non-pharmacological comfort care according to the standardised approach. No adverse events related to the trial were reported.

Conclusion: This thesis describes the preparations for the NONA-LISA trial. These results can improve training, procedural competency, and non-pharmacological comfort care for the LISA procedure. The results from the large NONA-LISA trial are warranted, and we believe it is safe and feasible to continue with the trial.

SUMMARY IN DANISH (DANSK RESUME)

Introduktion: Respiratorisk distress syndrom (RDS) hos præmature nyfødte opstår typisk inden for de første 24 timer efter fødslen. De nuværende retningslinjer anbefaler Less Invasive Surfactant Administration (LISA) til surfaktantbehandling af præmature børn født før 30 gestationsuger med RDS. LISA proceduren involverer intratrakeal administration af lungemodnende medicin, surfaktant, via et tyndt kateter. Dog er der ingen ensartede krav til LISA træning eller kompetencevurdering. Non-farmakologisk behandling og smertevurdering er ikke standardiseret, og brugen af analgetisk eller sederende præmedicinering ved LISA er debatteret.

Formål: Denne afhandling havde til formål at beskrive forberedelserne til NON-pharmacological Approach to Less Invasive Surfactant Administration (NONA-LISA) forsøget. Artikel I havde til formål at etablere international ekspertkonsensus for et LISA curriculum samt et scoringsværktøj til at træne og vurdere LISA kompetencer. Artikel II havde til formål at evaluere validiteten af scoringsværktøjet ved hjælp af Messicks struktur. Artikel III havde til formål at designe et randomiseret kontrolleret forsøg til at undersøge effekten af præmedicinering ved LISA proceduren. Artikel IV havde til formål at vurdere sikkerheden og gennemførligheden af NONA-LISA forsøget.

Metoder: Artikel I indsamlede og kondenserede ekspertholdninger gennem tre runder af online spørgeskemaer for at opnå konsensus. Resultaterne fra spørgeskemaundersøgelsen blev rapporteret i henhold til CROSS tjeklisten. Artikel II var et simulationsstudie, der inkluderede LISA eksperter og novicer. Resultaterne blev rapporteret i henhold til de fem typer af validitetsevidens beskrevet i Messicks struktur. Artikel III var protokolartiklen for NONA-LISA forsøget, og resultaterne blev beskrevet i henhold til SPIRIT tjeklisten for rapportering af forskningsprotokoller for kliniske randomiserede kontrollerede forsøg. Artikel IV evaluerede gennemførligheden forud for NONA-LISA forsøget. Resultaterne blev beskrevet i henhold til CONSORT tjeklisten, som bruges til rapportering af kliniske forsøg.

Resultater: Artikel I inkluderede 153 eksperter fra 14 lande og opnåede en svarprocent på >80% i de efterfølgende runder. I Delphi runde 1 blev 44 unikke elementer identificeret til et præliminært LISA curriculum og 22 til scoringsværktøjet. I Delphi runde 2 blev antallet af elementer reduceret til henholdsvis 29 og 15 i overensstemmelse med den foruddefinerede konsensustærskel, og svarankre blev etableret for de tilbageværende elementer i scoringsværktøjet. I Delphi runde 3 accepterede eksperterne næsten enstemmigt det endelige LISA curriculum og scoringsværktøjet.

Artikel II inkluderede ti eksperter og 23 novicer. Otte elementer i det oprindelige LISA scoringsværktøj var i stand til at skelne mellem eksperter og novicer. Disse otte elementer blev brugt til at etablere et modificeret scoringsværktøj med en minimumsscore på 8 point og en maksimumscore på 40 point. Det modificerede scoringsværktøj havde høj test-retest-reliability, internal consistency og god inter-rater-reliability. Beståelsesscoren blev fastsat til 39/40 point i overensstemmelse med den laveste kvartil for eksperternes præstationer. Novicerne brugte 4 til 9 forsøg på at opnå beståelsesscoren, med en median [IQR] på 6 [5-7] forsøg.

Artikel III udviklede den standardiserede tilgang til non-farmakologisk behandling ved LISA proceduren inklusiv en detaljeret beskrivelse af NONA-LISA forsøget. NONA-LISA forsøget er et multicenter, blindet, randomiseret kontrolleret forsøg, der inkluderer nyfødte børn, der opfylder kriterierne for LISA. Forsøget sammenligner intravenøs præmedicinering i form af saltvand med fentanyl i en dosis på 0.5-1.0 mkg/kg. Det primære effektmål er behovet for invasiv ventilation via en endotrakeal tube i en kumuleret varighed på 30 minutter eller mere inden for 24 timer efter LISA proceduren.

Artikel IV inkluderede 17 præmature børn født på de to oprindelige NONA-LISA inklusionssites. En COMFORTneo score ≥ 14 (vurderet under proceduren) blev observeret hos tre ud af ni børn (33%) i saltvandsgruppen og fire ud af otte børn (50%) i fentanylgruppen. Yderligere fentanyl blev administreret intravenøst til to nyfødte i saltvandsgruppen med en COMFORTneo score ≥ 14 . Derudover blev alle nyfødte med en forhøjet COMFORTneo score tilstrækkeligt håndteret ved at pausere proceduren og fokusere på den non-farmakologiske behandling. Ingen bivirkninger relateret til NONA-LISA forsøget blev rapporteret.

Konklusion: Denne afhandling beskriver de omfattende forberedelser til NONA-LISA forsøget. De individuelle studieresultater kan forbedre træning, kompetencer og non-farmakologisk behandling ved LISA proceduren. Resultaterne fra det større NONA-LISA forsøg er efterspurgt, og vi vurderer, at det er sikkert og gennemførligt at fortsætte forsøget.

BACKGROUND

Prematurity and primary surfactant deficiency

Surfactant is produced late in foetal development, typically after 34 weeks of gestation. Surfactant consists of lipids and proteins naturally produced in the lungs. It reduces the alveolar surface tension, diminishes the work of breathing, and helps to keep the lungs aerated by allowing pulmonary gas exchange. Premature infants, especially those born before 28 completed weeks of gestation, are prone to primary surfactant deficiency with the need for exogenous surfactant therapy.⁵ Primary surfactant deficiency is a significant cause of neonatal respiratory distress syndrome (RDS), which remains a significant cause of neonatal mortality and respiratory morbidity in preterm infants.⁶⁻⁸ Neonatal RDS usually develops during the first 24 hours of birth.⁶ The main clinical signs are desaturation and increased work of breathing, both of which require increasing continuous positive airway pressure (CPAP) and supplemental oxygen to maintain normoxia.⁹

The role of surfactant administration in the management of RDS

Administering antenatal steroids when expecting preterm labour and using CPAP in the delivery room have improved the outcomes associated with neonatal RDS. In 1989, surfactant was administered for the first time via an ETT in Denmark. This procedure was called Intubate-Surfactant-Extubate (INSURE) and was first described by Verder et al.¹⁰ Subsequent studies demonstrated a significant impact of surfactant therapy on mortality and long-term respiratory morbidity in preterm infants with surfactant deficiency and RDS,^{11,12} and surfactant therapy remains a cornerstone intervention for preterm infants with RDS.^{9,13} Fig. 1 illustrates the effect of INSURE, showing a chest X-ray of an infant with severe RDS before (to the left) and after (to the right) surfactant administration. Importantly, diagnosing RDS and evaluating the treatment effect of surfactant therapy currently rely on clinical assessments and the fraction of inspired oxygen (FiO₂) instead of radiographic findings.⁹

The INSURE approach implies positive pressure ventilation, increasing the risk of ventilation-induced lung injury (bronchopulmonary dysplasia; BPD). This technique was further refined by Kribs et al.¹⁴ and Dargaville et al.,¹⁵ suggesting administering surfactant via a thin catheter to spontaneously breathing infants on CPAP to reduce invasive ventilation.¹⁶ This procedure is called Less Invasive Surfactant Administration (LISA)¹⁷ or Minimally Invasive Surfactant Therapy (MIST).¹⁵

Fig. 1 From Verder H et al., Surfactantbehandling af respiratorisk distress-syndrom. Ugeskr Læger (2021). <https://ugeskriftet.dk/videnskab/surfaktantbehandling-af-respiratorisk-distress-syndrom>.¹⁸ Permission for reuse in this thesis by the first author and under the Creative Commons License: CC BY-NC-ND 4.0: <https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-nc-nd/4.0/deed.da>

Less Invasive Surfactant Administration (LISA)

A recent state-of-the-art review summarised the evidence base, including the unknowns, for the LISA procedure.¹⁹ During LISA, a thin catheter is introduced orally and placed below the vocal cords using laryngoscopy for intratracheal surfactant administration in spontaneously breathing premature infants.^{12,20} Once the catheter is correctly placed in the trachea and the infant has a sufficient respiratory drive, surfactant administration can be completed within 1–2 minutes, after which the catheter is removed.^{9,20} Maintaining spontaneous breathing allows the surfactant to be distributed to the alveoli without exposure to positive pressure ventilation, thereby minimising the risk of lung injury.^{21,22}

The scientific concept of LISA

Recent randomised controlled trials have provided evidence that LISA reduces the need for invasive ventilation during the first 72 hours after the procedure and until discharge compared to surfactant administration via an ETT (NINSAPP²³) or continuation of CPAP (AMV,¹⁶ CaLi,²⁴ and OPTIMIST-A²⁵). Reviews have demonstrated a reduction in intraventricular haemorrhage

incidence, invasive ventilation, and BPD following LISA compared to other noninvasive ventilation techniques.^{22,26} Two-year follow-up data from the OPTIMIST-A trial demonstrated improved pulmonary outcomes, reduced re-hospitalization rates due to respiratory illness, and reduced need for bronchodilator therapy.²⁷ Furthermore, 2-year follow-up data from the AMV trial demonstrated no negative effects on neurodevelopmental outcomes following LISA, concluding that LISA is safe.²⁸ Consensus guidelines in Europe, UK, and Canada now identify LISA as the preferred method for surfactant delivery in premature infants with RDS despite optimised noninvasive ventilation.²⁹⁻³¹ LISA is now widely used in neonatal intensive care units (NICUs) globally.^{1,32,33}

The current uncertainties of LISA

While the optimal mode of noninvasive respiratory support for LISA is still being investigated,³⁴ nasal CPAP remains the most used.¹ However, procedural variations exist, including the type of catheter,³⁵⁻³⁷ and the use of video vs conventional laryngoscopy.^{38,39}

The use of analgesic or sedating premedication (e.g., fentanyl, propofol, ketamine, and morphine) in LISA is debated.^{40,41} The basis for this discussion is the delicate balance between achieving acceptable comfort versus over-sedating the infant, leading to insufficient respiratory drive and hypoventilation,^{42,43} which may hinder the LISA procedure and impose positive pressure ventilation, potentially harmful to the surfactant-deficient lung.^{19,44} Some studies advocate the routine use of premedication,⁴⁵ others suggest using premedication if non-pharmacological methods are insufficient to maintain procedural comfort,^{19,40} and some suggest an individualised approach based on age and appearance.^{42,46} Observational data suggest that the complexity of performing LISA is unaffected by whether opiated drugs are used or not.⁴⁷

Non-pharmacological comfort care during LISA

Non-pharmacological comfort care in the NICU is complex and multifactorial and requires awareness from all individuals involved in patient care to be successful, including neonatal nurses, neonatologists, and parents. The key to individualised comfort care is appropriate observation of the infant's signs of distress and pain and being able to discriminate these from a clinically deteriorating condition or adverse effects associated with pharmacology.⁴⁸

The assessment of procedural pain and distress

An infant apparently "tolerating" stress or pain may have reached a state of complete exhaustion.⁴⁹ Hence, the infant dissociates, enters an energy-conserving mode, and gives the false impression of tolerating the painful procedure. Various physiological responses to stress and pain have been

identified, including changes in heart rate, respiration rate, and blood pressure caused by stimulation of the sympathetic nervous system through the hypothalamus-pituitary-adrenal axis. Behavioural signs of pain and distress include facial expressions, body movements, and changes in body tonus. These responses have been included in various assessment scales for infants.⁵⁰ The Behavioural Indicators of Infant Pain (BIIP),⁵¹ Premature Infant Pain Profile (PIPP),⁵² PIPP revised (PIPP-R),^{53,54} and most recently, the Astrid Lindgren and Lund Children's Hospitals Pain and Stress Assessment Scale for Preterm and Sick Newborn Infants (ALPS-Neo)⁵⁵ have been validated for assessment of procedural pain.⁵⁶ In contrast, the COMFORTneo was initially validated for ongoing pain,⁵⁷ but studies have confirmed that the COMFORTneo score can be used to assess pain and discomfort during video recordings of the LISA procedure.^{58,59}

The importance of standardising non-pharmacological comfort care for LISA

A variety of non-pharmacological strategies to minimise stress and pain have been suggested, and several studies have shown synergy when combining several non-pharmacological measures.⁶⁰ Most LISA experts worldwide use one or more non-pharmacological comfort care strategies for LISA,¹ and studies investigating procedural pain or discomfort have successfully applied these (e.g., oral sucrose or mother's milk^{61,62} and swaddling/facilitated tucking^{63,64}) also for the LISA procedure.⁶⁵ However, no clinical trial have evaluated a standardised approach to non-pharmacological comfort care during LISA guided by continuous assessment of pain. A standardised non-pharmacological approach has the potential to avoid detrimental analgesic or sedating premedication without increasing the infant's level of pain and distress and may help to achieve the full potential of LISA.

Educational gaps in LISA training

LISA is included in the European Technical Skills Curriculum in Neonatology,⁶⁶ but many NICUs adhere to the apprenticeship model for LISA training without a formalised simulation-based training (SBT) programme.^{1,38,39} In the apprenticeship model, the operator practices on infants in the NICU under the supervision of an experienced LISA operator. However, due to the relatively small number of infants eligible for LISA and the implementation of SBT at many centres, the apprenticeship model may be considered inappropriate.¹ SBT is now the recommended method for acquiring LISA competence and improving LISA success rates, as it can be achieved in a safe environment without harming the patient.^{20,66-68}

The role of curriculum development in enhancing LISA competency

David E. Kern originally proposed a Six-Step Approach to curriculum development, including 1) Problem identification and general needs assessment, 2) Targeted needs assessment, 3) Formulation of goals and objectives, 4) Development of educational strategies, 5) Implementation, and 6) Evaluation and feedback.^{69,70} These six domains in curriculum development are interconnected in an ongoing and evolving process as new treatment options or educational modalities arise and is illustrated in Fig. 2.^{69,71}

Within healthcare, the Delphi process is a structured group facilitation method using iterative survey questionnaires to extract valuable expert opinions.⁷² This process can establish consensus on general^{66,73} or specific needs assessments,¹ an assessment tool,¹ and guidelines.⁷⁴ The name "Delphi" relates to the ancient Greek Oracle of Delphi as the symbol of seeking advice from knowledgeable sources on complex issues with limited empirical evidence.⁷⁵ This process builds on participant anonymity to limit the influence of individuals,⁷⁶ electronic survey distribution to facilitate participation from diverse geolocations, and personal invitations combined with scheduled reminders to limit non-response bias.

Fig. 2 From Nayahangan LJ, Clementsen PF, Doubleday A, Riddle J, Annema JT, Konge L. Developing a simulation-based training curriculum in transesophageal ultrasound with the use of the endobronchial ultrasound-endoscope. *Endosc Ultrasound* (2022).⁷¹ DOI: [10.4103/EUS-D-21-00126](https://doi.org/10.4103/EUS-D-21-00126), Nayahangan et al. adapted the figure from Thomas PA, Kern DE, Hughes MT, et al. *Curriculum Development for Medical Education: A Six-Step Approach*. John Hopkins

The impact of skills assessment on LISA competency

Like most professions, medical doctors' self-assessments of their clinical performance are unreliable.⁷⁷ In technical skills training, formulating measurable objectives (e.g., an assessment tool) and establishing a minimum passing score is crucial to ensure that all trainees meet the required skill level for safe clinical practice.⁷⁸ Ongoing (formative) assessments with feedback and final (summative) assessments to evaluate learning outcomes against a predefined minimum passing score can be embedded in the mastery learning model. In this model, LISA operators practice with feedback until they achieve a predefined minimum passing score before advancing to supervised training in the clinical setting.^{78,79}

The interpretation of test scores must be supported by validity evidence to establish a reliable minimum passing score. Messick's framework is recommended by the American Educational Research Association and considered the gold standard for evaluating and reporting validity evidence.^{80,81} It includes five different sources of validity evidence: 1) Content evidence, 2) Response process, 3) Internal structure, 4) Relations to other variables, and 5) Consequences of testing.⁸¹ *Content evidence* focuses on the degree to which an assessment tool metrics represent the technical skill it is intended to measure. A modified Delphi process can be used as a comprehensive way to achieve expert consensus on selecting items to be included in an assessment tool.¹ *The response process* focuses on eliminating all sources of error during test administration and data collection. *Evidence of internal structure* focuses on the relationship between specific items in an assessment tool, considering test-retest reliability, internal consistency, and inter-rater reliability. Test-retest reliability refers to the reliability of an assessment tool over time and reflects the variation in scores on the same subject under the same conditions. Internal consistency refers to the reliability across metrics on an assessment tool (e.g., laryngoscopy and catheterization), ensuring that they measure the same underlying concept (LISA competence). Inter-rater reliability assesses the degree of agreement between raters on the same subject under the same conditions, which is essential when the assessment involves human judgment.

Generalizability theory (G-study) extends beyond the traditional concepts of internal structure described above. It can be used to evaluate an assessment tool's overall reliability (or generalizability) across different sources of variability (or facets) and study the contribution of each of these facets to the overall degree of error.^{82,83} Afterwards, decision studies (D-studies) are conducted to provide recommendations to reduce the overall degree of error and improve the

reliability of the scores. For example, the D-study can provide a recommendation for a specific number of observers or performances to increase the reliability of the scores. The relationship to other variables focuses on the relationships between the assessment scores and theoretically related characteristics (e.g., expert/novice).⁸⁴ Evidence regarding the consequences typically focuses on establishing a minimum passing score that results in as few false positives (passing novices) and false negatives (non-passing experts) as possible.

AIMS

This thesis aims to describe the preparations for the NONA-LISA trial to improve training, procedural competency, and non-pharmacological comfort care for the LISA procedure.

Hypotheses

- Paper I. Through an iterative Delphi process involving LISA experts, international consensus can be achieved on a training curriculum for LISA operators and an assessment tool to evaluate LISA competence.
- Paper II. Using Messick's framework, validity evidence will support using the LISA-AT scores to train new LISA operators to a minimum passing score in the simulated setting.
- Paper III. It is possible to design a safe, randomised, controlled trial to investigate the effect of premedication with fentanyl compared to saline in preterm infants born before 30 completed weeks of gestation treated with LISA.
- Paper IV. It is safe and feasible to perform the standardised non-pharmacological comfort care during the LISA procedure, blind the use of premedication, and include patients via deferred consent.

SUMMARY OF PAPERS

Paper I

Aim: Paper I aimed to achieve expert consensus on the LISA-CUR and the LISA-AT to standardise LISA training and assessment of operator competence.

Methods: Paper I was a global three-round Delphi process conducted from February to July 2022 to obtain expert opinions and consensus on the content of the LISA-CUR and LISA-AT. LISA experts were defined as LISA operators with expertise in one or more: research, curriculum development, or clinical education relevant to the LISA procedure. Experts were identified using the steering committee members' professional network and through online advertisement on the European Society for Paediatric Research's website to increase representation from other countries. Round 1 was a brainstorming phase to collect and organise expert opinions to identify relevant items for the LISA-CUR and LISA-AT. Round 2 rated the importance of each item and excluded items supported by less than 80% consensus. Round 3 assessed expert consensus for the final LISA-CUR and LISA-AT.

Results: Paper I achieved global participation in round 1, which included 153 experts from 14 countries. Most experts were board-certified neonatologists (97%) and involved in clinical education relevant to the LISA procedure (87%), while participants with expertise in LISA research and curriculum development were also represented (48% and 56%). Rounds 2 and 3 achieved a response rate of >80%. Forty-four and 22 items were identified in round 1 for the LISA-CUR and LISA-AT, respectively. According to the predefined consensus threshold, 15 and seven items were excluded in round 2 for the LISA-CUR and LISA-AT, and response anchors were suggested for the remaining items of the LISA-AT. In round 3, the final LISA-CUR and LISA-AT, consisting of 29 and 15 items, were accepted among the experts.

Conclusion: Paper I resulted in a global consensus on a LISA-CUR and LISA-AT that can be used with existing educational strategies to standardise LISA training and assess operator competence.

Paper II

Aim: Paper II aimed to assess validity evidence gathered using Messick's framework to support using the LISA-AT scores for training and assessing LISA operators.

Methods: Paper II was a simulation study that included LISA experts (senior staff neonatologists at two Danish NICUs) and novices (medical students and young medical doctors with no prior experience in the LISA, INSURE, or intubation procedure). Data were collected during a pretest (experts and novices performed one LISA scenario), a first training round (experts and novices performed two LISA scenarios), and a second training round (novices trained until they achieved the minimum passing score in two consecutive LISA scenarios). Familiarisation was allowed before the pretest. After the pretest, all participants watched a step-by-step LISA demonstration video. Items that discriminated between the experts' and novices' performances in the first training round formed a modified LISA-AT. Test-retest reliability, internal consistency, and inter-rater reliability were evaluated based on the groups' performances in the first training round. The minimum passing score was the lowest quartile of the experts' performances in the first training round. Learning curves were established for the novices' performances and used to calculate the training costs according to the micro-costing procedure. Finally, generalisability theory (G-study) was used to evaluate the LISA-AT scores' reliability across two facets (performance and participant number), and decision studies (D-studies) were used to suggest modifications to the facets, which could improve the reliability.

Results: Paper II included ten experts and 23 novices. Eight out of 15 metrics on the original LISA-AT discriminated between the groups in the first training round and constituted the modified LISA-AT with a range of 8-40 points. The modified LISA-AT had high test-retest reliability (Spearman's $\rho = 0.87$), internal consistency (Cronbach's $\alpha = 0.88$), and good inter-rater reliability (Cronbach's $\alpha = 0.82$). The minimum passing score was established at 39/40 points according to the lowest quartile of the experts' performances, which resulted in zero passing novices and four non-passing experts. The novices used 4-9 attempts to reach the minimum passing score, with a median [IQR] of 6 [5-7] attempts. However, their laryngoscopy skills and procedural time remained significantly different compared to the expert group. The training costs per novice to achieve the minimum passing score were USD 68, ranging from USD 45-102 (EUR 62, ranging from EUR 39-94, according to the European Central Bank). The G-study demonstrated a G-coefficient of 0.73, indicating a moderate-good level of reliability, and the D-studies demonstrated that nine performances assessed by a single rater would be sufficient to obtain a G-coefficient >0.80 .

Conclusion: Paper II demonstrated robust validity evidence according to Messick's framework for using the LISA-AT scores to train new LISA operators and assess their competence in the simulated

setting. This is paramount before the LISA operator is upgraded to training in the clinical setting with supervision to improve their laryngoscopy skills and time further.

Paper III

Aim: Paper III aimed to design a safe, randomised, controlled trial to investigate the effect of premedication with fentanyl compared to saline in preterm infants born before 30 completed weeks of gestation treated with the LISA procedure.

Population, Intervention, Comparison, Outcome, Timepoint: Paper III is the protocol article for the NON-pharmacological Approach to LISA (NONA-LISA) trial (registered on www.ClinicalTrials.gov, NCT05609877, on October 18th, 2022). The study population is preterm infants born before 30 completed weeks of gestation at the trial sites, meeting the criteria for LISA as the first-choice method for surfactant treatment: need for $FiO_2 > 0.30$ despite CPAP ≥ 6 cm H₂O. The intervention is intravenous premedication with isotonic saline compared to fentanyl 0.5-1.0 mcg/kg. The primary outcome is the need for invasive ventilation via an ETT for a cumulated duration of 30 minutes or more within 24 hours of the LISA procedure. Data on secondary outcomes will be collected during the procedure and until hospital discharge. Both groups will receive a standardised approach to non-pharmacological comfort care guided by a modified COMFORTneo score performed in real-time. If the modified COMFORTneo score is ≥ 14 during the procedure, the staff should pause and adjust non-pharmacological comfort care. If this is insufficient to reduce the infant's level of pain or distress, open-label fentanyl can be administered intravenously at the clinician's discretion.

Randomisation and blinding: The NONA-LISA trial will randomly assign infants to the saline or fentanyl groups in a 1:1 ratio using a computer-generated randomisation sequence with permuted blocks of varying sizes stratified for gestational age and trial site. Researchers, clinical staff, and the infant's legal guardians will be blinded to the treatment allocation.

Sample size estimation and safety: The NONA-LISA trial will include 324 infants, assuming an incidence of the primary outcome of 45% in the fentanyl group and 30% in the saline group, with an alpha of 0.05 and a power of 0.80. An independent Data Management and Ethical Committee has been established, and safety analyses will be performed as appropriate to ensure participant safety.

Perspectives: The NONA-LISA trial may provide evidence for the routine use of a standardised approach to non-pharmacological comfort care as opposed to fentanyl as premedication to reduce the need for invasive ventilation via an ETT. These results may provide clarity on one of the current uncertainties of LISA.

Paper IV

Aim: Paper IV aimed to assess the feasibility of providing standardised non-pharmacological comfort care guided by the modified COMFORTneo score during the LISA procedure.

Furthermore, this paper evaluated the use of open-label intravenous fentanyl, the ability to blind the treatment allocation, and the feasibility of enrolling infants via deferred consent.

Methods: Paper IV was a feasibility study randomising infants born before 30 completed weeks of gestation to receive saline or fentanyl 0.5-1 mcg/kg intravenously as blinded premedication for LISA according to the NONA-LISA trial design. Both groups received the standardised approach to non-pharmacological comfort care. To assess the possibility of blinding the clinical staff to the treatment allocation, Paper IV randomly assigned the treatment allocations to a blue or red syringe, which is not included in the NONA-LISA's original trial design. After the procedure, the clinical staff were asked to indicate which treatment arm they anticipated. Furthermore, Paper IV collected feedback from the neonatologists and neonatal nurses through an online questionnaire.

Results: Paper IV included infants from the NICUS at Copenhagen University Hospital, Rigshospitalet, and Aarhus University Hospital, Skejby Hospital, from September 1st, 2023, until the large NONA-LISA trial was initiated on June 1st, 2024. In this period, 99 infants born before 30 completed weeks of gestation were screened of whom 20 were eligible. Because the trial medication was unavailable on weekends, 18 infants were randomised (nine infants were allocated to each treatment group). All infants' legal guardians consented except one, who was not proficient in English or Danish and could not give truly informed consent. Data were collected from all 17 included infants, corresponding to an inclusion rate of 85%. Infants had a median [IQR] gestational age of 28 [26-29] weeks, 77% were male, birth weight was 950 [826-1,055] grams, and a 5-minute Apgar score was 10 [9-10]. The median [IQR] time from fulfilling the inclusion criteria to procedure start was 30 [28-60] minutes, and the median [IQR] FiO₂ at procedure start was 0.38 [0.35-0.45]. Three of nine infants in the saline group and four of eight infants in the fentanyl group had a modified COMFORTneo score ≥ 14 , most frequently occurring during laryngoscopy (53% for the total population). Most cases were successfully handled by pausing the procedure and adjusting

non-pharmacological comfort care. Two infants from the saline group received open-label fentanyl 0.5 mcg/kg intravenously. The staff responsible for patient care correctly identified saline in six of nine infants but administered naloxone to five, and fentanyl in six of eight infants and administered naloxone to four. No adverse events, harms, or unintended effects related to the trial intervention were reported (see “Methods and Materials”). The clinical staff completed the survey questionnaire for 13 (81%) of the included infants. The most frequent complaint was the time required to randomise the infant in the Research Electronic Data Capture (REDCap) system, and the staff were concerned that their limited exposure to the treatment intervention may have affected their ability to provide the standardised approach to non-pharmacological comfort care.

Conclusions: Performing the LISA procedure with saline and standardised non-pharmacological comfort care guided by the modified COMFORTneo score is feasible. Pausing the procedure and adjusting non-pharmacological comfort care was sufficient to complete the procedure in most infants with a modified COMFORTneo score ≥ 14 . Considering the staff's ability to correctly identify saline in 2/3 and fentanyl in 3/4 infants could indicate that the blinding procedure was not working perfectly. However, the frequent use of naloxone in the saline group indicates that a correct guess was likely a result of hindsight, which did not influence the LISA procedure itself. The blinding aspect will be essential to monitor during the study. No adverse events, harms, or unintended effects were reported in either group. The infants' legal guardians responded positively to inclusion via deferred consent. In the future, we will rely more on certified translators to increase the inclusion rate. Based on the feedback from the clinical staff, we have changed the user interface of the randomisation system to improve functionality while maintaining the integration with the REDCap system, making it easier and faster to randomise infants for the NONA-LISA trial. Furthermore, we have developed a teaching video and clinical demonstration video available in English, aiming to improve the staff's capability of providing non-pharmacological comfort care, improving standardisation and quality of care between and within trial sites. In summary, continuing the NONA-LISA trial is feasible and safe, and future efforts should focus on including more trial sites.

METHODS AND MATERIALS

This section will present the ethical considerations, the study designs and methodological considerations, data collection and management, statistical analyses, and the role of the PhD student for all four studies.

Ethics

The Committee on Health Research Ethics in the Capital Region of Denmark waived ethical approval for Studies I and II (protocol numbers 21051793 and 22031294). The Committee on Health Research Ethics in the Region of Southern Denmark reviewed and approved the NONA-LISA trial protocol (relevant for Study III) for “deferred consent” (approval number H-21078489).³ Justification for inclusion via deferred consent with an opt-out approach is available in the appendix for Paper III.³ Participation in any parts of the data collection for the conducted studies was voluntary and unpaid, and all the included participants or infants’ legal guardians provided electronic informed consent. The Danish Data Protection Agency approved the data management plan for all the studies (P-2022-11, P-2022-318, and P-2022-594). The NONA-LISA trial was prospectively registered at www.ClinicalTrials.gov (NCT05609877) on October 18th, 2022, before enrolling the first patient in the NONA-LISA feasibility study, reported in Paper IV.

Study design and considerations

Paper I design

Paper I was an international three-round modified Delphi process using online structured and semi-structured survey questionnaires to gather opinions from LISA experts (researchers, curriculum developers, and clinical educators).^{1,72} Participants were identified using the steering committee members' professional network and through online advertisement on the European Society for Paediatric Research's website to increase representation from other countries. Paper I was reported according to the Consensus-Based Checklist for Reporting of Survey Studies (CROSS).⁸⁵ We considered a response rate for each round of $\geq 70\%$ sufficient to minimise non-response error and simultaneously ensure the progression of the study. In round 1, a brainstorming phase was facilitated to identify items to be included in a LISA curriculum and the LISA-AT. In round 2, a five-point Likert scale was used by the experts to rate the importance of each item: 1) Not important at all – 5) Very important. Any item receiving a score of 4 (important) or 5 (very important) by more than 80% of the experts was included in the preliminary lists. In round 3, at least 80% of the experts should approve the curriculum and the LISA-AT for acceptance.

Paper I considerations

Several methodological questions should be considered before conducting a Delphi study or any other needs assessment. No clear recommendations exist regarding the number of panellists if considered appropriate for the specific research question.^{86,87} Some studies suggest including approximately 23 panellists to achieve response stability during multiple survey rounds.⁸⁸ However, this size may be non-representative compared to the target group or in studies aiming to achieve worldwide consensus. We did not include newly trained LISA operators or neonatal nurses, which could have helped reflect learner needs and the interdisciplinary aspects of learning and assessing competence for the LISA procedure. In Paper I, participants were defined as LISA experts using broad inclusion criteria to ensure a range of viewpoints from LISA educators, researchers, and administrators was represented. Arguably, this may have diluted the definition of an "expert" while increasing generalizability to a broader audience. To ensure expert input, we allowed the steering committee members to participate. Importantly, the research protocol strictly regulated the steering committee members' influence by specifying the rules for content analysis following round 1,⁸⁹ data analyses following round 2, and the consensus threshold in round 3. For example, items considering teaching activities and methods were omitted during content analyses as other publications already described these.²⁰ Using a 5-point Likert scale with a neutral option as we did in round 2 reduces random choices and captures uncertainty, while encouraging non-committal responses. It is essential to predefine the consensus threshold as it significantly influences the number of items in the LISA-CUR and the LISA-AT.⁷² A review from 2014 reported a median consensus threshold of 75%, ranging from 50-97%.⁹⁰ We defined consensus as an agreement of 80% or more in rounds 2 and 3. Moreover, all decisions were based on unanimity within the steering committee. The steering committee members were encouraged to nominate participants from multiple NICUs within their country to increase the diversity among participants and minimise the risk of one NICU getting excessive influence. Online advertisements aimed to include experts from countries not represented within the steering committee. However, this strategy prevented us from assessing non-response rates in the first Delphi round, which is inconvenient as non-responders may differ from responders according to their demographics and opinions, potentially impacting the reliability of the final consensus. High non-response rates are also known to happen during the Delphi process, as its iterative nature requires multiple survey rounds.⁷² In the final round, participants may be fatigued and converge towards a common viewpoint to achieve consensus and avoid subsequent rounds, thereby overlooking valid minority opinions.⁸⁶ Despite involving over 150 experts from 14

countries, Paper I successfully maintained response rates above 80% in rounds 2 and 3 through personalised invitations and multiple reminder emails.

In summary, expert consensus is valuable but does not replace empirical evidence, which should be collected during implementation and used to improve the LISA-CUR and LISA-AT.

Paper II design

Paper II was a simulation study that included LISA experts and novices at two NICUs in Denmark.²

Paper II was reported according to Messick's framework recommended by the American Educational Research Association in their Standards for Education and Psychological Testing.⁸⁰

Two onsite raters (the PhD student and a medical student) and two video raters (senior staff neonatologists) underwent rater training prior to data collection. Medical students or newly trained medical doctors and senior staff neonatologists were included in a 2:1 ratio as a convenience sample to form the novice and the expert groups. The simulated setting is shown in Fig. 3.

During data collection, two investigators were present, including one trained rater and one acting as the assisting neonatal nurses. First, all participants were allowed five minutes of familiarisation with the equipment to reduce technical errors and minimise stress. Second, all participants received a short, standardised test introduction (scenario briefing) and were asked to perform a pretest on the simulator to establish a baseline in both groups. Third, all participants watched a step-by-step demonstration video on how to perform the LISA procedure and were asked to perform two LISA scenarios without feedback to assess the effect of video-based learning alone. Items that discriminated between the groups based on the scores from the first round formed a modified LISA-AT and were used to establish the minimum passing score (see Statistical analysis). Fourth, the novice group continued practising with feedback until they achieved the minimum passing score in two consecutive attempts to ensure that the individual had consistently achieved competence in the LISA procedure. Onsite raters were used to train novices to reach the minimum passing score, as no differences were observed between the onsite and video raters' assessments of expert performances. The novices' learning curve was inspected, and the costs of simulation-based LISA training were calculated using the micro-costing approach, including four steps: 1) specification of resources used (materials, equipment, and hourly salary), 2) determination of the quantities of resources (number of utensils or hours), 3) determination of the unit costs, and 4) multiplication of the quantities and the unit costs for each type of resource.⁹¹

Fig. 3 From Breindahl N., Bay E.T., Heiring C. *et al.* Competency in the Less Invasive Surfactant Administration procedure: Validity evidence for the LISA-AT score. Submitted, under review.²

Paper II considerations

As with all research designs, methodological variations can significantly influence the results. Similarly, validity evidence varies depending on the context of its application, even when using standardised frameworks.⁹² For example, collecting validity evidence in a simulated setting focusing solely on the LISA operator will yield different results than inter-disciplinary team training involving neonatal nurses. This may explain why some metrics did not discriminate between the novices and experts.

Furthermore, the complexity and unpredictability in the clinical setting are difficult to replicate in the simulated setting, often resulting in a setup where it is too easy to demonstrate competency in the simulation setting compared to the clinical demands. For example, assessing competencies in performing laryngoscopy on a simulator with a standardised airway anatomy that lacks the full complexity of a spontaneously breathing preterm infant, may lead to a more progressive learning curve. This may result in trainees being upgraded to supervised training in the clinical setting without the necessary proficiency, which could negatively impact patient safety. Therefore, an ideal simulation environment should reflect the difficulty levels encountered in clinical practice, which may be very costly. On the contrary, gathering validity evidence in a pragmatic simulation setup that utilises affordable and available equipment is crucial to support the broader implementation of structured skills assessments using the LISA-AT. We used the Premature Anne mannequin (Laerdal Medical™, Norway, Stavanger)⁹³ and increased the simulation fidelity⁹³ and increased the simulation fidelity using the NICU's standard LISA equipment and introducing complications during the scenarios (e.g., bradycardia, desaturation, or surfactant reflux).

A recent review investigated different methods for setting the minimum passing score in SBT of surgical procedures.⁹⁴ It demonstrated that 40% of the included studies used the expert group's

mean or median score, while most used a minimum passing score below the expert level. One method is the “*contrasting groups method*”,⁹⁵ which plots the intersect between the novices’ and experts’ performances and typically results in a low minimum passing score.^{78,96} A study by Rostoker et al. recently reported validity evidence for a LISA rating scale based on the performances of six experts with an average score of 73.6% (corresponding to 36.8/50 points).⁹⁷ This score was suggested as the minimum passing score. The problem with setting an easily achievable minimum passing score is that it may be useless from a clinical perspective, as achieving a score of 37/50 on this rating scale is possible even though 13/25 metrics are “*partially completed*” (scoring 1/3) or 6/25 metrics are “*not completed*” (scoring 0/3). Arguably, this approach would not result in LISA proficiency, and promoting the operator to clinical practice may impose significant risks to the patients. On the contrary, the “*Angoff method*” uses expert opinion to set the minimum passing score,⁹⁸ which often results in an unrealistically high score, which is hard to achieve.⁹⁵ Paper II used the lowest quartile of the experts’ performances as the minimum passing score and their median score as the mastery learning level. Setting the minimum passing score based on the expert group’s performances promotes a higher level of competence compared to the contrasting groups’ method while reflecting an achievable level compared to the Angoff method, which may improve the transferability of skills proficiency to the clinical setting.

Other methodological considerations include blinding and adding a time restriction of 90 minutes maximum training time per day. Blinding could have been achieved through video ratings, but this assessment method was impractical as it could not provide the participants with real-time assessments and immediate feedback. This may have introduced experimenter bias, where the investigators behave differently between experts and novices or inexperienced or experienced novices, which can impact the assessments. This was minimised through a standardised assessment scheme, but adding a second rater could increase the reliability of assessment scores. A time restriction was introduced to prevent fatigue. However, it may have biased the investigators to provide more favourable assessments toward the end of the training session to avoid the need for scheduling an additional session with the participant.

Paper III design

Overview

Paper III was reported in Papers III-IV. Paper III was the NONA-LISA protocol article, which included comprehensive information on the trial design and methodology.³ Paper III was reported according to the Standard Protocol Items: Recommendations for Interventional Trials (SPIRIT).⁹⁹

Population, Intervention, Comparator, Outcome, Timepoint

The NONA-LISA trial is a multicentre, blinded, randomised controlled trial enrolling preterm infants born before 30 completed weeks of gestation who meet the first-choice LISA criteria⁹: $\text{FiO}_2 > 0.30$ despite $\text{CPAP} \geq 6$ cm H_2O . The NONA-LISA trial compares LISA with intravenous saline to LISA with intravenous fentanyl 0.5-1.0 mcg/kg to investigate the effect of premedication on the need for invasive ventilation, meaning manual or mechanical ventilation via an ETT, for 30 minutes or more (cumulated) within 24 hours of the LISA procedure. Exclusion criteria were defined as one or more of the following being present before randomisation: 1) suspicion of lung hypoplasia, 2) endotracheal intubation (e.g., due to severe respiratory instability requiring invasive ventilation), 3) suspicion of pneumothorax, pulmonary haemorrhage or pleural effusion, 4) major congenital anatomical anomalies.¹⁰⁰ The primary respiratory support was CPAP in both NICUs.

The LISA procedure

All LISA procedures will be performed with a video laryngoscope and a dedicated surfactant catheter for intratracheal administration of a single dose of 200 mg/kg porcine surfactant (Curosurf®, Chiesi Pharma AB, Italy). The NONA-LISA trial allows the administration of atropine, caffeine, and naloxone as indicated at the clinician's discretion. However, a loading dose of caffeine before the LISA procedure is the standard of care in Denmark, according to the existing evidence.²⁴ Regarding respiratory support for LISA, nasal CPAP is the most used worldwide,¹ and is routinely used in all Danish trial sites.

Standardising non-pharmacological comfort care for LISA

As part of developing the protocol, we conducted an iterative process using email correspondence, online meetings, and a final physical meeting to establish a Danish inter-disciplinary consensus for a standardised approach to non-pharmacological comfort care during LISA. Neonatologists and neonatal nurses with extensive experience in the Newborn Individualised Developmental Care and Assessment Program (NIDCAP),¹⁰¹ the COMFORTneo score,⁵⁷ and the Family Infant Neurodevelopmental Education (FINE) education⁴⁹ from the two founding trial sites participated. Numerous discussions on assessing procedural pain and discomfort, selecting non-pharmacological measures, and providing them resulted in a standardised approach to non-pharmacological comfort care.

This approach was later converted into a teaching video (available at <https://youtu.be/I4gKTi-Jmi0>) and a clinical demonstration video (available at <https://youtu.be/7LyELgVecZ0>).³ We selected the COMFORTneo score as the tool for assessing procedural pain and discomfort during LISA, as this

tool is included in the training curriculum for neonatal nurses in Denmark. Furthermore, previous studies have used the COMFORTneo score post-procedure to assess pain and distress during LISA.^{58,59} A COMFORTneo score between eight and 13 immediately before engaging with the procedure was necessary to ensure optimised non-pharmacological comfort care was in place. However, to perform non-pharmacological comfort care guided by the COMFORTneo score, the score must be performed in real-time during the procedure to avoid interrupting the procedure flow.³ The term "modified COMFORTneo" was used for this purpose. Vital signs and breathing patterns are not included in the original COMFORTneo score but were continuously monitored and responded to as appropriate during the LISA procedure.⁵⁷ The procedure should be paused, non-pharmacological comfort care should be adjusted, and the infant should be stimulated as a response to insufficient respiratory drive during the procedure. As a response to procedural pain or discomfort, indicated by a modified COMFORTneo score ≥ 14 ,⁵⁸ the procedure should be paused, and non-pharmacological comfort care should be adjusted. If these initial attempts are insufficient to improve tolerance, open-label fentanyl can be administered intravenously at the neonatologist's discretion.

Randomisation

The NONA-LISA trial is one of the first trials within neonatology in Denmark to obtain ethical approval for inclusion via deferred consent with an opt-out approach, meaning that informed consent will be sought from the parents or legal guardians as soon as possible *after* enrolment. All participant information materials were developed together with a parent representative.

Infants will be randomly assigned to receive saline or fentanyl as premedication for LISA in a 1:1 ratio. The randomisation sequence will be computer-generated and use permuted blocks of varying sizes stratified by gestational age at birth (\pm 28 completed weeks of gestation) and trial site. In the NONA-LISA trial, twins and triplets will be considered independent both in the randomisation procedure and the statistical analyses, as they will be enrolled based on individual clinical observations, and we expect independence between their outcomes.

Blinding

Researchers, staff involved in patient treatment, and the parents will be blinded to the treatment allocation, as staff not involved in patient care will prepare the trial medication daily in sealed syringes with similar weight and appearance. The primary analyses will be performed blinded and presented to all authors as Group A vs Group B to reduce the risk of interpretation bias. The authors will then agree on two alternative written interpretations before unblinding the primary analyses.

Secondary outcomes

Short-term secondary outcomes included the number of laryngoscopy attempts, duration of the procedure, modified COMFORTneo score before and during the procedure, and complications like desaturation, bradycardia, and surfactant reflux. Other secondary outcomes included the need for a second dose of surfactant and the incidence of invasive ventilation during NICU admission. Long-term secondary outcomes included BPD and mortality at 36 weeks postmenstrual age.

Sample size estimation and inclusion timeline

Various rates of invasive ventilation after the LISA procedure in preterm infants born before 30 completed weeks of gestation have been reported, ranging from 33-75%.^{16,23,102} We anticipated an incidence of the primary outcome of 45% and 30% for the fentanyl and saline groups, respectively. Considering an alpha of 0.05 and a power of 0.8, this trial will enrol 324 infants in a 1:1 ratio.

Safety reporting and auditing

Three independent individuals (two professors of neonatology and a data manager) agreed to join the Data Management and Ethical Committee (DMEC) responsible for monitoring the data completeness and the performance of individual trial sites to ensure participant safety. All adverse and serious adverse events will be carefully monitored and reported as appropriate to the DMEC and trial sites. Adverse events include proven or advanced necrotising enterocolitis, intraventricular haemorrhage (grades III and IV), severe retinopathy of prematurity, massive pulmonary haemorrhage and pulmonary air leak related to surfactant administration. Serious adverse events include death, permanent disability or damage, and prolonged hospitalisation closely related to the trial intervention.¹⁰³ Immediate procedure-related complications (e.g., apnoea, bradycardia, and surfactant reflux) were reported in the paper but not considered adverse events. Safety analyses will be performed as appropriate, and the DMEC may recommend terminating the trial before the intended sample size is reached for safety or ethical reasons.

Paper III considerations

The NONA-LISA trial design, including its strengths and limitations, has been discussed previously.^{3,104,105} In the early stages of designing the NONA-LISA trial, it became apparent that a pragmatic trial design allowing fentanyl dosages between 0.5-1.0 mcg/kg intravenously was necessary to ensure unanimous support from all neonatologists at the Danish trial sites. According to expert recommendations, a slow bolus infusion over 5-10 minutes of fentanyl 0.5-1 mcg/kg

intravenously seems a reasonable option for pharmacological analgesia.¹⁹ Hence, selecting this dosing interval for the NONA-LISA trial reflects clinical practice and increases the relevance for NICUs outside the NONA-LISA trial setting. However, the NONA-LISA trial was not designed nor powered to determine causality between specific fentanyl dosages and hypoventilation, which may imply difficulty when interpreting the results. As of 2024, patients are enrolled at two Danish NICUs, adhering to the same guidelines and with similar treatment strategies. However, upon including trial sites outside Denmark, other discussions related to the pragmatic trial design may arise, including but not limited to individual practices regarding pre-procedure care, video vs. conventional laryngoscope, type of surfactant catheter, and type of respiratory support before the procedure. As we expect inclusion to last three to four years, new recommendations and clinical practice guidelines may arise and prompt the discussion of indications for surfactant treatment using different modalities like gastric aspirate analysis¹⁰⁶ and focused lung ultrasound.¹⁰⁷ Prophylactic surfactant administration in the delivery room for extremely premature infants is now considered in many German NICUs.¹⁰⁸ However, if the infant has an intravenous access to administer trial medication, statistical analyses can adjust for these covariates, providing a sufficient sample size. The NONA-LISA trial uses a single surfactant dose of 200 mg/kg administered intratracheally slowly over 1-2 minutes and adapted to preserve spontaneous breathing.³ While remaining untested in clinical trials, this dosage is supported by other studies and is associated with reduced rates of mechanical ventilation and a lower need for re-intubation.¹⁰⁹

Standardising non-pharmacological comfort care for LISA

The COMFORTneo score was initially validated for a two-minute assessment of ongoing pain.⁵⁷ However, later studies have confirmed that the COMFORTneo score can also be used post-procedure to assess pain and discomfort during video recordings of the LISA procedure.^{58,59} Selecting this score as the basis for assessing pain and distress during the LISA procedure and guiding non-pharmacological comfort care also seemed reasonable, as this score is the national standard for assessment of neonatal pain and distress in Denmark. The COMFORTneo score only relies on behavioural parameters and does not consider respiratory drive for non-intubated infants and related physiological parameters (e.g., oxygen saturation and respiratory rate). This may be a limitation when assessing procedural pain, as hypoventilation (e.g., apnoea) causing changes in physiological parameters can be a strong signal of procedural pain. However, most pain scores increase with an impaired respiratory drive or desaturations, and in the NONA-LISA trial, an increased COMFORTneo score above the threshold can potentially indicate the use of open-label fentanyl. As hypoventilation can also occur from fentanyl administration, it is beneficial that

apnoea's or desaturations are not included in the COMFORTneo score but assessed and managed separately by pausing the procedure, stimulating the infant, increasing FiO₂, or similar.

Belliemi et al. argue that detecting procedural pain is more valuable than scoring it,¹¹⁰ and despite being a continuous scale, a modified COMFORTneo score ≥ 14 will be used in the NONA-LISA trial as a threshold to indicate pain or discomfort needing intervention.^{57,58} In the NONA-LISA trial, non-pharmacological comfort care should be applied before using open-label fentanyl intravenously.¹¹¹

Randomisation

In Paper III, we defined the block sizes as two and four.³ However, as suggested by the statistician from the DMEC, we chose block sizes of four and six for Paper IV and the NONA-LISA trial to secure blinding according to the principle of “proper concealed allocation”. We maintained the group sizes as small as possible to prevent unequal distributions of infants in each treatment allocation towards the end of the trial. Similar to other multicentre studies, gestational age and trial site were selected as stratification factors at the randomisation stage to ensure that extremely preterm and very preterm infants and infants from various trial sites were evenly distributed across the treatment allocations, which has been done previously.¹¹² ‘Gestational age’ was selected as a stratification factor, as other trials have demonstrated significant interactions between gestational age and treatment group for mortality and the incidence of invasive ventilation.²⁵ ‘Trial site’ was included as the other stratification factor to minimise bias resulting from site-related variability due to variations in clinical practice, which may be even more critical as we include other trial sites outside Denmark.

Enrolling twins and triplets in clinical trials presents statistical challenges, as outcomes might be correlated due to shared genetic and environmental factors.¹¹³ If their outcomes are correlated, individual randomisation violates the basic assumption of independent observations in statistical analyses. However, this was not considered relevant for the NONA-LISA trial. Other neonatal trials have used complex statistical analyses to estimate the theoretical possibility of correlation of outcomes within a twin ‘cluster’.¹¹⁴ It should also be considered whether individual randomisation is ethically appropriate, as the legal guardians and adult twins often prefer randomisation to the same treatment allocation in neonatal trials.¹¹⁵ The NONA-LISA trial received ethical approval for individual randomisation, as all infants will receive surfactant via the LISA method and the standardised non-pharmacological comfort care, including assessment of procedural pain and distress.

Blinding

Most LISA studies are not blinded, as they typically evaluate and compare the effect of LISA, INSURE, CPAP or other treatment strategies, which is practically impossible to blind. However, blinding the NONA-LISA trial maintains the reliability of the results by ensuring the integrity of the randomisation and reducing bias. The investigators and staff providing care for the infants are blinded to the study arms, as the allocation sequence will be computer-generated, and the trial medication will be prepared in syringes by staff *not* directly involved in patient care or the LISA procedure. This will minimise the risk of detection bias resulting from unblinded assessment of outcome data and performance bias, which may result from unblinded assessment of pain or discomfort during the LISA procedure. However, the nature of the intervention (saline vs fentanyl) arguably makes it challenging to blind the staff to the study arms. Therefore, Paper IV will investigate the blinding potential of the intervention.

Sample size estimation and inclusion timeline

The sample size calculation for the NONA-LISA trial is based on the primary outcome, i.e. invasive ventilation via an ETT for a cumulated duration of 30 minutes or more during the first 24 hours after the procedure as a surrogate measure for LISA success. According to scientific custom, we have selected a significance level of 0.05, thereby allowing a 5% risk of type 1 error in the sample size calculation. When interpreting the results, the confidence interval around the point estimate will be considered.¹¹⁶

The inclusion timeline was based on Danish numbers, assuming an inclusion rate of 80% of all preterm infants born before 30 completed weeks of gestation treated with surfactant.¹¹⁷ However, while most infants will receive surfactant using the LISA method at the four NONA-LISA trial sites in Denmark, premature birth can be sudden. Some infants will receive surfactant using the INSURE method at other NICUs before transfer to a NONA-LISA trial site or may be too unstable to receive surfactant via the LISA method at the trial site. Achieving an inclusion rate corresponding to 80% of all Danish infants born before 30 completed weeks of gestation requiring surfactant may not be possible and require the inclusion of more NONA-LISA trial sites in the future to achieve the sample size within the expected three to four years.^{4,104,105}

Various secondary outcomes are also essential when evaluating the NONA-LISA trial results. Table 1 presents power calculations for some of these secondary outcomes based on two published randomised trials comparing the effect of premedication vs control for LISA. In the trial by Dekker et al. (2018),⁵⁸ 78 infants were randomised to receive no premedication or propofol 1 mg/kg intravenously and assessed COMFORTneo score <14 as the primary outcome. Both groups

received comfort care (sucrose 24% and swaddling or facilitated tucking). In the trial by Sk et al. (2022),¹¹⁸ 34 infants were randomised to receive no premedication or fentanyl 1 mcg/kg intravenously and assessed PIPP-R score <12 as the primary outcome. Both trials assessed their primary outcome using video recordings of the infant.

For the NONA-LISA trial, these secondary outcomes are only considered exploratory since only COMFORTneo score ≥ 14 and desaturation during the procedure may be sufficiently powered at a 5% alfa level. Furthermore, adjusting the significance level for multiple testing using Bonferroni, Hochberg, or other correction factors would be necessary to draw any conclusions based on the results from the secondary outcomes, which would decrease their power even more.¹¹⁹ Trying to conclude these secondary outcomes would increase the risk of finding a correlation for any of the outcomes when none exists (type I error) and simultaneously increase the risk of failing to detect a difference due to insufficient power (type II error).¹²⁰ We will only draw conclusions based on one primary outcome to avoid type I and II errors in the NONA-LISA trial.

Table 1. Power calculations for selected secondary outcomes.

Outcome	Assumption on incidence in the intervention group (%)	Assumption on incidence in the control group (%)	Sample size
COMFORTneo score ≥ 14 during the procedure	S1: 10/42 (24) S2: 2/17 (12)	S1: 28/36 (78) S2: 9/17 (53)	S1: 24 S2: 38
Desaturation during the procedure	S1: 38/42 (91) S2: 7/17 (41)	S1: 25/36 (69) S2: 5/17 (29)	S1: 102 S2: 494
Bradycardia during the procedure	S1: 9/42 (21) S2: 2/17 (12)	S1: 5/35 (14) S2: 2/17 (12)	S1: 922 S2: N/A
Invasive ventilation within 24 (S1) or 72 hours (S2)	S1: 10/42 (24) S2: 2/17 (12)	S1: 6/36 (17) S2: 1/17 (6)	S1: 1,042 S2: 712
Bronchopulmonary dysplasia	S1: - S2: 5/17 (31)	S1: - S2: 3/17 (19)	S1: N/A S2: 406
Mortality	S1: 1/42 (2) S2: 1/17 (6)	S1: 1/36 (3) S2: 1/17 (6)	S1: 7,650 S2: N/A

Legend: All calculations are based on a 5% alfa level and a power of 80%. Literature references for the assumptions in columns two and three are presented in the table. Scenario 1 presents incidences from Dekker et al (2018).⁵⁸ Scenario 2 presents incidences from Sk et al. (2022).¹¹⁸

Safety reporting and auditing

As already mentioned, safety analyses will be performed as appropriate. Other studies use statistical methods to adjust the confidence intervals and p-values at each interim analysis to decide whether the trial should be terminated early.¹²¹ However, we have decided not to prespecify any interim analysis to avoid false rejection of the null hypothesis caused by an insufficient sample size.¹²²

Paper IV design

Overview

Paper IV was the NONA-LISA feasibility study utilising the same study design as described for Paper III but with different outcomes and an additional blinding procedure described below. Paper IV included infants from two Danish NICUs, where the clinical staff was accustomed to administering fentanyl as premedication for LISA, and was reported according to the Consolidated Standards of Reporting Trials (CONSORT) Statement.¹²³ Data collection was conducted in adherence to the NONA-LISA trial. Additionally, a survey questionnaire including structured and semi-structured questions was sent to all neonatologists and neonatal nurses involved in the intervention.

Feasibility outcomes

Feasibility outcomes were defined specifically for Paper IV. The safety and feasibility of performing non-pharmacological comfort care guided by the modified COMFORTneo score were evaluated by the incidence of infants with a modified COMFORTneo score ≥ 14 during the procedure and administration of open-label fentanyl intravenously during the procedure. This information was collected from the post-procedure form, supported by the clinical staff's feedback from an electronic survey questionnaire. The ability to blind the use of premedication was evaluated by the incidence of procedures where the clinical staff could unblind the premedication, which was collected from the post-procedure form. The feasibility of enrolling infants via deferred consent using an opt-out approach was evaluated by the inclusion rates and legal guardians' reactions to inclusion via deferred consent when approached by the investigators.

Blinding the use of premedication

In Paper IV, the randomisation procedures were identical to Paper III. After entering information on inclusion and exclusion criteria and stratification factors, the infant was randomised to a blue or red syringe for intravenous administration of trial medication. To assess the possibility of blinding the use of fentanyl or saline as premedication, Paper IV implied an additional blinding procedure. During the data collection for Paper IV, the staff responsible for preparing the intervention medication randomly assigned saline and fentanyl to blue or red syringes. Hence, on day 1, fentanyl could be in the blue syringe and the red syringe on day 2. Two blue and two red syringes were prepared daily for rare occasions of randomising two infants within 24 hours.

Paper IV considerations

Feasibility outcomes

Paper IV did not include a power calculation, as it did not evaluate a specific intervention, but rather the safety and feasibility of performing the intervention for the fully powered NONA-LISA trial, including blinding the use of premedication for LISA, and the feasibility of including patients via deferred consent. These aspects were critical to evaluate in preparing for the NONA-LISA trial.

Blinding and randomisation procedure

The additional blinding procedure was only performed for Paper IV, as it could result in an unequal allocation of infants to the treatment allocations and potentially undermine the original power calculation, which was based on an inclusion rate of 1:1.

Due to economic restraints, we could not involve a centralised drug preparation service like a pharmacy or clinical trial unit in preparing the syringes containing trial medication. To maintain the blinding of investigators and clinical staff involved in patient care, we decided to engage a small team of staff not involved in patient care. Engaging staff in preparing blinded trial medication implies the risk that they accidentally compromise the blinding process to their colleagues (e.g., staff involved in patient care or the site investigators). Furthermore, the staff not involved in patient care is usually unavailable on weekends and public holidays, and relying on a small team increases the vulnerability to sudden schedule changes, which challenges the preparation of trial medication.

Data collection and management

All studies collected data through the REDCap system hosted at the Capital Region of Denmark.¹²⁴ Papers I and IV used online survey questionnaires for data collection, and Papers II and IV used paper forms for data collection. In Paper I, participants from mainland China received the survey as PDF files and submitted their responses by email due to restricted access to the REDCap system. All paper forms were subsequently entered into REDCap by the PhD student. Access to the online forms and datasets was restricted by password, and participants and infants in all studies were pseudonymised. Videos were processed using OBS Studio 28.0.1 and safely stored on a secure drive. Papers I, II, and IV did not use imputation of missing data.

Statistical analyses

Descriptive analyses

Descriptive analyses performed for Papers I, II, and IV are covered in this subsection to avoid repetition. Statistical analyses were performed using the software "R Studio".¹²⁵ Baseline

characteristics were presented separately for each group and the study population. Categorical variables were presented as frequencies (counts and percentages) and continuous variables as medians with interquartile ranges (IQR) for non-Gaussian distributions or as means with standard deviations (SD) for Gaussian distributions (inspected using histograms and Q-Q plots). As appropriate, analyses were performed using the Chi-squared, Mann-Whitney U, Kruskal-Wallis, and Wilcoxon sign tests. Paper II used the Hochberg method to adjust for multiple testing.^{2,126}

Paper I

Only descriptive analyses were necessary to conclude Paper I (see “Descriptive analyses”).

Paper II

The LISA-AT’s internal structure was evaluated by test-retest reliability, internal consistency, and inter-rater reliability. We used Spearman’s correlation coefficient and Intraclass Correlation Coefficients (ICC, model = two-way random-effects, type = agreement, unit = single) to calculate the test-retest reliability by comparing the participants’ total scores in the first round (two consecutive procedures without feedback).¹²⁷ Cronbach’s Alpha was used to calculate the internal consistency for all items on the LISA-AT by comparing the participants’ scores in the first round. For Spearman’s correlation coefficient and Cronbach’s Alpha, we considered a correlation of >0.80 to indicate good internal consistency.¹²⁷ ICC values below 0.5 indicated poor reliability, values between 0.50 and 0.75 indicated moderate reliability, values between 0.75 and 0.90 indicated good reliability, and any value above 0.90 to indicate excellent reliability.¹²⁷ The G-study was used to assess the overall reliability of the LISA-AT scores based on the novices’ first six performances to obtain a fully-crossed design. As only one investigator assessed the novices’ performances in round two, the only two facets of this analysis were the participant and performance numbers. The D-study was used to estimate the number of performances necessary to reach reliable assessments (i.e., G-coefficient >0.80).^{82,83} The minimum passing score and mastery learning level constituted the consequences of testing and were determined based on the lowest quartile (Q1) and the median for the experts’ performances, respectively.

Paper III

The primary analysis of the NONA-LISA trial’s results will be reported using descriptive analyses and unadjusted absolute risk difference and relative risks with 95% confidence intervals using the intention-to-treat principle. If the primary analyses reveal a significant difference between the

treatment allocations, we will calculate the number needed to treat for benefit or harm to assess the clinical significance.

We will perform a logistic regression model adjusted for the stratification factors used during randomisation and the following independent factors as covariates due to their association with assisted ventilation¹²⁸: sex, repeat doses of prenatal corticosteroids, small-for-gestational-age status, 5-min APGAR scores, illness severity at NICU admission based on the Score for Neonatal Acute Physiology (SNAP) score, and oxygenation index. In a secondary analysis, we will use the per-protocol principle, excluding infants who may have received open-label fentanyl intravenously during the LISA procedure. Adjusting for multiple testing is irrelevant in the NONA-LISA trial, since there is only one primary outcome, and the secondary outcomes will be considered exploratory (see “Paper III considerations”).¹²⁹

Paper IV

Descriptive analyses and relative risks with 95% confidence intervals were conducted using the intention-to-treat principle for all the randomised infants to support the evaluation of the NONA-LISA trial's feasibility. We expected wide confidence intervals indicative of uncertainty around the point estimates, likely resulting from the small sample size. When calculating relative risks, a continuity correction may be applied to avoid division by zero, likely resulting from the small sample size, by adding the value '0.5' to all cells in a row containing the original value '0'. All analyses were unadjusted based on the small sample size.

The role of the PhD student

The PhD student and the supervisory team developed the research protocols with valuable input from the co-authors. Data collection was a combined effort between the PhD student, co-authors, and clinical staff at the NICUs in Copenhagen and Aarhus. The PhD student performed all data analyses, except the G- and D-studies performed in Paper II, conducted by co-author AF. The PhD student authored the initial drafts of all manuscripts, which benefitted from valuable input from the supervisors and co-authors.

RESULTS

This section will present the main findings from Papers I, II, and IV, as Paper III was the NONA-LISA protocol article, which did not include any results. Baseline characteristics and detailed results are available in the appendices.

Paper I

The results are summarised in Fig. 4. In round 1, 153 experts represented 14 countries. Response rates were >80% in Delphi rounds 2 and 3. The brainstorming phase in Delphi round 1, followed by content analysis, resulted in 44 unique items for the LISA curriculum and 22 items for the LISA-AT, which were reduced to 29 items and 15 items, respectively, in Delphi round 2. Delphi round 3 established unanimous expert consensus for the curriculum and the LISA-AT.

Fig. 4 From Breindahl N., Tolsgaard M.G., Henriksen T.B. *et al.* Curriculum and assessment tool for less invasive surfactant administration: an international Delphi consensus study. *Pediatr Res* 94, 1216–1224 (2023). DOI: [10.1038/s41390-023-02621-2](https://doi.org/10.1038/s41390-023-02621-2).¹

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The experts also answered questions about their standard of care regarding LISA, and their responses supported several hypotheses. First, the use of analgesic or sedating premedication for LISA is not standardised (Fig. 5). Paper I reported that 41% of experts did not use analgesic or sedative premedication, whereas 49% used fentanyl. Other drugs like ketamine and morphine were used less frequently, and some experts used more than one type of analgesic or sedative premedication. Almost all experts (96%) used non-pharmacological measures: Swaddling/wrapping (58%), sucrose (48%), and facilitated tucking (46%). Other measures like skin-to-skin care and pre-procedure non-nutritive suctioning were also reported. Finally, the exposure to the LISA procedure per operator is low, emphasising the need for developing standardised LISA training and assessing competence (Fig. 6).

Fig. 5 Data from Breindahl N., Tolsgaard M.G., Henriksen T.B. *et al.* Curriculum and assessment tool for less invasive surfactant administration: an international Delphi consensus study. *Pediatr Res* 94, 1216–1224 (2023). DOI: [10.1038/s41390-023-02621-2](https://doi.org/10.1038/s41390-023-02621-2).¹

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Fig. 6 Data from Breindahl N., Tolsgaard M.G., Henriksen T.B. *et al.* Curriculum and assessment tool for less invasive surfactant administration: an international Delphi consensus study. *Pediatr Res* 94, 1216–1224 (2023). DOI: [10.1038/s41390-023-02621-2](https://doi.org/10.1038/s41390-023-02621-2).¹

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Paper II

This results were based on the performances of ten experts and 23 novices. Table 2 summarises the five sources of validity evidence according to Messick’s framework to support using the LISA-AT scores for training and assessing LISA operators. The cost required to train a novice to achieve the minimum passing score was USD 68, ranging from USD 45 to USD 102. In our setup, the rater’s salary was the most influential factor contributing to the increased costs.

Table 2. Sources of validity evidence to support the interpretation of LISA-AT scores using the Messick framework	
Sources of evidence	Validity evidence for the LISA-AT
Content	See Paper I.
Response process	We found no significant difference between the onsite and video assessment of the experts' performances (73 [73-73] vs 74 [72-75], $p=0.34$).
Internal structure	TRR: Spearman's rho = 0.87 and ICC = 0.81. IC: Cronbach's alpha = 0.88. IRR: Cronbach's alpha = 0.82 and ICC = 0.71. G-study: G-coefficient = 0.73. D-studies: 9 procedures assessed by one rater would be sufficient for obtaining a G-coefficient >0.80.
Relations to other variables	Eight metrics discriminated between novices and experts and formed the modified LISA-AT (range 8-40 points). Novices' and experts' median [IQR] scores in the first two attempts were 29 [26-32] vs 39 [39-40]).
Consequences	Minimum passing score: 39 points (Fig. 7). Mastery learning level: 39 points (Fig. 7). Learning curves: Median [IQR] of 6 [5-7] attempts, ranging from 4-9, was required to reach the minimum passing score. The novices' laryngoscopy skills and duration remained significantly different from the experts (median [IQR] duration for the novices was 36 seconds [27-47] compared to 20 seconds [15-26] for the experts).
Legend: The five sources of validity evidence according to the Messick framework. Abbreviations: IC = Internal Consistency, ICC = Intraclass Correlation Coefficient, IRR = Inter-Rater Reliability, IQR = Interquartile ranges, TRR = Test-retest reliability. This table contains unpublished data from Breindahl N., Bay E.T., Heiring C. <i>et al.</i> Competency in the Less Invasive Surfactant Administration procedure: Validity evidence for the LISA-AT score. Submitted, under review. ²	

Fig. 7 Data from Breindahl N., Bay E.T., Heiring C. *et al.* Competency in the Less Invasive Surfactant Administration procedure: Validity evidence for the LISA-AT score. Submitted, under review.²

Paper IV

The results to determine the feasibility outcomes of the NONA-LISA trial are presented in Table 3. From September 1st, 2023, to May 31st, 2024, 99 infants born before 30 completed weeks of gestation were screened for eligibility, and 79 infants were excluded. Out of 20 eligible infants, two infants were missed as the trial medication was unavailable on weekends. Despite the two randomisation procedures in the feasibility study, nine infants were randomised to each treatment arm. In one case, the legal guardians could not give truly informed consent due to significant language barriers. The inclusion flowchart is available in the appendices.

A modified COMFORTneo score ≥ 14 occurred in 3/9 infants in the saline group and 4/8 in the fentanyl group with a relative risk of 1.5 (95% CI: 0.47-4.76) for reaching the threshold in the fentanyl group compared to the saline group. Two infants from the saline group received open-label fentanyl 0.5 mcg/kg intravenously with a relative risk of 0.22 (95% CI: 0.01-4.04) for requiring additional fentanyl in the fentanyl group compared to the saline group.

The staff correctly guessed the treatment arm in 6/9 infants in the saline group and 6/8 infants in the fentanyl group with a relative risk of 1.13 (95% CI: 0.61-2.07) for unblinding fentanyl compared to saline. Naloxone to reverse apnoea resulting from oversedation with fentanyl was administered to 5/9 infants in the saline group and 4/8 infants in the fentanyl group. According to the procedure forms completed by the clinical staff after the procedure, the staff correctly guessed saline in all five infants in the saline group treated with naloxone. No adverse events, harms, or unintended effects closely related to the trial intervention were reported.

The clinical staff responsible for patient care completed the survey questionnaire for 13 (81%) of the included infants. The neonatologists were responsible for randomising the infant, and 33% complained about the time-consuming procedure for inexperienced or infrequent users of the REDCap system, which potentially delayed surfactant administration. The staff were concerned that the little exposure to the treatment intervention influenced their capability to provide the standardised approach to non-pharmacological comfort care. Finally, they criticised the need to report specific scores for all the metrics on the COMFORTneo score during the procedure, arguing that this data collection was unreliable. Instead, the staff suggested reporting only the total modified COMFORTneo score during the procedure.

Table 3. Feasibility results for Paper IV		
	Fentanyl (N = 8)	Saline (N = 9)
Safety		
Procedure-related complications, n (%)		
Apnoea 20 seconds or more	4 (50)	4 (44)
Apnoea requiring positive pressure ventilation	2 (25)	0 (0)
Desaturation with preductal saturation <85%	6 (75)	7 (78)
Bradycardia <100 BPM	4 (50)	3 (33)
Observed surfactant reflux	5 (62)	7 (78)
Adverse events, n (%)	0 (0)	0 (0)
Serious adverse events, n (%)	0 (0)	0 (0)
Blinding		
Expected premedication true	6 (75)	6 (67)
Naloxone to reverse apnoea, n (%)	4 (50)	5 (56)
Comfort		
Modified COMFORTneo score ≥ 14 , n (%)	4 (50)	3 (33)
Highest modified COMFORTneo score during the procedure, median [IQR]	(n = 8) 14 [12-16]	(n = 7) 12 [11-16]
Administration of open-label fentanyl intravenously during the procedure, n (%)	0 (0)	2 (22)
Legend: Selected procedure data and feasibility outcomes stratified for treatment arm (saline or fentanyl as premedication for LISA). Abbreviations: BPM = Beats Per Minute, IQR = Interquartile range. This table contains unpublished data from Breindahl N., Bay E.T., Heiring C. <i>et al.</i> Competency in the Less Invasive Surfactant Administration procedure: Validity evidence for the LISA-AT score. Submitted, under review. ²		

DISCUSSION

This section will discuss the focal points of the thesis based on the methodologies and findings from Studies I-III.

Principal findings and status on the full-scale NONA-LISA trial

This thesis describes the preparations for the NONA-LISA trial.

Paper I established international consensus on a LISA curriculum consisting of 29 unique items and a LISA-AT comprising 15 unique items with response anchors. The LISA curriculum should be combined with the existing evidence-based strategies to improve and standardise LISA training. The LISA-AT will be used consistently in training to provide data-driven feedback and assessment of operator competence until certification.

Paper II demonstrated strong validity evidence to support the interpretation of LISA-AT scores, which can be used for formative and summative assessment in simulation-based LISA training. Four to nine procedures were required for a novice to achieve the minimum passing score in the simulated setting. However, continued supervised training in the clinical setting may be necessary to achieve true expertise in the LISA procedure (e.g., laryngoscopy).

Paper III described the NONA-LISA trial protocol and developed the standardised approach to non-pharmacological comfort care in close collaboration between neonatal nurses and neonatologists from the two founding trial sites. This is one of the first studies within neonatology in Denmark to obtain approval for deferred consent using an opt-out approach.

Paper IV concluded the feasibility and safety of the treatment interventions for the NONA-LISA trial in a small sample. It was feasible to provide the standardised approach to non-pharmacological comfort care guided by the modified COMFORTneo score, and it was possible to manage most painful incidents by simply pausing the procedure and adjusting non-pharmacological comfort care. The legal guardians responded positively to inclusion via deferred consent, and we believe it is possible to blind the use of premedication during the procedure. However, all these aspects must be monitored closely during the large NONA-LISA trial. The experiences from Paper IV have been used to improve the teaching materials, procedures for randomising infants and obtaining consent, and data collection forms for the NONA-LISA trial.

The NONA-LISA trial was registered on www.ClinicalTrials.gov on October 18th, 2022. Paper IV included the first infant on September 9th, 2023, and randomised 18 infants during nine months at the two founding NONA-LISA trial sites. The large NONA-LISA trial was initiated on June 1st,

2024. Since then (5 months), 24 infants have been randomised at the two founding trial sites (17 in Copenhagen and 7 in Aarhus), corresponding to the expected average inclusion rate per month per site.³ Surprisingly, we have experienced a significantly lower flow of eligible patients at the two remaining Danish NICUs in Odense and Aalborg compared to our initial assumptions.¹¹⁷ In the spring of 2024, we organised simulation-based LISA training for neonatal nurses and neonatologists at the NICU in Odense to prepare for the NONA-LISA pilot phase starting June 1st, 2024. After five months, they are still waiting for the first eligible infant. The NICU in Aalborg has an even smaller patient flow compared to Odense. Recruiting more NONA-LISA trial sites with a sufficient number of eligible patients is paramount to ensure that the trial achieves the intended sample size before the expected completion date and to maintain quality in the intervention and data collection at the individual sites.^{104,105} We have had numerous online meetings with potential trial sites in Norway and Sweden. So far, everyone has declined to join the NONA-LISA trial, as they see it as a “step back” from their current practices, which favour analgesic or sedating premedication. This is interesting, as we have recently demonstrated that half of the LISA experts from 14 countries do not use any premedication,¹ which is generally well-tolerated,^{15,130,131} and some of the largest LISA trials prohibit the use of premedication.¹³² Finally, experts recommend using premedication only if non-pharmacological comfort care is inadequate to ensure comfort,^{19,40} which supports the interventions for the NONA-LISA trial, as open-label fentanyl can be administered intravenously at the neonatologist’s discretion. We have recently published a call for international collaboration and are now actively seeking other potential trial sites.¹⁰⁵

The NONA-LISA trial: Pragmatic evidence for clinical application

In the hierarchy of evidence, results from well-designed randomised trials represent the most robust and reliable evidence.^{133,134} Overall, the NONA-LISA is a pragmatic trial in contrast to explanatory trials.^{135,136} It investigates how LISA, with a standardised approach to non-pharmacological comfort care guided by the COMFORTneo score, affects clinical practice compared to LISA with routine analgesic or sedating premedication. Pragmatic trials are characterised by having minimal guidelines on how to use the intervention, treatment-as-usual is used for comparison (intravenous fentanyl 0.5-1.0 mcg/kg), follow-up is based on routine data already available from the electronic health records, and a primary analysis relying on the intention-to-treat principle, as described in Paper III.^{3,135} While the clinical staff was trained to comply with the standardised approach to non-pharmacological comfort care for safety reasons, they were allowed to make various treatment decisions according to their own discretion, including when to use atropine, caffeine, and naloxone,

what dose of trial medication to administer, when to administer open-label fentanyl intravenously, and which measures of non-pharmacological comfort care from the treatment guideline to improve. Including more trial sites serves the purpose of achieving the necessary sample size within the expected duration of three to four years and improves the pragmatic design. If the trial only relies on data collected at sites with experienced investigators (e.g., the founding NONA-LISA trial sites in Denmark), it could overestimate benefits and underestimate harms.¹³⁶

Maintaining blinding for the NONA-LISA trial is crucial. In Paper IV, the clinical staff correctly identified saline in 2/3 of infants and fentanyl in 3/4, which may suggest that the blinding process was not entirely effective. However, the we interpreted the frequent use of naloxone in the saline group as an indication that the clinical staff were uncertain about the treatment allocation, meaning correct guesses could have resulted from hindsight. Monitoring the effectiveness of the blinding will be critical as the NONA-LISA trial progresses. Finally, demonstrating a benefit for the primary outcome of the NONA-LISA trial, which is arguably a surrogate endpoint, may not transfer to a similar association on a patient-relevant respiratory endpoint and must be investigated separately.

Improving training and procedural competency for the LISA procedure

A lack of formalised LISA training, infrequent clinical exposure, and no formalised practice/guidelines are frequent barriers to implementation and may challenge adherence to clinical guidelines.^{20,31,38,137} Studies I-III add to the existing evidence base to support and improve procedural competency for neonatologists and neonatal nurses performing the LISA procedure.²⁰ Laryngoscopy and intratracheal surfactant administration may contradict the term “less invasive” as they impose the risks of bradycardia, pain and discomfort, and hypoventilation (e.g., apnoea and desaturations) as well as trauma to the upper airway.⁴¹ Video laryngoscopy may reduce some of these associated events,¹³⁸ and implementing the standardised LISA-CUR and LISA-AT after adaptation to the local setting may serve as a template for accreditation to increase operator competence.^{1,2} However, the effective and safe performance of LISA relies not only on the selection of equipment or an experienced operator but also on the coordinated efforts of a well-functioning interdisciplinary team.⁹ The need for continued training in the clinical setting was highlighted in Paper II, as the novices, after achieving the minimum passing score, still performed significantly worse compared to the experts in the laryngoscopy skills and duration of laryngoscopy. Ensuring competency in laryngoscopy is highly relevant, as studies, including Paper IV, have demonstrated increased levels of pain or discomfort and physiological instability, including episodes of hypoventilation and bradycardia, during LISA.^{4,16,25,58} If inappropriately managed, these adverse events may prevent the LISA procedure from achieving its full potential. However, it is a common

misconception to assume that a procedure that is quickly performed and successful on the first attempt is necessarily high quality. Furthermore, Studies I-III demonstrated that procedural quality for the LISA procedure depends on more than one individual's performance. Knowing this, Paper I should have included neonatal nurses as part of the target group, and Paper II should have assessed the validity evidence for the LISA-AT in a simulated team-based setting to incorporate a collaborative aspect to the definition of competence, instead of emphasising individual learning. All medical technical skills involving patient care also contain social and cognitive elements like teamwork and communication, which adds to the complexity of reaching and maintaining proficiency. Future simulation-based LISA training should focus on a team-based approach, as we did in the NICU at Odense University Hospital preparing for the NONA-LISA trial and must be followed by clinical training using traditional apprenticeship models, where novices observe before performing the procedure supervised by an experienced LISA operator. However, unlike the LISA rating scale, which only focuses on the operator,⁹⁷ the original LISA-AT consists of metrics that evaluate the team members' social and cognitive skills and non-pharmacological interventions.² Unpublished data suggest that the original LISA-AT can be used for interdisciplinary team training of neonatal staff and achieve the minimum passing score in approximately 5 attempts. In our experience, more time is required for the learning conversation following team-based SBT than for providing feedback to the operator alone. Five attempts followed by a structured team debriefing focusing on feedforward can be performed within the original time restriction in Paper II of 90 minutes. However, team training with neonatal staff implies higher opportunity costs, and the effect on clinical proficiency and patient outcomes has yet to be demonstrated.

Standardising non-pharmacological comfort care for neonatal procedures

During a NICU admission, the infant is exposed to many potentially distressing or painful events, which are sometimes inevitable to optimise neonatal care (e.g., vascular access, lumbar puncture, catheterisation, heel lance and feeding tubes, but also attachment and removal of monitoring devices, and even daily routine interventions such as suctioning, repositioning, diaper changes or skin washes, and exposure to warmth, humidity, cold, draft, noise, pressure, and vibration). However, prolonged or recurrent pain and distress during NICU admissions have been shown to have a detrimental impact on neurodevelopment in preterm infants and may have long-term negative effects on psychological and socioemotional functions.^{139,140} Inappropriate performance of the LISA procedure can induce distress and pain, contributing to the cumulative burden during the NICU admission. Therefore, the staff must be competent in understanding and detecting procedural

pain and distress, performing non-pharmacological comfort care for LISA and other neonatal procedures, and using pharmacologic modalities, if needed.¹¹¹

According to the Family and Infant Neurodevelopmental Education endorsed by NIDCAP, “*Stress and pain have similar physiological and behavioural responses in preterm infants (...)*” and may result from environmental stressors or an acute noxious stimulus.^{49,101} As the clinical appearance of distress and pain are alike, assessment and comfort care focus on reducing both.

Infants are non-verbal, and careful observation is necessary to assess pain or distress properly. Multiple validated tools exist to help the clinical staff assess neonatal pain and distress, but no standardised approach exists.¹⁴¹ The choice of scale should depend on the type of pain (e.g., procedural, ongoing, or postoperative) and the population of infants (e.g., preterm or term) relevant to the assessment.¹⁴¹ The COMFORTneo score exclusively reports behavioural measures (e.g., alertness, calmness, respiratory response/crying, body movement, facial tension, and muscle tone) and was initially validated to assess ongoing pain postoperatively or in the NICU.⁵⁷ However, the COMFORTneo score has previously been used to assess pain and distress during the LISA procedure,^{19,58,59} and experts suggest using this score specifically for LISA.^{19,40} Furthermore, the neonatal staff in Denmark is accustomed to the COMFORTneo score as part of their daily practice. Implementing a new pain assessment score across NICUs and ensuring the reliability of assessments is challenging.¹⁴² Therefore, the COMFORTneo score was selected to guide non-pharmacological comfort care during the LISA procedure. Other measures have been suggested, including physiological parameters (e.g., blood pressure),¹¹¹ salivary cortisol,¹⁴³ skin conductance,¹⁴⁴ and changes in brain activity (e.g., using electroencephalography)¹⁴⁵ all increasing by stimulated sympathetic nervous activity. However, these methods may not be suitable for guiding non-pharmacological comfort care during neonatal procedures, as obtaining the data may in itself involve a painful or distressing stimulus (e.g., increasing cuff pressure, sampling, or attachment and removal of monitoring devices) or the results may only be available after the procedure or may not correlate well with the existing behavioural measures for LISA.

The standardised approach to non-pharmacological comfort care described in Paper III only contained measures used by the participants in Paper I to ensure their relevance for the LISA procedure (light and noise reduction, temperature adjustment, appropriate positioning of the infant, swaddling, administration of mother’s milk or oral sucrose, if cooperative, and facilitated tucking).^{1,3}

To ensure the feasibility and facilitate the implementation of the standardised approach to non-pharmacological comfort care, we developed a stepwise guideline based on perspectives from neonatologists and neonatal nurses from the two founding NONA-LISA trial sites and developed a

teaching and clinical demonstration video.³ We decided to maintain the same number of staff members as previously described (a proceduralist/neonatologist performing the laryngoscopy and catheterisation and two neonatal nurses).²⁰ However, we slightly changed the responsibilities of the neonatal nurses: one should only focus on providing non-pharmacological comfort care guided by the modified COMFORTneo score, and the other should administer the medication and assist the neonatologist with the technical aspects of the LISA procedure.³ The essential aspects of our standardised approach to non-pharmacological comfort care include: 1) clear criteria on when the procedure can start (3-5 minutes after administration of premedication, if indicated, a modified COMFORTneo score between 8-13, and sufficient respiratory drive), 2) clear responsibilities within the team and emphasis on collaboration between the neonatal nurse responsible for comfort care and the neonatologist, 3) clear criteria on when to pause the procedure to adjust non-pharmacological comfort care (modified COMFORTneo score ≥ 14), and 4) clear criteria on when to administer intravenous fentanyl as a rescue treatment for pharmacological comfort. Paper IV demonstrated the feasibility of using this approach to guide comfort care during the procedure.⁴ During the feasibility study, we realised that the low inclusion rates could challenge the quality of the non-pharmacological approach if practised solely during LISA procedures, where it needed to be adequate to ensure patient safety. Therefore, we instructed the staff to practice this approach in all neonatal procedures, with positive feedback from the neonatal nurses and neonatologists (unstructured and unpublished data).

No premedication for LISA?

Preterm infants' ability to feel pain has historically been questioned, unfortunately resulting in inadequate premedication for painful procedures.¹⁴⁶ It is obvious that infants do feel pain and distress,¹⁴⁵ and prolonged or recurring exposures to noxious stimuli may negatively impact long-term neurodevelopmental outcomes.¹⁴⁷ During the LISA procedure, pain and distress most frequently occur during laryngoscopy. Paper I demonstrated that approximately 40% of LISA experts do not use any analgesic or sedative premedication.¹ Other studies highlight the uncertainties about premedication for LISA,^{39,44,148} and some larger trials even prohibit premedication.²⁵ A recent state-of-the-art review of LISA advises against the routine use of premedication and suggests an individualised approach.¹⁹

Previous trials by Dekker et al.⁵⁸ and Sk et al.¹¹⁸ have demonstrated greater comfort during LISA in the group receiving premedication compared to placebo (76% vs 22% favouring propofol,⁵⁸ 88% vs 47% favouring fentanyl¹¹⁸) while causing increased incidences of hypoventilation (91% vs 69%) and need for positive pressure ventilation within 24 hours (93% vs 47%)⁵⁸ and 72 hours (12% vs

6%).¹¹⁸ However, these studies included 78⁵⁸ and 34 infants¹¹⁸ and did not include a standardised approach to non-pharmacological comfort care. In Paper IV, 4/8 (50%) in the fentanyl group and 6/9 infants (67%) in the saline group had adequate COMFORTneo scores <14.⁴ These are limited data, and conclusions should be drawn with caution. Still, only 2/7 infants with COMFORTneo scores ≥ 14 (28%) received open-label fentanyl intravenously, indicating that pausing the procedure and adjusting non-pharmacological comfort care according to the standardised approach was adequate in most cases with pain or discomfort.⁴ Neurodevelopmental outcomes were not assessed in the studies by Dekker et al. and Sk et al.^{58,118} The two-year follow-up data after LISA from the AMV²⁸ and NINSAPP¹⁴⁹ demonstrated no adverse effects of LISA on neurodevelopment, and none of these trials routinely used analgesic or sedating premedication.

In summary, experienced clinical staff trained in the standardised approach to non-pharmacological comfort care can perform the LISA procedure safely without premedication. However, as a safety precaution, the NONA-LISA trial will continue to use an individualised approach to administering open-label fentanyl intravenously.

CONCLUSION

This thesis aimed to describe the preparations for the NONA-LISA trial to improve training, procedural competency, and non-pharmacological comfort care for the LISA procedure. Paper I established an international expert consensus on the LISA-CUR and the LISA-AT to improve operator training and competency. In Paper II, we demonstrated strong validity evidence for using the LISA-AT scores to evaluate operator competence in the simulated setting. Paper III described the NONA-LISA trial design, including the standardised approach to non-pharmacological comfort care guided by the COMFORTneo score. This approach may be used for all other neonatal procedures and should not be reserved for the LISA procedure. Lastly, Paper IV investigated the safety and feasibility of performing the standardised approach to non-pharmacological comfort care during the LISA procedure. This paper concluded that performing the NONA-LISA trial seems safe and feasible, blinding premedication at a level that might not influence the clinical staff's treatment decisions and include infants via deferred consent.

In conclusion, this thesis describes the extensive preparations for the NONA-LISA trial. Furthermore, each study provides insights into aspects of training, procedural competency, and non-pharmacological comfort care, which may be used to inform and improve future neonatal care and research.

PERSPECTIVES AND FUTURE DIRECTIONS

Clinical implications

The findings from Studies I-III presented in this thesis have several implications for neonatal clinical practice regarding training and comfort care, which may extend beyond the LISA procedure. Paper I developed a consensus-based LISA curriculum to optimise and standardise LISA training. Paper II obtained strong validity evidence for the LISA-AT, which can be used for formative and summative assessments to ensure proficiency in the simulated setting and improve patient safety. Paper III developed a standardised approach to non-pharmacological comfort care for LISA, providing neonatal nurses and neonatologists with a common framework for assessing and managing procedural pain and distress, which can be used for various procedures in the NICU. Paper IV obtained evidence for the feasibility of performing the LISA procedure with the standardised approach to non-pharmacological comfort care guided by the modified COMFORTneo score. It demonstrated that blinding the premedication was possible to an extent where the clinical staff's treatment decisions were unaffected, and that the legal guardians responded positively to inclusion via deferred consent. These findings may translate to improved procedural competency and comfort care in the clinical setting, improving patient-related outcomes following the LISA procedure, but may also

Future studies

While this thesis has addressed the preparations for the NONA-LISA trial by improving training, procedural competency, and non-pharmacological comfort care for the LISA procedure, several opportunities for future research exist to explore and qualify our findings further.

The validity evidence of the LISA-AT should be re-evaluated in a team-based simulated setting, including neonatologists and neonatal nurses, as we did in Odense (unpublished data). Establishing learning curves for an “intermediate” group would more accurately reflect the barriers to implementing LISA, including the costs associated with training. Importantly, as the neonatal staff is upgraded to supervised training in the clinical setting, data on procedural performance (e.g., LISA-AT scores) should be collected to assess skills retention and transfer from the simulated setting into clinical performance. Data on patient-relevant endpoints (e.g., COMFORTneo score and the incidence of invasive ventilation) should be collected before and after the training intervention to assess the impact of simulation-based LISA team training, which is rarely available in publications reporting validity evidence.⁸⁴ Organising a step-wedge cluster randomised trial could

provide a feasible solution, as we offer LISA simulation-based training to all future NONA-LISA trial sites. In this design, clusters (e.g., different NICUs or hospitals) will be randomised to receive simulation-based training at different time points. Outcomes will be reported before and after the training intervention.

A two-year follow-up study is being planned to evaluate neurodevelopmental outcomes and conclude on the safety aspect of LISA without the routine use of premedication. Importantly, this follow-up study should also assess if the primary outcome for the NONA-LISA trial translates to patient-relevant clinical endpoints (e.g., improved respiratory outcomes).

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APPENDICES

Appendix I

- Paper I. Breindahl N., Tolsgaard M.G., Henriksen T.B. *et al.* Curriculum and assessment tool for less invasive surfactant administration: an international Delphi consensus study. *Pediatr Res* 94, 1216–1224 (2023). DOI: [10.1038/s41390-023-02621-2](https://doi.org/10.1038/s41390-023-02621-2).¹

Appendix II

- Paper II. Breindahl N., Bay E.T., Heiring C. *et al.* Competency in the Less Invasive Surfactant Administration procedure: Validity evidence for the LISA-AT score. Submitted, under review.²

Appendix III

- Paper III. Breindahl N., Henriksen T.B., Heiring C. *et al.* NON-pharmacological Approach Less Invasive Surfactant Administration (NONA-LISA) trial: protocol for a randomised controlled trial. *Pediatr Res* 96, 1084-1089 (2024). DOI: [10.1038/s41390-023-02998-0](https://doi.org/10.1038/s41390-023-02998-0).³

Appendix IV

- Paper IV. Breindahl N., Henriksen T.B., Heiring C. *et al.* Can Non-pharmacological Comfort Care Replace Fentanyl in LISA? The NONA-LISA Feasibility Study. Submitted, under review.⁴

APPENDIX I (PAPER I)

POPULATION STUDY ARTICLE **OPEN**

Curriculum and assessment tool for less invasive surfactant administration: an international Delphi consensus study

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BACKGROUND: Training and assessment of operator competence for the less invasive surfactant administration (LISA) procedure vary. This study aimed to obtain international expert consensus on LISA training (LISA curriculum (LISA-CUR)) and assessment (LISA assessment tool (LISA-AT)).

METHODS: From February to July 2022, an international three-round Delphi process gathered opinions from LISA experts (researchers, curriculum developers, and clinical educators) on a list of items to be included in a LISA-CUR and LISA-AT (Round 1). The experts rated the importance of each item (Round 2). Items supported by more than 80% consensus were included. All experts were asked to approve or reject the final LISA-CUR and LISA-AT (Round 3).

RESULTS: A total of 153 experts from 14 countries participated in Round 1, and the response rate for Rounds 2 and 3 was >80%. Round 1 identified 44 items for LISA-CUR and 22 for LISA-AT. Round 2 excluded 15 items for the LISA-CUR and 7 items for the LISA-AT. Round 3 resulted in a strong consensus (99–100%) for the final 29 items for the LISA-CUR and 15 items for the LISA-AT.

CONCLUSIONS: This Delphi process established an international consensus on a training curriculum and content evidence for the assessment of LISA competence.

Pediatric Research; <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41390-023-02621-2>

IMPACT:

- This international consensus-based expert statement provides content on a curriculum for the less invasive surfactant administration procedure (LISA-CUR) that may be partnered with existing evidence-based strategies to optimize and standardize LISA training in the future.
- This international consensus-based expert statement also provides content on an assessment tool for the LISA procedure (LISA-AT) that can help to evaluate competence in LISA operators. The proposed LISA-AT enables standardized, continuous feedback and assessment until achieving proficiency.

INTRODUCTION

Less invasive surfactant administration (LISA) is a technique to administer surfactant to preterm infants with respiratory distress

syndrome (RDS). LISA is performed by placing a thin catheter below the vocal cords of spontaneously breathing infants on non-invasive respiratory support.^{1–4} Since the 2016 update of the

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Fig. 1 Overview of the three-round Delphi process from February to July 2022. All experts who participated in the first round were invited to participate in the following rounds. LISA less invasive surfactant administration, LISA-CUR LISA curriculum, LISA-AT LISA assessment tool.

European Consensus Guidelines on Management of Respiratory Distress Syndrome,⁵ LISA has been suggested as the preferred method of surfactant administration in spontaneously breathing premature infants and is now widely used in neonatal intensive care units (NICUs) globally.^{6–9} However, the risks of airflow obstruction, apnea, desaturations, bradycardia, misplacement of the catheter, pain and discomfort persist.¹⁰ Video laryngoscopy may reduce some of these adverse events.^{11,12} Effective and safe performance of LISA requires an experienced operator and supporting clinical team.¹³ However, operator and team's experience with LISA may be limited due to the relatively small number of infants eligible for LISA per clinician. Standardized simulation-based LISA education, including use of video laryngoscopy, has been recommended to improve LISA success rates.^{14–17} Nonetheless, to date, there is a lack of consensus on clinical practice and training required for gaining LISA proficiency.¹⁸ Therefore, clinicians would benefit from an internationally consented curriculum, based on sound clinical evidence and expert's experience, that will serve as a template for LISA accreditation. Curriculum development should follow a structured approach starting with problem identification and a general needs assessment.^{19,20} Further, to support skills development, methods for assessment of LISA competence are needed to ensure high and consistent performance and to enable future mastery learning of the LISA procedure, where trainees practice with feedback until they achieve a predefined mastery learning level.^{21,22} This study aimed to provide international expert consensus on (1) the training curriculum for LISA operators and (2) what to include in the assessment of LISA competence.

METHODS

Study design

From February to July 2022, we conducted a three-round iterative Delphi process using online survey questionnaires to collect information and establish consensus regarding the content to be included in (1) a LISA curriculum (LISA-CUR) and (2) a LISA assessment tool (LISA-AT) for the assessment of LISA competence. The Delphi process is a systematic, group facilitation technique using structured and semi-structured questionnaires to

collect and organize the opinions from experts in the field until consensus is reached.²³ The survey questionnaires for Delphi rounds 1–3 are available from the corresponding author. We defined consensus in rounds 2 and 3 as an agreement of ≥80%. Figure 1 presents an overview of the process.

Data collection

We used the Research Electronic Data Capture (REDCap) system for data collection. Chinese experts could not access REDCap from mainland China and submitted their replies by e-mail. This information was subsequently entered into REDCap by the principal investigator (N.B.).

Sample characteristics

The LISA experts were identified based on their involvement in research, curriculum development, and clinical education in the LISA procedure.

Invitations to participate were sent via e-mail by the steering committee members using their professional networks. The initial invitation to participate was promoted by the European Society for Paediatric Research (ESPR) via its website, on social media, and in its newsletter. The invitation included a link to the online consent form and the survey questionnaire for round one. Participation was voluntary. All experts who participated in the first round were invited to participate in the following rounds.

Survey administration

A Delphi steering committee was established to facilitate and manage all the steps in the Delphi process, including recruitment of experts and data analyses. The steering committee included an international team of 16 members with experience in neonatal intensive care or postgraduate medical education. All steering committee members except N.B. and M.G.T. were invited to participate in the survey due to their roles as international experts on the LISA procedure. The survey was developed by N.B. and piloted by the steering committee before the data collection in each round.

Delphi round 1

The first round was a brainstorming phase where experts replied to the following statements: (1) "List, in free text, the specific knowledge and skills that you believe a newly certified LISA operator needs to have and should be included in a curriculum for LISA training", and (2) "List, in free text, all relevant aspects of the LISA procedure to be included in an assessment tool to evaluate competence/certification of a LISA operator."

Table 1. Experts' baseline information.

Category	LISA experts (n = 153)
Sex (male), n (%)	78 (51%)
Age (years), median [IQR], range	51 [45–57], 32–70
Areas of experience, n (%) ^a	
Research	73 (48%)
Curriculum development	85 (56%)
Clinical education	133 (87%)
Years of LISA experience, median [IQR]	5 [4–8]
Specialty, n (%) ^a	
Neonatology	149 (97%)
Pediatrics	25 (16%)
Anesthesia	1 (1%)
Other (epidemiology)	1 (1%)
Number of LISA operators per hospital, n (%)	
<4	2 (1%)
4	6 (4%)
5	9 (6%)
6	16 (10%)
7	6 (4%)
8	18 (12%)
9	4 (3%)
10	9 (6%)
>10	82 (54%)
Monthly incidence of LISA procedures per operator, n (%)	
<1	56 (37%)
1–5	79 (52%)
6–10	10 (7%)
11–15	3 (2%)
16–20	3 (2%)
21–30	0 (0%)
>30	1 (1%)
Nationality, n (%)	
Denmark	23 (15%)
Spain	22 (14%)
Norway	13 (8%)
China	11 (7%)
Germany	11 (7%)
Italy	11 (7%)
Netherlands	11 (7%)
France	10 (7%)
Poland	9 (6%)
United Kingdom	9 (6%)
Sweden	8 (5%)
Australia	7 (5%)
United States of America	7 (5%)
Austria	1 (1%)
Number of items suggested for the LISA-CUR, median [IQR]	5 [3–7]
Number of items suggested for the LISA-AT, median [IQR]	4 [3–6]

LISA experts' baseline information in round 1 (n = 153).

LISA less invasive surfactant administration, LISA-CUR LISA curriculum, LISA-AT LISA assessment tool.

^aMore than one option could be chosen.

Experts provided baseline information, including sex, age, specialty, and years of experience with the LISA procedure and answered questions concerning local LISA procedure practice and use of training equipment.

Data were gathered by N.B. and processed by the steering committee. Duplicates were removed. Teaching activities, learning-teaching strategies, and teaching methods were omitted as they were already described in other publications.¹⁵ The remaining items were analyzed using content analysis²⁴ to identify repeated categories of procedures and various textual expressions for each unique item to consolidate the lists for the LISA-CUR and the LISA-AT used in round 2. Due to variations in phraseology in round 1, the steering committee was allowed to adjust the wording but not the content of each suggested item. Decisions were based on 100% agreement within the steering committee.

Delphi round 2

In this round, items generated in the *Delphi round 1* were assessed for suitability for the LISA-CUR and the LISA-AT. The selection was based on importance by using a five-point Likert scale; (1) Not important at all, (2) Less important, (3) Neutral, (4) Important, (5) Very important. The experts replied to the following statements individually for each item: (1) "How important are the following items when learning how to perform the LISA procedure?" and (2) "How important are the following items when assessing the skill of an operator performing the LISA procedure?"

Items rated as important (4) or very important (5) by 80% or more of the experts were included in the preliminary LISA-CUR and LISA-AT that were sent back to the experts for final review and comments in *Delphi round 3*.

Delphi round 3

The experts were informed about the distribution of scores, the excluded items, and selected comments from other experts in round 2. Subsequently, they were asked to approve or reject and comment on the preliminary LISA-CUR and LISA-AT.

Ethical considerations

Ethical approval was waived by the Committee on Health Research Ethics in the Capital Region of Denmark (Journal number: 21051793). Experts were informed about the aims of this study, the importance of participation, and the detailed tasks in each step of the Delphi process. All experts provided electronic informed consent prior to study participation. The datasets were de-identified prior to analyses. All information was handled confidentially. Data management and processing were approved (ID-number: P-2022-11). This study is reported according to the Consensus-Based Checklist for Reporting of Survey Studies (CROSS)²⁵ (Online Supplement, Appendix A).

Statistical analysis

Categorical data from *Delphi round 1* are presented as frequencies (counts and percentages) and continuous data as medians with interquartile ranges [IQRs] and range as appropriate. Statistical analyses were performed using RStudio version 1.2.5001. There were no changes to study design after this study commenced. There was no imputation of missing data. The required response rate for each round was $\geq 70\%$ to minimize non-response error.

RESULTS

Expert demographics

One hundred fifty-three experts agreed to participate in this study representing 14 countries worldwide (Table 1). Experts were involved in research (48%), curriculum development (56%), and clinical education (87%) regarding the LISA procedure, and the median [IQR] time of involvement in the LISA procedure was 5 [4–8] years. Most were board-certified neonatologists (97%), 16% in pediatrics, 1% in anesthesia, and 1% in epidemiology. More than half the experts (54%) worked at hospitals with more than 10 individual LISA operators. According to the experts, 37% of LISA operators in their respective units performed less than one procedure per month, and 52% performed 1–5 procedures per month (Table 1).

The LISA procedure

Based on the experts' replies, median gestational age of infants considered eligible for treatment with the LISA procedure was 28

Table 2. Experts' report of therapies applied during LISA.

Category	Results
Report of gestational age for eligible infants, median [IQR], range	28 [24–32], 22–42
Report of analgesic/sedative pharmacological treatment, n (%) ^a	
Fentanyl	75 (49%)
Propofol	28 (18%)
Ketamine	17 (11%)
Lidocain spray	2 (1%)
Midazolam	7 (5%)
Phenobarbital	2 (1%)
Morphine	7 (5%)
Sufentanil	1 (1%)
No use of analgesics/sedatives	63 (41%)
Report of non-pharmacological treatment, n (%) ^a	
Swaddling/wrapping	89 (58%)
Sucrose	73 (48%)
Tucking	70 (46%)
Skin-to-skin care	23 (15%)
Environment (light and noise reduction)	19 (12%)
Containment/holding	15 (10%)
Positioning	10 (7%)
Non-nutritive suctioning	6 (4%)
NIDCAP principles	3 (2%)
Human milk	3 (2%)
No use of non-pharmacological treatment	6 (4%)
Report of surfactant used, n (%)	
Curosurf/Poractant alfa/Porcine surfactant	125 (94%)
Calsurf/Bovine surfactant	8 (6%)
Report of pre-procedure pharmacological treatment, n (%) ^a	
Caffeine	138 (90%)
Atropine	35 (23%)
Paracetamol	2 (1%)
No use of pre-procedure pharmacological treatment	11 (7%)
Report of post-procedure pharmacological treatment, n (%) ^a	
Naloxone	36 (24%)
Caffeine	7 (5%)
Theophylline	1 (1%)
Paracetamol	1 (1%)
Antibiotics	1 (1%)
Atropine	1 (1%)
Doxapram	1 (1%)
No use of post-procedure pharmacological treatment	106 (69%)
Report of respiratory support during LISA, n (%) ^a	
nCPAP	129 (84%)
NIPPV	71 (46%)
HFNC	14 (9%)
Other respiratory support during LISA	9 (6%)

Therapies applied during LISA according to the 153 experts.

HFNC high-flow nasal cannula, IQR interquartile range, LISA less invasive surfactant administration, nCPAP nasal continuous positive airway pressure, NIDCAP Newborn Individualized Developmental Care and Assessment Program, NIPPV nasal intermittent positive pressure ventilation.

^aMore than one option could be chosen.

weeks (IQR 24–32 weeks, range 22–42 weeks) (Table 2). nCPAP was the most frequently reported mode of respiratory support used during LISA (84%), followed by NIPPV (46%) and HFNC (9%).

Forty-one per cent of experts reported no use of pre-procedure sedatives or analgesics, whereas 49% indicated the use of fentanyl as pre-procedure treatment (Table 2). Use of non-pharmacological measures was reported by 96% of the experts: 58% used swaddling/wrapping, 48% used sucrose, 46% used tucking and other interventions like skin-to-skin care, light and noise reduction, positioning, and pre-procedure non-nutritive suctioning.

Main findings

The final LISA-CUR and the LISA-AT, including response anchors for guided assessments, are available in Tables 3 and 4, respectively.

Delphi round 1

The experts suggested 807 and 658 items for the LISA-CUR and the LISA-AT, respectively.

For the LISA-CUR, 148 and 498 of the 807 items were excluded being duplicates or according to the following criteria: teaching activities, learning-teaching strategies, and teaching methods. The remaining 159 unique items were further condensed to 44 items and post hoc organized into the following nine categories to achieve a better overview: (1) *Indications and contraindications*, (2) *Complications*, (3) *Familiarity with the equipment*, (4) *Drugs and non-pharmacological measures*, (5) *Airway management*, (6) *Respiratory support*, (7) *Monitoring and assessment*, (8) *Evaluation*, (9) *Other skills* (Online Supplement, Appendix B).

For the LISA-AT, 256 and 314 of the 658 items were excluded for the same reasons as those listed for the LISA-CUR. The steering committee further condensed the remaining 88 unique items to 22 and post hoc sorted all items chronologically in descending order from procedure start to finish (Online Supplement, Appendix C). These two lists were used in *Delphi round 2* and returned to the experts for assessment.

The list of training equipment used to practice LISA is available in the Online Supplement, Appendix D.

Delphi round 2

The response rate was 82% (126/153 experts).

For the LISA-CUR, 12 items were eliminated by consensus (consensus score <80%, Online Supplement, Appendix B). Between rounds 2 and 3, the steering committee decided to merge three of the included items based on the experts' comments resulting in a preliminary LISA-CUR of 29 items.

For the LISA-AT, eight items were eliminated by consensus (Online Supplement, Appendix C), resulting in a preliminary LISA-AT of 14 items. One item, "*Surfactant administration synchronized with the patient's inspiration with a closed mouth*", was rephrased by the steering committee to "*Surfactant administration: Slow infusion to allow surfactant to be inhaled by the infant*" based on the comments received. Round 2 was repeated for this item alone.

The steering committee assigned specific response anchors on a five-point Likert scale to each item included in the LISA-AT based on the experts' suggestions. The steering committee provided precise guidance on the "poor," the "sufficient," and the "excellent" performance (response anchors 1, 3, and 5, respectively) for each item to hopefully increase inter-rater reliability and provide more standardized assessments without restricting the use of the LISA-AT, as operators may perform very differently.

The complete overview of adjustments to the LISA-CUR and LISA-AT between rounds 2 and 3 is available in the Online Supplement, Appendices E and F, respectively.

Delphi round 3

The response rate in *Delphi round 3* was 83% (127/153 experts). The LISA-CUR and LISA-AT achieved consensus without changes

Table 3. The final approved LISA curriculum (LISA-CUR).

Indications and contraindications
Knowledge about the indications and limitations of the LISA procedure
Knowledge about the effect of surfactant on pulmonary function
Knowledge about how to assess the severity of RDS according to local protocol
Knowledge on the most recent relevant guidelines on RDS
Complications
Knowledge about the incidence, signs, and management of complications during the LISA procedure
Familiarity with the equipment
Familiar with equipment required for the LISA procedure
Practical skills in inserting and positioning the catheter in the trachea at the correct depth
Practical skills in maintaining the correct position of the catheter during surfactant administration
Drugs and non-pharmacological analgesic interventions
Knowledge about the indications, dosage, correct administration, effects, and side effects of drugs that may be used as part of the LISA procedure
Knowledge about advantages and disadvantages of using sedation and analgesia as part of the LISA procedure
Knowledge about use of non-pharmacological analgesic interventions as part of the LISA procedure
Airway management
Practical skills in optimizing positioning of the patient including manual airway maneuvers (e.g., jaw lift)
Knowledge about the neonatal upper respiratory and lower respiratory airway anatomy
Knowledge about airway visualization techniques using a laryngoscope
Knowledge about indications for intubation in terms of failure criteria for the LISA procedure
Practical skills in endotracheal intubation
Respiratory support
Practical skills in mask ventilation using a bag-valve-mask or T-piece
Practical skills in non-invasive ventilation
Knowledge of indications for CPAP
Practical skills in using nasal CPAP
Physical examinations and vital signs
Knowledge about target vital sign values such as heart rate and saturation
Knowledge about how to recognize signs of pain and distress
Evaluation and outcomes
Knowledge about how to evaluate LISA procedure success or failure
Other skills
Knowledge about other methods of surfactant administration
Practical skills in treatment of pneumothorax
Knowledge about chest X-ray interpretation in newborn infants with signs of respiratory distress
Knowledge about blood gas interpretation
Knowledge about maintaining thermal control during the LISA procedure
Practical skills in neonatal life support

The approved LISA-CUR.

CPAP continuous positive airway pressure, LISA less invasive surfactant administration, LISA-CUR LISA curriculum, LISA-AT LISA assessment tool, RDS respiratory distress syndrome.

(100% and 98%, respectively). Furthermore, the rephrased item was included in the final assessment tool as 86% of the experts rated the item 4 (important) or 5 (very important).

DISCUSSION

In this Delphi process, 153 LISA experts from 14 countries were involved in a three-round iterative process to gather consensus regarding the training and assessment of LISA operators. Together, we developed the LISA-CUR consisting of 29 unique items, and the LISA-AT consisting of 15 unique items with response anchors. There are several benefits of implementing the LISA-CUR and LISA-AT

in standardized training after adaptation to the local setting to increase operator competence and patient safety.

Until recently, a lack of formalized training¹⁸ has been a barrier to the implementation of LISA, as confirmed by experts' in our study. Furthermore, the majority of the LISA experts in our study only performed 0–5 LISA procedures per month. Lack of formal training and infrequent clinical exposure to the LISA procedure may challenge adherence to clinical guidelines.^{15,26}

A combination of theoretical aspects with practical training for learning the LISA procedure is recommended.¹⁴ So far, a consensus on a LISA training curriculum or assessment tool to evaluate operator competence has yet to be published. In 2021,

Table 4. The final approved LISA assessment tool (LISA-AT) with response anchors one, three, and five after *Delphi* round 3.

Pre-procedure	1	2	3	4	5
Monitoring <i>Ensure appropriate monitoring of vital signs before and during the LISA procedure.</i>	Fails to ensure monitoring.		Competent but not consistent monitoring of vital signs.		Excellent monitoring of vital signs before and during the procedure.
Equipment preparation <i>Ensure all equipment used in the LISA procedure is functioning.</i>	Fails to check equipment/checks equipment incorrectly.		Competent but not consistent check of the equipment.		Excellent check of all the equipment.
Positioning <i>Position the patient optimally and maintain position during the LISA procedure.</i>	Fails to position the patient.		Competent but not consistent position of the patient throughout the procedure.		Excellent position of the patient during the procedure.
Team-briefing/Team resource management <i>Perform a team briefing before the LISA procedure including task assignment, outlining potential problems, etc.</i>	Fails to perform team briefing.		Performs team briefing with some experience.		Excellent team briefing.
Procedure	1	2	3	4	5
Pharmacological interventions <i>Check drugs and doses that may be used as part of the LISA procedure (including antidote if opioid is being used).</i>	Fails to check drugs.		Competent but not consistent check of drugs.		Excellent check of all drugs and doses.
Non-pharmacological interventions <i>Apply non-pharmacological techniques for pain and stress management.</i>	Poor application of non-pharmacological techniques.		Some application of non-pharmacological techniques		Full application of non-pharmacological techniques.
Laryngoscopy <i>Competent and non-injurious handling of the laryngoscope and good visualization of the vocal cords including sufficient overview of the airway.</i>	Fails to handle the laryngoscope/injurious handling of the laryngoscope/fails to visualize the vocal cords.		Competent but not consistent handling of the laryngoscope.		Excellent handling of the laryngoscope.
Catheterization <i>Insert the catheter into the trachea at the desired depth and maintain the position during instillation while retracting the laryngoscope.</i>	Fails to insert the catheter.		Competent but not consistent handling of the catheter.		Excellent handling of the catheter.
Surfactant administration <i>Slow infusion to allow surfactant to be inhaled by the infant.</i>	Fails to administer surfactant correctly.		Competent but not consistent surfactant administration.		Excellent surfactant administration.
Complications <i>Manage possible complications during administration.</i>	Fails to manage complications.		Manages complications with some experience.		Excellent management of complications.
Respiratory support <i>Maintain CPAP/NIV during the LISA procedure.</i>	Fails to maintain CPAP/NIV during the procedure.		Competent but not consistent use of CPAP/NIV during the procedure.		Excellent use of CPAP/NIV during the procedure.
Non-technical skills	1	2	3	4	5
Non-technical skills <i>Situational awareness, communication, teamwork, team leadership skills.</i>	Fails to use non-technical skills.		Use non-technical skills with some experience.		Excellent use of non-technical skills.
Overall	1	2	3	4	5
Number of attempts <i>Number of attempts until the LISA procedure is successfully performed.</i>	Procedure successfully performed only after more than 3 attempts, or procedure is abandoned.		Procedure successfully performed with 2 or 3 attempts.		Procedure successfully performed at the first attempt.

Table 4. continued

	1	2	3	4	5
Overall					
Adherence to algorithm / Time factor Able to follow this algorithm and minimize time delay in treatment.	Fails to follow the algorithm.	Able to follow the algorithm but with significant time delay.	Able to follow the algorithm with minimal time delay.		
Handling of the infant Gentle handling of the patient during the LISA procedure.	Fails to handle the patient in a gentle way.	Handles the patient with some experience.	Excellent handling of the patient.		
Total item score (15–75): _____					
Overall assessment:					
() PASS: Competent, safe, and gentle performance of the LISA procedure					
() BORDERLINE: Partially competent with adherence to safety requirements, but more training is needed					
() FAIL: Competence and safety not demonstrated					

The approved LISA-AT consists of 15 items, each rated on a 5-point Likert scale. The minimum score is 15 points, and maximum score is 75 points. The LISA-AT obtained 98% approval among the participating LISA experts.

CPAP continuous positive airway pressure, LISA less invasive surfactant administration, LISA-CUR LISA curriculum, LISA-AT LISA assessment tool, NIV non-invasive ventilation.

Liebers et al.¹⁷ developed a LISA training program including multimedia materials, checklists, pocket cards, and team briefing, which increased the mean success rate of LISA from 62% to 92%, defined as no need for any of the following: intubation within the following 72 h, a second surfactant dose, or termination of the LISA procedure. In 2019, Vento et al.¹⁵ published a practical recommendation for surfactant administration specifying the characteristics of a trainer and a trainee and how training should be structured. Three training modules for operators and assistants were proposed, including (1) pre-course preparation and online test, (2) LISA training on a mannequin, and (3) post-course LISA consolidation by performing several procedures in the clinical setting with supervision combined with periodic refreshers on a mannequin. Recommendations by Vento et al.¹⁵ and Reynolds et al.²⁷ suggest treatment thresholds, exclusion criteria, personnel, monitoring, equipment, non-pharmacological measures, and analgesics, including doses. The LISA-CUR may work with these existing recommendations to optimize and standardize LISA training in the future.

The consensus-based LISA-AT consists of 15 unique items and may provide standardized feedback, assessment, and potential certification of LISA operators. Vento et al. (2019)¹⁵ and Reynolds et al. (2021)²⁷ also identified core items that an operator should be able to undertake, but these reflected the individual opinions of the clinicians involved in formulating the recommendations. All their core items were included in the LISA-AT we propose and are now supported by international expert consensus. Various techniques for the LISA procedure exist,¹⁵ which may explain the lack of consensus achieved for various procedure-specific items like catheter type, Magill forceps, checking for gastric retention, and lung ultrasound, which were excluded from the final LISA-CUR and LISA-AT. These procedural factors clearly should be a focus of future research. Local protocols for each procedure step must exist before the LISA-CUR and LISA-AT can be adapted to the local setting and successfully implemented. Since this is first of a kind initiative, opinions may be inconsistent and further validation of the tool will help to refine it.

Development of the LISA-AT is the first step to enable mastery learning through standardized, continuous feedback and assessment until a predefined performance criterion is achieved.

However, there is currently no validity evidence to support the use of the LISA-AT and its ability to differentiate between operators with different levels of experience.²¹ To our knowledge, there is no pre-defined mastery learning level, and we do not know how much practice is needed during simulation-based LISA training to reach sufficient levels of mastery.^{9,28} Future studies need to validate the LISA-AT using Messick's framework,²⁹ which is the gold standard when evaluating validity as the American Educational Research Association recommended in their Standards for Education and Psychological Testing.^{30,31} Following validation, NICUs and neonatal simulation centers may standardize LISA training and assessment by implementing the LISA-CUR and LISA-AT. This should be a necessary step before the operator is promoted from training in the simulated environment to training in the clinical setting.

The Delphi research method is ideal for studying which items to include in the LISA-CUR and the LISA-AT when objective information is unavailable.³² We minimized the risk of conflict of interest and group pressure frequently associated with expert panels by anonymizing all responses prior to analyses and providing a unique link for each expert per round.^{32,33} This study was conducted following a detailed protocol (available from NB upon request) with no changes to the study design after the initiation of round 1, limiting individual members' influence through all three rounds. Hence, only items achieving the predefined consensus cut-off were included in the final LISA-CUR and LISA-AT. Due to the online advertisement through the ESPR website, we are unaware of the total number of potential

experts who might have seen the invitation. We are also unaware of the actual number of participants recruited by the online advertisement and the reasons for non-participation at each stage. However, we minimized the risk of bias from lack of response by achieving response rates of more than 80% of the initial responders in Delphi rounds two and three. Multiple NICUs contributed data from each country, minimizing the risk of bias arising from multiple responses from a single institution. No single country was represented by more than 15% of all the experts in our study. We chose a broad set of inclusion criteria for LISA experts to gather as many inputs as possible. Although this might have diluted the qualification of being an “expert,” baseline data showed that 97% of experts were board-certified neonatologists involved with the LISA procedure for several years. The experts involved in this study represented highly specialized NICUs from Western and non-Western countries. However, some NICUs may not have the resources to improve training and assessment for the LISA procedure, as this procedure is just one part of a resource-demanding intensive care strategy for preterm infants.

CONCLUSION

This Delphi process generated international consensus on a LISA curriculum (LISA-CUR) and a LISA assessment tool (LISA-AT). The LISA-CUR and LISA-AT are published with this study and may be used by LISA trainers, supervisors, and curriculum developers to guide their efforts.

DATA AVAILABILITY

The datasets generated during and/or analyzed during the current study are available from the corresponding author on reasonable request.

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AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS

N.B., M.G.T., T.B.H., and L.A. participated in study conception and design. All co-authors were involved in acquisition of data. All authors contributed to analysis and interpretation of data. N.B. drafted the article. All co-authors revised the manuscript critically for important intellectual content. All co-authors read and approved the final manuscript.

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COMPETING INTERESTS

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ETHICS APPROVAL AND CONSENT TO PARTICIPATE

This study did not require patient consent. We collected electronic informed consent from all LISA experts prior to study participation.

ADDITIONAL INFORMATION

Supplementary information The online version contains supplementary material available at <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41390-023-02621-2>.

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APPENDIX II (PAPER II)

Original Manuscript

Competency in the Less Invasive Surfactant Administration procedure: Validity evidence for the LISA-AT scores

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Category of study

Population Study Article.

Impact

- This study showed robust validity evidence for using the Less Invasive Surfactant Administration Assessment Tool (LISA-AT) to train LISA novices with a high test-retest reliability, high internal consistency, and good inter-rater reliability.
- The LISA-AT effectively discriminated between novices and experts, with a minimum passing score of 39 points, corresponding to the lowest quartile (Q1) of the experts' performances. Novices typically needed six attempts, ranging from four to nine. However, their laryngoscopy skills and the duration of laryngoscopy remained significantly different from experts.
- Using the LISA-AT score can ensure competence in the simulated setting before advancing to supervised clinical procedures.

Abstract

Background: The Less Invasive Surfactant Administration Assessment Tool (LISA-AT) was developed to support operator training and competence assessment. This study aimed to gather validity evidence to support using the LISA-AT scores.

Methods: Validity evidence was gathered using the Messick framework. The lowest quartile (Q1) for the median of the experts' LISA-AT scores defined the minimum passing score.

Results: Ten experts and 23 novices were enrolled in this study. The LISA-AT (ranging 8-40 points) had high test-retest reliability (Spearman's $\rho = 0.87$), high internal consistency, and good inter-rater reliability (Cronbach's $\alpha = 0.88$ and 0.82 , respectively). The LISA-AT discriminated between novices' and experts' first two attempts with median [IQR] scores of 29 [26-32] vs 39 [39-40]). The minimum passing score was defined as 39/40 points, and the novices used a median [IQR] of 6 [5-7] attempts, ranging from 4-9 attempts, to reach this score. Compared with the expert group, the novices' laryngoscopy skills and time remained significantly different even after attaining the minimum passing score.

Conclusion: We found strong validity evidence to support using the LISA-AT scores to train new LISA operators to the minimum passing score to ensure competence in the simulated setting.

Introduction

Less Invasive Surfactant Administration (LISA) is a method of surfactant administration to preterm infants with increasing oxygen demands despite optimised non-invasive ventilation. By supplying surfactant, LISA aims to prevent alveolar collapse while avoiding endotracheal intubation and invasive ventilation before, during, and after surfactant administration.¹⁻³ According to the European Consensus Guidelines on Management of RDS, LISA is the preferred method of surfactant administration in spontaneously breathing preterm infants^{1,4} and LISA is becoming more widely used in neonatal intensive care units (NICUs) worldwide.⁵⁻⁸

LISA is a complex procedure characterised by surfactant administration through a thin endotracheal catheter using laryngoscopy while supporting spontaneous breathing by applying non-invasive respiratory support.^{2,3,9,10} Effective and safe performance of LISA requires a clinician with experience in the LISA procedure, rescue intubation, and non-invasive respiratory support.^{9,11,12} However, this is often difficult to establish due to a low monthly incidence of LISA procedures per operator even in moderately sized NICUs.¹² Simulation-based training is the recommended method for acquiring competence in LISA because it can be achieved in a safe, controlled environment without harming the patient.^{13,14} A review from 2018 showed that 72% of physicians using LISA in the United States had no formal training on a mannequin before performing the procedure on infants.⁸

The LISA curriculum (LISA-CUR) and the LISA assessment tool (LISA-AT) were established by international consensus in 2023 to support training and assessment of operator competence.¹²

However, there was no validity evidence to support the use of the LISA-AT scores to evaluate trainee competence.

This study aimed to gather validity evidence to support the LISA-AT scores, establish a minimum passing score, and explore learning curves to estimate the number of attempts needed for novices to reach a predefined mastery level in a simulated setting.

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Methods

Study design

This study was conducted from March to November 2023 at the Department of Neonatal and Paediatric Intensive Care at Aarhus University Hospital and Copenhagen University Hospital (Rigshospitalet), Denmark. We assessed the validity evidence to support the LISA-AT scores using Messick's framework recommended by the American Educational Research Association in their Standards for Education and Psychological Testing.¹⁵⁻¹⁷ This framework includes five different sources of validity evidence: 1) content evidence, 2) response process, 3) internal structure, 4) relations to other variables, and 5) consequences of testing.¹⁸ Finally, the micro-costing approach¹⁹ was used to evaluate the cost of training one novice to the minimum passing score. We included four steps: 1) specification of resources used (time, materials, and equipment), 2) determination of the quantities of resources, 3) determination of the unit costs, and 4) multiplication of the quantities and the unit costs.^{20,21}

Development of the LISA assessment tool (LISA-AT)

In 2023, 153 LISA experts from 14 countries participated in a modified three-round Delphi process to establish international expert consensus for the LISA curriculum (LISA-CUR) and the LISA assessment tool (LISA-AT, available in the Online Supplement, Appendix A). The original LISA-AT is described previously (see Content evidence).¹²

Participants

Novices and experts were included in a 2:1 ratio as a convenience sample. The novices included final-semester medical students and young medical doctors without clinical experience in endotracheal intubation or LISA. Medical students were recruited during their clinical rotation in

paediatrics, and medical doctors were recruited from the paediatric departments in the Capital Region and Region Zealand of Denmark. The experts included senior staff neonatologists experienced in endotracheal intubations and the LISA procedure. Five experts were enrolled from both NICUs. All participants gave consent and received no compensation for participation.

Simulation equipment

Equipment used was the C-MAC® video-laryngoscope HD series, a Miller blade size 0 (Karl Storz™, Germany),²² the Surfath (Vygon™, United Kingdom),²³ and the Premature Anne mannequin (Laerdal Medical™, Norway, Stavanger) simulating a preterm infant born at 25 weeks and birth weight 750 grams.²⁴ The scenario was performed in a simulated single-family room (Fig. 1a-b). Videos were obtained from the video-laryngoscope and from two static video cameras: one placed above the mannequin and one placed next to the mannequin's head to visualise the head positioning (Fig. 1c). The recordings did not include footage of the participant's faces.

Simulation setting

Fig. 2 displays the simulation and data flow. All participants were allowed five minutes to familiarise themselves with the simulation equipment before beginning the first simulation scenario. All experts and novices were given a short test introduction telling them to behave similarly to what they would in real life to increase the psychological realism (Online Supplement, Appendix B). The participants performed a practical pretest and watched a demonstration video. The pretest was identical to the subsequent scenarios. The demonstration video highlighted key actions and provided a step-by-step visual guide on performing the LISA procedure, focusing on the equipment and the technique. Afterwards, the participant performed the first round (two LISA scenarios without feedback). LISA-AT metrics that did not discriminate between the novices and experts in

the first round were removed. The minimum passing score was established based on the experts' performances in the first round (see Statistical analysis). Only the novices continued practising in the second round until they attained the minimum passing score in two consecutive attempts. After each attempt in the second round, the novices received one minute of feedback on how to improve their LISA-AT score. The novices were not informed of their score after each attempt but received feedback on the metrics with scores lower than the maximum score of five points. A training session had a maximum duration of 90 minutes to prevent participant fatigue.

Two investigators were present during data collection. Investigator A was responsible for the ratings using the LISA-AT (Online Supplement, Appendix A).¹² Investigator B played the role of two neonatal nurses assisting during all performances but was unable to perform any actions without being instructed and did not offer any advice to the participant during the scenario (i.e., if Investigator B was instructed to perform non-pharmacological measures, Investigator B would reply: "*How should I do that?*"). Managing complications was a part of the original LISA-AT¹² and was defined specifically for this study as bradycardia, desaturation, and surfactant reflux, played in consecutive order, one for each scenario. Otherwise, the scenarios were identical. These complications aimed to increase the fidelity of the simulation to better mimic the clinical environment (Online Supplement, Appendix C). Investigator B, acting as the neonatal nurse, was instructed to incorporate the complications during the surfactant administration by verbalizing the problem (e.g., bradycardia, desaturation, or surfactant reflux).

Rater training

Four investigators, including two onsite investigators (a physician and a medical student) and two video investigators (senior staff neonatologists), assessed four participants not included in the study (three novices and one expert), followed by a comparison of scores. Based on the group

discussions, the assessment guide was reworded while the content was unchanged (Online Supplement, Appendix C).

The video ratings were considered the gold standard but resource-demanding and impractical as they could not provide immediate feedback to the participants. On the contrary, using non-specialist, trained investigators as onsite raters was considered more feasible to provide immediate feedback at a lower cost. Therefore, this study compared the trained investigators' onsite and senior staff neonatologists' video ratings of the experts' performances in the first round. If no differences could be detected, trained investigators would be used to rate the novices' performances onsite in the second round (Fig. 2).

Data collection

The participants provided their baseline characteristics, including their level of experience with simulation and the LISA procedure. All LISA-AT forms were filled out on paper and entered into the Research Electronic Data Capture (REDCap) system for data collection.^{25,26} All videos were processed and merged using OBS Studio 28.0.1 and safely stored on a secure drive.

Ethical considerations

All participants provided written informed consent, including approval of video recordings at the first simulation session before data collection. Participation was anonymous, and all information was handled confidentially. This study was exempt from ethical approval according to Danish legislation (protocol number 22031294). Data management and processing were approved (PRIVACY journal number: P-2022-318).

Statistical analyses

R Studio version 3.5.3 was used for statistical analysis.²⁷ Baseline characteristics were presented separately for each group and the total study population. Categorical variables were presented as frequencies (counts and percentages) and numerical variables as medians with interquartile ranges (IQR) due to non-normality (inspected using histograms and Q-Q-plots). Analyses were performed using the Chi-squared test, Mann-Whitney U test, Kruskal-Wallis test, and Wilcoxon sign test, as appropriate. P-values were adjusted for multiple testing using the Hochberg method.²⁸

The internal structure was assessed in terms of the reliability of the LISA-AT over time (test-retest reliability), across items (internal consistency), and different raters (inter-rater reliability).

The test-retest reliability reflects the variation in measurements taken by an instrument on the same subject under the same conditions. It was calculated by comparing the participants' LISA-AT scores in the first two attempts using Spearman's correlation coefficient and Intraclass Correlation Coefficients (ICC, model = two-way random-effects, type = agreement, unit = single).²⁹ A correlation of >0.80 indicated good reliability.²⁹

The internal consistency for all LISA-AT items was calculated by comparing the participants' LISA-AT scores in the first round using Cronbach's Alpha.

The inter-rater reliability was calculated using ICC (model = two-way random effects, type = agreement, unit = single).²⁹

We applied generalizability (G) theory to assess the overall reliability of the LISA-AT scores in the second round. To obtain a fully-crossed design, only the first 6 performances were included in the G study. This included two facets: Participant and Performance number, as the performances in the second round were only assessed by one rater. A G-coefficient >0.80 was considered appropriate for high-stake assessment.^{30,31} We performed subsequent decision (D) studies to estimate the optimal number of performances required to reach a reliable assessment.

The consequences of testing were determined by a minimum passing score using the lowest quartile (Q1) of the LISA-AT scores for the experts.

For Review Only

Results

Participant demographics

Ten experts and 23 novices were enrolled in this study. Table 1 shows the baseline characteristics. The experts had performed a median [IQR] of 11 [10-14] unsupervised LISA procedures, ranging from seven to 30 procedures before enrollment. Fig. 2 illustrates the study flowchart, including the number of performances during the rounds. Table 2 summarises the five sources of validity evidence.

Content evidence

The LISA-AT was developed in a separate study and contained 15 metrics rated on a Likert scale of one to five with a range from 15 to 75 points, and a global rating scale (pass/borderline/fail).¹² Descriptive anchors were provided for scores one, three, and five to guide the investigators (Online Supplement, Appendix A). The duration of laryngoscopy was defined to assess the time from introducing the laryngoscope blade for the first time to removing the blade from the simulator's mouth after a successful LISA procedure.

Response process

The response process is described under "Data collection" in the Methods section. The median [IQR] LISA-AT score in the first round showed no significant differences between onsite and video ratings of the experts' performances (73 [73-73] vs 74 [72-75], $p=0.34$ [Online Supplement, Appendix D]). Therefore, trained investigators were used as onsite raters to train the novices.

Internal structure

The internal structure of the LISA-AT was assessed during the first round.

The LISA-AT showed good reliability over time (test-retest reliability), with a Spearman's rho = 0.87 [Online Supplement, Appendix E]), and ICC [IQR] = 0.81 [0.63-0.90].

The LISA-AT showed good reliability across items (internal consistency) with a Cronbach's alpha [IQR] = 0.88 [0.84-0.91]. The LISA-AT showed moderate to good reliability across different investigators (inter-rater reliability) with a Cronbach's alpha = 0.82 and ICC [IQR] = 0.71 [0.38-0.88].

The overall G-coefficient was 0.73 indicating a moderate to good level of reliability of the LISA-AT scores in the second round. The largest contributor to the variance was the number of performances (53%). Subsequent decision (D) studies established that 9 performances assessed by one rater would be sufficient for obtaining a G-coefficient >0.80 to reduce the rate of measurement error or other unmeasured sources of variability.

There was an overall significant correlation between the global rating scale (pass/borderline/fail) and the total LISA-AT score. The pairwise comparisons showed significantly different distributions of the total LISA-AT scores within each category of the global rating scale (Online Supplement, Appendix F).

Relations to other variables

Table 3 shows the novices' and experts' performances in the first round for each LISA-AT metric.

When adjusting for multiple testing using the Hochberg method,²⁸ seven metrics

(“*Pharmacological interventions*”, “*Non-pharmacological interventions*”, “*Positioning*”, “*Team briefing*”, “*Catheterisation*”, “*Non-technical skills*”, and “*Number of attempts*”) did not discriminate significantly between the novices and experts and were excluded from the LISA-AT. The total LISA-AT scores in this study were calculated as the sum of the remaining eight metrics ranging from 8-40 points (“*Monitoring*”, “*Equipment preparation*”, “*Laryngoscopy*”, “*Surfactant*”

administration”, “*Complications*”, “*Ventilation*”, “*Adherence to algorithm / Time factor*”, “*Handling of the infant*”).

Consequences of testing

The novices had significantly lower LISA-AT scores compared to the experts in the first round (median [IQR]: 29 [26-32] vs 39 [39-40], $p < 0.001$). The minimum passing score was set at a LISA-AT score of 39 points, corresponding to the lowest quartile (Q1) of the experts’ performances. Setting the minimum passing score of 39 points resulted in zero false positives (passing novices) and four false negatives (non-passing experts).

Learning curves

Fig. 3 displays the learning curves for the novices. The median [IQR] number of attempts required for the novices to reach the minimum passing score in the simulation setting was 6 [5-7], ranging from 4-9, which was possible within one training session of 90 minutes. The duration of laryngoscopy significantly decreased from the pretest to the first round (Online Supplement, Appendix G). There was no improvement in the duration of laryngoscopy during the second round with feedback, which remained different from the experts’ performances (median [IQR] for the novices was 36 seconds [27-47] compared to 20 seconds [15-26] for the experts, $p < 0.001$, Table 4). The novices’ laryngoscopy skills significantly improved between the pretest and the subsequent rounds (Online Supplement, Appendix H). However, they remained significantly different from the experts' performances ($p < 0.001$, Table 4).

Evaluation of cost

The simulator cost was USD 3,149 (excluding VAT).³² Assuming straight-line depreciation over 5 years and 50 days of use per year (7 hours per day), the hourly price was determined at USD 2.²¹

We were able to perform up to nine attempts within the time restriction of 90 minutes (one attempt per 10 minutes). Based on the micro-costing procedure, the direct costs of onsite LISA simulation training with basic simulators using trained investigators as onsite raters were USD 68, ranging from USD 45-102 per novice to achieve the minimum passing score (Table 5). One-way sensitivity analysis identified the most important variables as the raters' salary. If senior staff neonatologists were employed as raters, the unit costs would increase from USD 22 to USD 67, increasing the median (range) expenditure for raters from USD 44 (29-66) to USD 134 (90-201). Other considerations included training paediatric residents or interdisciplinary team-training with higher opportunity costs than a single novice, assuming off-site simulation with increased facility costs,²¹ or using a more advanced simulator.³³

Discussion

This study found robust validity evidence for using the LISA-AT scores to train new LISA operators using the Messick framework. Using the LISA-AT scores can ensure competence in the simulated setting before the operator is promoted to training in the clinical setting under the supervision of an experienced LISA operator. The LISA-AT can be used to train novices to a predefined minimum passing score at low expenses. LISA-AT scores can provide ongoing assessments and feedback during each attempt (formative assessment) and for a final assessment to measure the learners' competency and determine when the minimum passing score has been achieved (summative assessment).

The safe performance of LISA requires an experienced interdisciplinary team.¹ However, the team's experience with LISA may be limited due to the relatively small number of infants eligible for LISA.¹² Standardised simulation-based LISA training has been recommended in the European Technical Skills Curriculum in Neonatology¹⁴ to improve LISA success rates.^{13,34,35}

A previous study showed improved success rates of LISA in the clinical setting following a standardised approach to LISA training involving an educational film, checklists, pocket cards, and team briefings,³⁵ but the medical staff did not train until reaching a predefined minimum passing score. Setting a minimum passing score is an essential asset of an assessment tool,^{15,36,37} which is required in competency-based learning for procedural assessment to guarantee that all trainees possess the essential skills required for safe practice.^{38,39} In this study, there were no consequences of time-based education, as all novices achieved the minimum passing score within the time limit of 90 minutes.

The need for continued training is highlighted by the significant differences in the laryngoscopy skills and duration of laryngoscopy time observed between the experts and the novices, even after

the novices achieved the minimum passing score. Similar to other clinical skills rarely performed in the clinical setting, periodic re-training may be essential. However, this study was not designed to evaluate skill retention or the transferability of skills from the simulated setting to clinical practice. Seven metrics did not discriminate between the novices and experts in the first round. This is likely because nurses perform some of the metrics (an onsite investigator in this study), and the participants were asked to mention the interventions, not perform them (e.g., “*Non-pharmacological interventions*”). Therefore, an acceptable score was too easy to achieve. Other metrics may have been challenging to observe and evaluate in the simulation setting by the onsite investigators (e.g., “*Positioning*”). Future studies could explore the integration of sensor technology to enhance the extent and precision of skill evaluation; however, this study prioritised using standard training manikins widely available in clinical settings to ensure the results would be broadly applicable. Some metrics were easy to remember and learn just by watching the demonstration video (e.g., “*Team-briefing*”). However, these metrics are still crucial for the LISA procedure’s success and should be addressed in the training of the clinical staff. Preferably, this training should involve both nurses and doctors on an interdisciplinary team to allow for the safe practice of both procedural skills, social and cognitive skills (i.e., non-technical skills and team-briefing), and the non-pharmacological approach to promote the safety and success of the LISA procedure.⁴⁰

A recent study by Rostoker et al. (2024)⁴¹ developed a rating scale to teach LISA in simulation using the same sources of validity evidence⁴² and a modified Delphi process similar to Breindahl et al. (2023).¹² However, Rostoker et al. only included 12 neonatologists from two countries (France and Belgium), and Breindahl et al. included 153 LISA experts from 14 countries. The final rating scale by Rostoker et al. was composed of 25 metrics in 8 categories with three response anchors

(“*not completed*”, “*partially completed*”, or “*perfectly completed*”). The LISA-AT was composed of 15 metrics with five response anchors. Like Rostoker’s rating scale, the LISA-AT considered the lack of consistency regarding premedication and could be used to train operators across units. While the Rostoker’s rating scale focused exclusively on the operator’s technical skills, the LISA-AT emphasised the importance of non-pharmacological interventions and several social and cognitive skills (i.e., “*team briefing*” and “*non-technical skills*”), which are integral elements of a successful LISA and may be suitable for interdisciplinary team training. Rostoker et al. included six experts with an average score of 73.6% and suggested that novices achieving the average score (i.e., a minimum of 36.8/50 points) could perform the procedure.⁴¹ However, a score of 37/50 can be achieved even though 6/25 metrics are “*not completed*” (scoring 0) or 13/25 metrics are “*partially completed*” (scoring 1). To achieve the minimum passing score on the LISA-AT and be promoted to training in the clinical setting under the supervision of an experienced LISA operator, the participant must achieve the highest score of five points on all metrics except for two metrics, scoring four points, but if only one metric scores three points the minimum passing score cannot be achieved. Thus, using the LISA-AT ensures a high level of competence. However, both tools still need to be translated into clinical performance.

This study has some limitations. It was impossible to blind the onsite investigators, thereby introducing experimenter bias, where the investigator may behave differently with the experts and novices, which can impact the assessments. Experimenter bias was minimised through a standardised assessment protocol (Online Supplement, Appendix C) and could have been minimised further by adding a second rater in the second round. Blinding is important to increase objectivity and reduce bias and could have been achieved through video assessment. However, the ability to provide feedback after each attempt would then have been impossible. Additionally, the

total score following each attempt was critical in determining when to conclude the second training round, making live assessment essential to the study's design. The small sample size may have been a limitation to the internal validity, but it was evident from the pretest assessments that the experts and novices represented two separate samples. Including only Danish participants may have been a threat to the external validity. However, we accounted for this by including participants from multiple institutions. The maximum training time of 90 minutes was chosen to prevent fatigue among the participants, but adding a time restriction may have impacted the assessments, as the investigators may have been more likely to give a higher score towards the end to complete the data collection for that participant without needing to schedule a second training. Finally, this study only focused on collecting validity evidence for the LISA-AT scores by assessing the 'neonatologist' performance and therefore did not include neonatal nurses. However, the LISA procedure requires a proficient interdisciplinary team to be successful in a clinical environment, and a multidisciplinary team training approach should be considered for future LISA simulation-based training. This should include the assessment of skills that rely on teamwork like non-pharmacological interventions, team briefing, and non-technical skills.

This study has several strengths. Using the Messick framework as a systematic approach to collect different aspects of validity evidence strengthens the overall validity argument for the LISA-AT. The test-retest reliability in the first round without feedback was high, indicating a limited testing effect, where the participant becomes better from just taking the test. Hence, the improvements in the novices' performances during the second round can be attributed to the feedback provided by the investigators, meaning that the LISA-AT can be used for formative assessment to identify procedural deficiencies and provide structured feedback to achieve the learning objectives. The effect of maturation (learning over time from other reasons) was limited, as all novices achieved the minimum passing score within 90 minutes, limiting the drop-out rate and related attrition bias.

Diffusion in terms of crosstalk or observation between participants was eliminated as the participants were enrolled individually on different days. Finally, this study demonstrated that simulation-based LISA training can be conducted at low costs using onsite trained raters.

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Conclusion

Robust validity evidence using the Messick framework supported using LISA-AT scores to train new LISA operators. The LISA-AT can be used for formative and summative assessment in simulation-based LISA training. The high minimum passing score emphasises the need for novices to train in a simulation-based environment before being promoted to training in the clinical setting under the supervision of an experienced LISA operator.

For Review Only

Data availability statement

The datasets generated and analysed for this study are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

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Figure legends

Fig. 1: Simulation setting and camera output

Legend: Fig. 1a-b: The simulation setting. Fig. 1c: The simulation setup used 3 external cameras, including 1) a sagittal view of the simulator's head and neck, 2) a bird's-eye view of the entire simulator, and 3) the operator's point of view (POV) through the video laryngoscope.

Fig. 2: Study flowchart

Legend: Ten experts and 23 novices were enrolled in this study. Both novices and experts were allowed 5 minutes of familiarisation with the equipment before completing the pretest. The first round consisted of two consecutive attempts without feedback. The novices continued training in the second round until they achieved the minimum passing score in two consecutive attempts. One minute of feedback was allowed after each attempt.

Fig. 3: Learning curves for the participants through the pretest, first, and second rounds

Legend: The vertical lines indicate the transition from the pretest to the first round (after the demonstration video, without feedback) to the second round (with feedback). The horizontal line indicates the minimum passing score of 39 points. The median [IQR] number of attempts required for the novices to reach the minimum passing score in the simulation setting was 6 [5-7], ranging from 4-9. Each attempt took approximately 10 minutes, and all novices achieved the minimum passing score within the time limit of 90 minutes.

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Author contributions

NB, ETB, AF, TBH, MGT, and LA contributed substantially to the study conception and design.

NB, ETB, CH, IRM, AG, and LA contributed substantially to data acquisition. NB and AF

performed the analyses. NB, AF, TBH, MGT, and LA contributed substantially to data

interpretation. NB drafted the article. All authors revised the article critically for important

intellectual content. All authors read and approved the final version of the article to be published.

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Competing interests

The authors declare no competing interests.

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Consent statement

This study did not include patients. All experts and novices gave electronic informed consent prior to study participation.

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1 **Tables with legends**

Table 1 Participants' baseline characteristics			
	Novices (N = 23)	Experts (N = 10)	Total (N = 33)
Sex, n (%)			
Female	15 (65)	4 (40)	19 (58)
Male	8 (35)	6 (60)	14 (42)
Age, years, median [IQR]	31 [28-37]	48 [46-50]	35 [29-45]
Clinical experience, years, median [IQR]	3 [2-7]	20 [18-20]	5 [2-18]
LISA procedures, median [IQR], range			
Primary operator, simulated	NA	14 [5-20], 0-50	NA
Primary operator, supervised	NA	2 [2-2], 0-5	NA
Primary operator, unsupervised	NA	11 [10-14], 7-30	NA
Primary operator, within 30 days	NA	1 [0-1], 0-2	NA
Legend: Baseline characteristics of the novices and experts. Abbreviations: IQR = interquartile ranges, NA = not applicable.			

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Table 2 Sources of validity evidence to support the interpretation of LISA-AT scores using the Messick framework		
Sources of evidence for validity	Description of source	Validity evidence for the LISA-AT
Content	The LISA-AT should measure the intended goals and objectives	The LISA-AT content, including response anchors, was developed by 153 LISA experts from 14 countries.
Response process	The integrity of data should always be maintained. Test administration should be controlled or standardised at the highest level	The LISA-AT scores of the experts' performances (the first round) showed no significant differences between onsite and video ratings ($p=0.34$). The novices were trained according to a prespecified protocol by trained raters onsite.
Internal structure	The LISA-AT should be reliable over time (test-retest), across items (internal consistency), and different raters (inter-rater).	The LISA-AT had a high test-retest reliability (Spearman's $\rho = 0.87$ and ICC = 0.81), high internal consistency (Cronbach's $\alpha = 0.88$), and moderate-good inter-rater reliability (Cronbach's $\alpha = 0.82$ and ICC = 0.71). The global rating scale was highly correlated with the total modified LISA-AT score for pairwise comparisons ($p<0.001$). overall G-coefficient was 0.73. The largest contributor to the variance was the number of procedures performed by the participant (53%). Subsequent decision (D) studies established that 9 procedures assessed by one rater would be sufficient for obtaining a G-coefficient >0.80 .

Relations to other variables	Assessment scores should correlate with known measures of competence	Seven LISA-AT metrics did not discriminate significantly between the novices and experts and were removed to form the modified LISA-AT. The novices had significantly lower modified LISA-AT scores compared to the experts in the first round (median [IQR]: 29 [26-32] vs 39 [39-40]).
Consequences	Consequences of testing are supported by the pass/fail standard that is set	The lowest quartile (Q1) for the median modified LISA-AT score in the experts' first round was used to set the minimum passing score at 39 points (higher than the intercept between novices and experts, which was 36 points).
<p>Legend: The five sources of validity evidence according to the Messick framework. Abbreviations: LISA = Less Invasive Surfactant Administration, LISA-AT = LISA Assessment Tool, ICC = Intraclass Correlation Coefficient, IQR = InterQuartile Range.</p>		

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Table 3 The LISA-AT metrics' ability to discriminate between the novices' and experts' performance in the first round				
LISA-AT metrics	Novices N = 46	Experts N = 15	P-value unadjusted^α	P-value adjusted^β
Pre-procedure, median [IQR]				
Monitoring	3 [2-4]	5 [5-5]	<0.001*	0.001*
Equipment preparation	4 [3-5]	5 [5-5]	<0.001*	0.003*
Pharmacological interventions	5 [3-5]	5 [5-5]	0.023*	0.092
Non-pharmacological interventions	4 [4-5]	4 [4-5]	0.825	0.825
Positioning	5 [3-5]	5 [4-5]	0.287	0.575
Team-briefing / Team resource management	5 [4-5]	5 [5-5]	0.123	0.368
Procedure, median [IQR]				
Laryngoscopy	3 [2-3]	5 [5-5]	<0.001*	0.001*
Catheterisation	4 [3-5]	5 [5-5]	0.008*	0.056
Surfactant administration	4 [4-5]	5 [5-5]	0.005*	0.039*
Complications	3 [2-5]	5 [5-5]	<0.001*	0.002*
Ventilation	4 [3-5]	5 [5-5]	0.002*	0.017*
Non-technical skills, median [IQR]				
Non-technical skills	5 [4-5]	5 [5-5]	0.022*	0.092
Overall, median [IQR]				
Number of attempts	5 [4-5]	5 [5-5]	0.012*	0.075
Adherence to algorithm / Time factor	4 [3-5]	5 [4-5]	0.001*	0.014*
Handling of the infant	3 [3-4]	5 [5-5]	<0.001*	0.001*
Legend: n count the number of attempts assessed by onsite raters. A total of 23 novices and 10 experts performed two attempts, but one of the experts' attempts in the first round went missing				

and four experts terminated their simulation training after the first attempt. Seven metrics did not discriminate significantly between the novices and the experts when adjusting for multiple testing using the Hochberg method. All significant metrics were included in the modified LISA-AT score. Abbreviations: IQR = interquartile range, LISA-AT: Less Invasive Surfactant Administration Assessment Tool. Footnotes: α = all analyses were performed using the Chi-squared test. β = adjusted for multiple testing using the Hochberg method. * = significant p-value <0.05.

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Table 4 Comparison of the novices' and experts' performances after the novices achieved the minimum passing score in the second round				
LISA-AT metric	Novices N = 95	Experts N = 15	P-value unadjusted^α	P-value adjusted^β
Pre-procedure, median [IQR]				
Monitoring	5 [5-5]	5 [5-5]	0.259	0.783
Equipment preparation	5 [5-5]	5 [5-5]	0.418	0.783
Procedure, median [IQR]				
Laryngoscopy	4 [3-5]	5 [5-5]	<0.001*	0.001*
Surfactant administration	5 [5-5]	5 [5-5]	0.783	0.783
Complications	5 [5-5]	5 [5-5]	0.319	0.783
Ventilation	5 [5-5]	5 [5-5]	0.435	0.783
Overall, median [IQR]				
Adherence to algorithm / Time factor	5 [4-5]	5 [5-5]	0.329	0.783
Handling of the infant	5 [4-5]	5 [5-5]	0.014*	0.151
Laryngoscopy time, median [IQR]	36 [27-47]	20 [15-26]	0.001*	0.001*

Legend: n count the number of attempts in the novices' second round and the experts' first round assessed by onsite raters. Two metrics discriminated significantly between the novices and the experts even after the novices achieved the minimum passing score: "*Laryngoscopy*" and "*Laryngoscopy time*". Abbreviations: IQR = interquartile range, LISA-AT = Less Invasive Surfactant Administration Assessment Tool. Footnotes: α = all analyses were performed using the Chi-squared test except for laryngoscopy time analysed using the Mann-Whitney U test. β = adjusted for multiple testing using the Hochberg method. * = significant p-value <0.05.

Table 5 Direct cost of simulation-based LISA training of one novice			
Expense	Unit costs [USD]	Quantities of resources	Total [USD]
Primary analysis, median (range)			
Trained investigators as onsite raters	22	2 x [time _{MPS}]	44 (29-66)
Novices as trainees (opportunity costs)	22	[time _{MPS}]	22 (15-33)
Depreciation of simulator	2	[time _{MPS}]	2 (1-3)
Total [USD]			68 (45-102)
One-way sensitivity analysis, median (range)			
Assume consultant-level neonatologists as onsite raters	67	2 x [time _{MPS}]	134 (90-201)
Assume paediatric residents as trainees (opportunity costs)	35	[time _{MPS}]	35 (23-53)
Assume team training (one paediatric resident [PR] and two neonatal nurses [NN])	PR: 35 NN: 28	1PR x [time _{MPS}] 2NN x [time _{MPS}]	91 (61-137)
Assume off-site simulation	27	[time _{MPS}]	27 (18-41)
Assume more advanced simulator	32	[time _{MPS}]	32 (21-48)
<p>Legend: The calculations did not consider the cost of developing the LISA-AT, as this tool was already developed, and acquiring a video-laryngoscope and other procedure-related utensils, as the department already had these in custody. Two simulator instructors were required for LISA training (one assessor and one acting as the assisting nurses). We anticipated identical hourly expenses between the trained investigator's salary and the novice's opportunity costs. The novices in this study were unpaid, but they may have used their time for paid work elsewhere if they had not participated in this study. Therefore, it is essential to acknowledge opportunity costs. The quantities were calculated from time_{MPS} (the time required to reach the minimum passing score), as one attempt took 10 minutes. The median (range) number of attempts to achieve the minimum passing score was 6 (4-9) attempts, corresponding to 60 (40-90) minutes. Assuming depreciation over 5 years and 50 days of use per year (7 hours per day), the hourly price was determined at USD 2 with a basic simulator and 32 with an advanced simulator. We estimated the hourly expenses of consultants, residents, and nurses based on Danish salary agreements. Trained investigators and facility costs were based on the article by Post et al. (2023) using the same Danish setting. All cost</p>			

estimates are subject to assumptions and rounded up to integers. Abbreviations: LISA = Less Invasive Surfactant Administration, USD = United States dollar, NN = Neonatal Nurse, PR = Paediatric Resident, $time_{MPS}$ = the time required to reach the minimum passing score.

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Figure 4: Learning curves for the participants through the pretest, first, and second training rounds

Appendix A: The LISA assessment tool (LISA-AT) with response anchors

LISA-AT metric	Response anchors				
	1	2	3	4	5
<i>Pre-procedure</i>					
Monitoring <i>Ensure appropriate monitoring of vital signs before and during the LISA procedure.</i>	Fails to ensure monitoring.		Competent but not consistent monitoring of vital signs.		Excellent monitoring of vital signs before and during the procedure.
Equipment preparation <i>Ensure all equipment used in the LISA procedure is functioning.</i>	Fails to check equipment / checks equipment incorrectly.		Competent but not consistent check of the equipment.		Excellent check of all the equipment.
Pharmacological interventions <i>Check drugs and doses that may be used as part of the LISA procedure (including antidote if opioid is being used).</i>	Fails to check drugs.		Competent but not consistent check of drugs.		Excellent check of all drugs and doses.
Non-pharmacological interventions <i>Ensure non-pharmacological precautions on pain and stress management.</i>	Displays poor knowledge on non-pharmacological precautions.		Displays some knowledge of non-pharmacological precautions		Displays ample knowledge of non-pharmacological precautions.
Positioning <i>Position the patient optimally and maintain position during the LISA procedure.</i>	Fails to position the patient.		Competent but not consistent position of the patient throughout the procedure.		Excellent position of the patient during the procedure.
Team-briefing / Team resource management <i>Perform a team briefing before the LISA procedure including task assignment, outlining potential problems etc.</i>	Fails to perform team briefing.		Performs team briefing with some experience.		Excellent team briefing.
<i>Procedure</i>					
Laryngoscopy <i>Competent and non-injurious handling of the laryngoscope and good visualisation of the vocal cords including sufficient overview of the airway.</i>	Fails to handle the laryngoscope / Injurious handling of the laryngoscope / Fails to visualise the vocal cords.		Competent but not consistent handling of the laryngoscope.		Excellent handling of the laryngoscope.
Catheterisation <i>Insert the catheter into the trachea at the desired depth and maintain the position during instillation while retracting the laryngoscope.</i>	Fails to insert the catheter.		Competent but not consistent handling of the catheter.		Excellent handling of the catheter.
Surfactant administration <i>Slow infusion to allow surfactant to be inhaled by the infant.</i>	Fails to administer surfactant correctly.		Competent but not consistent surfactant administration.		Excellent surfactant administration.
Complications <i>Manage possible complications during administration.</i>	Fails to manage complications.		Manages complications with some experience.		Excellent management of complications.
Ventilation <i>Maintain CPAP/NIV during the LISA procedure.</i>	Fails to maintain CPAP/NIV during the procedure.		Competent but not consistent use of CPAP/NIV during the procedure.		Excellent use of CPAP/NIV during the procedure.
<i>Non-technical skills</i>					
Non-technical skills <i>Situational awareness, communication, teamwork, team leadership skills.</i>	Fails to use non-technical skills.	1	Use non-technical skills with some experience.		Excellent use of non-technical skills.
<i>Overall</i>					
Number of attempts <i>Number of attempts until the LISA procedure is successfully performed.</i>	Eventually, the procedure is successfully performed.		Successfully performs the procedure by the third attempt.		Successfully performs the procedure on the first attempt.
Adherence to algorithm / Time factor <i>Able to follow this algorithm and minimise time delay in treatment.</i>	Fails to follow the algorithm.		Able to follow the algorithm but with significant time delay.		Able to follow the algorithm with minimal time delay.
Handling of the infant <i>Gentle handling of the patient during the LISA procedure.</i>	Fails to handle the patient in a gentle way.		Handles the patient with some experience.		Excellent handling of the patient.

Appendix B: LISA test introduction

“You will receive a brief introduction before you begin: You are about to perform the Less Invasive Surfactant Administration (LISA) procedure on a premature simulator. The simulator is an authentic representation of a premature infant born at 25 complete gestational weeks with a birth weight of approximately 750 grams. The infant was born one hour ago and now shows clinical signs of increased work of breathing and is receiving 35% oxygen. Normally, you would be assisted by two neonatal nurses during the procedure. I will act as both nurses, but you must tell me exactly what you want me to do. You must perform the procedure exactly as you would in a clinical setting, except here, you should verbalise your thoughts and actions so that we can assess your performance. You will perform all actions under the camera there. Would you like me to repeat the instructions? Do you have any questions before we begin?”

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Appendix C: LISA assessment investigator guide

LISA-AT metric	Test instructions for the investigator
<i>Pre-procedure</i>	
<p>Monitoring</p> <p><i>Ensure appropriate monitoring of vital signs before and during the LISA procedure.</i></p>	<p><i>If the participant asks the investigator to ensure monitoring...</i></p> <p>I: “What kind of monitoring do you want?”</p>
<p>Equipment preparation</p> <p><i>Ensure all equipment used in the LISA procedure is functioning.</i></p>	<p><i>If the participant asks the investigator to prepare equipment...</i></p> <p>I: “What kind of equipment do you want to use?”</p>
<p>Pharmacological interventions</p> <p><i>Check drugs and doses that may be used as part of the LISA procedure (including an antidote if the opioid is being used).</i></p>	<p><i>If the participant asks the investigator to prepare pharmacological interventions...</i></p> <p>I: “What should I prepare?”</p>
<p>Non-pharmacological interventions</p> <p><i>Ensure non-pharmacological precautions for pain and stress management.</i></p>	<p><i>If the participant asks the investigator to ensure non-pharmacological comfort care...</i></p> <p>I: “Can you describe how I should do this?”</p>
<p>Positioning</p> <p><i>Position the patient optimally and maintain position during the LISA procedure.</i></p>	<p>Caught on camera.</p>
<p>Team-briefing / Team resource management</p> <p><i>Perform a team briefing before the LISA procedure, including task assignment, outlining potential problems, etc.</i></p>	<p>Caught on camera.</p>
<i>Procedure</i>	
<p>Laryngoscopy</p> <p><i>Competent and non-injurious handling of the laryngoscope, good visualisation of the vocal cords, and sufficient overview of the airway.</i></p>	<p>Caught on camera.</p>
<p>Catheterisation</p> <p><i>Insert the catheter into the trachea at the desired depth, maintaining the position during instillation while retracting the laryngoscope.</i></p>	<p>Caught on camera.</p>
<p>Surfactant administration</p> <p><i>Slow infusion is needed to allow the infant to inhale the surfactant.</i></p>	<p><i>If the participant asks the investigator to administer surfactant...</i></p> <p>I: “Can you describe how I should do this?”</p>
<p>Complications</p>	<p>Scenario 1: Bradycardia</p>

<i>Manage possible complications during administration.</i>	<p>I: “The patient is bradycardic with a heart rate of 89 bpm and a pre-ductal SpO₂ of 92%.”</p> <p><u>Scenario 2: Desaturation</u></p> <p>I: “The patient is desaturating with a pre-ductal SpO₂ of 75%.”</p> <p><u>Scenario 3: Surfactant reflux</u></p> <p>I: “There is surfactant reflux.”</p>
<p>Ventilation</p> <p><i>Maintain CPAP/NIV during the LISA procedure.</i></p>	I: “How do you secure sufficient ventilation during the procedure?”
<i>Non-technical skills</i>	
<p>Non-technical skills</p> <p><i>Situational awareness, communication, teamwork, and team leadership skills.</i></p>	Caught on camera.
<i>Overall</i>	
<p>Number of attempts</p> <p><i>Number of attempts until the LISA procedure is successfully performed.</i></p>	Caught on camera.
<p>Adherence to algorithm / Time factor</p> <p><i>Able to follow this algorithm and minimise time delay in treatment.</i></p>	Caught on camera.
<p>Handling of the infant</p> <p><i>Gentle handling of the patient during the LISA procedure.</i></p>	Caught on camera.
<p>Legend: This is a guideline on how to obtain the necessary information from the participant during the LISA procedure. The scenarios were identical except for three complications (bradycardia, desaturation, and surfactant reflux), played in consecutive order. Abbreviations: LISA = Less Invasive Surfactant Administration, LISA-AT = LISA Assessment Tool, I = Investigator, CPAP = Continuous Positive Airway Pressure, NIV = Non-Invasive Ventilation.</p>	

Appendix D

LISA-AT scores of the experts' first training round: Trained investigators (onsite) compared to consultant-level neonatologists (video)

Legend: The median [IQR] of trained investigators (onsite) vs consultant-level neonatologists (video) was 73 [73-73] vs 74 [72-75], $p=0.34$. Therefore, the novices were trained using trained investigators (onsite) during the second training round.

Appendix E

Legend: The correlation of the two performances in the first training round indicated good test-retest reliability, with a Spearman's rho = 0.87.

Appendix F

Legend: There was an overall significant correlation between the global rating scale (fail = 1, borderline = 2, fail = 3) and the total modified LISA-AT score ($p < 0.001$). The pairwise comparisons showed significantly different distributions of the total modified LISA-AT scores within each category of the global rating scale.

Appendix G

Legend: The novices' laryngoscopy time decreased significantly from the pretest to the first training round. However, there was no significant improvement in the laryngoscopy time during the second training round with feedback, which remained significantly different from the experts' performances (median [IQR] for the novices was 36 seconds [27-47] compared to 22 seconds [15-33] for the experts, $p=0.001$).

Appendix H

Legend: The novices' laryngoscopy skills improved significantly from the pretest to the first training round and from the first training round to the second training round. However, their laryngoscopy skills remained significantly different compared to the experts' performance ($p < 0.001$). The "Laryngoscopy" metric on the modified LISA-AT was defined as: "Competent and non-injurious handling of the laryngoscope and good visualisation of the vocal cords, including a sufficient overview of the airway" and did not include the laryngoscopy time.

APPENDIX III (PAPER III)

STUDY PROTOCOL **OPEN**

NON-pharmacological Approach Less Invasive Surfactant Administration (NONA-LISA) trial: protocol for a randomised controlled trial

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INTRODUCTION: Using pre-procedure analgesia with the risk of apnoea may complicate the Less Invasive Surfactant Administration (LISA) procedure or reduce the effect of LISA.

METHODS: The NONA-LISA trial (ClinicalTrials.gov, NCT05609877) is a multicentre, blinded, randomised controlled trial aiming at including 324 infants born before 30 gestational weeks, meeting the criteria for surfactant treatment by LISA. Infants will be randomised to LISA after administration of fentanyl 0.5–1 mcg/kg intravenously (fentanyl group) or isotonic saline solution intravenously (saline group). All infants will receive standardised non-pharmacological comfort care before and during the LISA procedure. Additional analgesics will be provided at the clinician's discretion. The primary outcome is the need for invasive ventilation, meaning mechanical or manual ventilation via an endotracheal tube, for at least 30 min (cumulated) within 24 h of the procedure. Secondary outcomes include the modified COMFORTneo score during the procedure, bronchopulmonary dysplasia at 36 weeks, and mortality at 36 weeks.

DISCUSSION: The NONA-LISA trial has the potential to provide evidence for a standardised approach to relief from discomfort in preterm infants during LISA and to reduce invasive ventilation. The results may affect future clinical practice.

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IMPACT:

- Pre-procedure analgesia is associated with apnoea and may complicate procedures that rely on regular spontaneous breathing, such as Less Invasive Surfactant Administration (LISA).
- This randomised controlled trial addresses the effect of analgesic premedication in LISA by comparing fentanyl with a placebo (isotonic saline) in infants undergoing the LISA procedure. All infants will receive standardised non-pharmacological comfort.
- The NONA-LISA trial has the potential to provide evidence for a standardised approach to relief from discomfort or pain in preterm infants during LISA and to reduce invasive ventilation. The results may affect future clinical practice regarding analgesic treatment associated with the LISA procedure.

INTRODUCTION

Respiratory distress syndrome (RDS) caused by surfactant deficiency remains a significant reason for neonatal mortality and short- and long-term morbidity in preterm infants.¹ RDS usually develops during the first 24 h of the delivery, and most infants with RDS present with breathing difficulties and an increased need for oxygen supplementation within the first few hours of birth. Surfactant decreases alveolar surface tension and helps to keep the lungs aerated, allowing pulmonary gas exchange.

Exogenous surfactant treatment of preterm infants with RDS reduces mortality and long-term morbidity.^{2–4}

Less Invasive Surfactant Administration (LISA) is a strategy to administer surfactant to infants with worsening RDS despite optimised non-invasive ventilation. LISA aims to prevent alveolar collapse and avoid endotracheal intubation and invasive ventilation before, during, and after surfactant administration.^{4–6} LISA involves surfactant administration via a thin catheter placed in the trachea using laryngoscopy on a spontaneously breathing infant.

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Before LISA was introduced, surfactant was administered via an endotracheal tube followed by invasive ventilation and later via the INTubation-SURfactant-Extubation (INSURE) method with immediate extubation following surfactant administration. Studies have shown that using LISA reduces the incidence of intraventricular haemorrhage (IVH), mortality, the need for invasive ventilation, and the risk of bronchopulmonary dysplasia (BPD) in preterm infants.^{7,8} LISA is currently considered the preferred method of surfactant administration in spontaneously breathing infants according to the European Consensus Guidelines on Management of RDS,⁴ and LISA is increasingly used in NICUs worldwide.⁹

However, the need for analgesic premedication in LISA is debated. In a recent study of 153 LISA experts,¹⁰ 41% indicated no use of pre-procedure sedatives or analgesics, and 49% reported using fentanyl as a pre-procedure treatment. On the contrary, 4% indicated no use of non-pharmacological treatment. There is a delicate balance between the desired effect of analgesia reducing discomfort and pain associated with laryngoscopy as opposed to acute cardiovascular side effects and the risk of over-sedation and apnoea. This may potentially impede the procedure and result in the need for positive pressure ventilation, which may harm the surfactant-deficient lung.^{11,12} Observational data suggests the ease of performing LISA to be unaffected by whether opiates are used or not.¹³

The NONA-LISA trial (ClinicalTrials.gov, NCT05609877) compares LISA with saline to LISA with 0.5–1 mcg/kg fentanyl in infants born before 30 gestational weeks and evaluate the need for invasive ventilation via an endotracheal tube for at least 30 min (cumulated) within 24 h of the procedure. Secondary outcomes include the number of laryngoscopy attempts, duration of the procedure, modified COMFORTneo score during the procedure, bronchopulmonary dysplasia at 36 weeks, and mortality at 36 weeks.

METHODS

Design and setting

The NONA-LISA trial is a multicentre, blinded, randomised controlled trial of fentanyl 0.5–1 mcg/kg or placebo (isotonic saline), administered to infants born before 30 gestational weeks who meet the criteria for surfactant treatment by LISA. A total of 324 infants will be randomised in a 1:1 ratio to one of the two arms. They will be followed up at 36 weeks PMA and at hospital discharge (shown in Fig. 1). The trial protocol conforms with the Standard Protocol Items: Recommendations for Interventional Trials (SPIRIT),¹⁴ and the trial results will be reported in compliance with the Consolidated Standards of Reporting Trials (CONSORT) Statement.¹⁵ The trial will be initiated at (but not limited to) the Danish level III Neonatal Intensive Care Units (NICUs).

Population

Infants will be eligible for inclusion if they are born before 30 gestational weeks at one of the trial sites and meet the criteria for first-choice surfactant treatment by LISA as described by Sweet et al.⁴: worsening babies with RDS and $\text{FiO}_2 > 0.30$ on CPAP pressure ≥ 6 cm H_2O . The primary respiratory support is CPAP in all four units.

Infants will be excluded if they meet any of the exclusion criteria; 1) suspicion of lung hypoplasia, 2) endotracheal intubation at any time before randomisation, 3) suspicion of pneumothorax, pulmonary haemorrhage or pleural effusion before LISA, 4) major congenital anatomical anomalies as described by the European Surveillance of Congenital Anomalies (EUROCAT).¹⁶

Randomisation

Participants will be randomly assigned to the saline or fentanyl group in a 1:1 ratio using computer-generated random allocation sequences with permuted blocks of varying sizes (two and four). The randomisation sequence will be stratified by trial site and gestational age at birth (more or less than 28 completed gestational weeks). Once randomised in the Research Electronic Data Capture (REDCap) system, all entry data will

automatically be transferred to the electronic case record forms (eCRF) linked to the infant's unique identification number. The allocation sequence is pre-coded and generated from the randomisation programme. A person not involved in the trial will generate the allocation sequence. The clinical staff will enrol participants.

Blinding

Blinding will be secured by the following means: The patient will be randomised after entering stratification variables in REDCAP. The randomisation sequence will be generated by one person unrelated to the study. The trial medication (fentanyl or isotonic saline) will be prepared once per day in sealed syringes with similar appearance and weight by the pharmacy or staff not involved in patient care. Thus, neither staff involved in screening or treatment of patients nor the parents will know the treatment allocation. Primary analyses will be performed blinded to the group allocation (Group A compared with Group B) and presented to all authors, who will agree on two alternative written interpretations before the randomisation code is unblinded to reduce the risk of interpretation bias.

Interventions

Participants are randomised to receive LISA with fentanyl 0.5–1 mcg/kg (fentanyl group) or LISA with isotonic saline (saline group). All infants will receive standardised non-pharmacological comfort care before and during the LISA procedure (Online Supplement, Appendix A). All LISA procedures will be performed using video laryngoscopes according to the Hobart method.^{2,3} Both groups will receive the neonatal unit's standard pre-procedure care (e.g., atropine and caffeine), which will not be standardised across trial sites. Naloxone may be administered at the clinician's discretion and will not be used routinely. In both groups, the infant's level of discomfort or pain will be monitored continuously during the procedure by vital signs and a modified COMFORTneo score (Online Supplement, Appendix A).¹⁷ Open-label analgesics can be administered to all participants at the clinician's discretion by indications of non-tolerance (e.g., modified COMFORTneo score >14).

All administered medications will be registered. A single dose of 200 mg/kg porcine surfactant (Curosurf®, Chiesi Pharma AB, Italy) will be used in this trial.

Outcomes

Primary outcomes. The primary outcome of this trial is the need for invasive ventilation, meaning mechanical or manual ventilation via an endotracheal tube for at least 30 min (cumulated) within 24 h of the procedure. Non-invasive ventilation (NIV) is not included in the primary outcome.

Secondary outcomes. The secondary outcomes include:

- Unique and composite outcome of death or moderate/severe BPD¹⁸ at 36 weeks PMA.
- Adverse events during the procedure (from the introduction of the laryngoscope blade into the oral cavity to the removal of the catheter) in terms of apnoea that require bag and mask ventilation, desaturation with an absolute decrease in peripheral oxygen saturation $>20\%$ from pre-procedure baseline, and bradycardia <100 BPM individual outcomes.¹⁹
- Pain or discomfort during the procedure (according to modified COMFORTneo score >14 ^{17,20,21}).
- Highest modified COMFORTneo score during the procedure.
- Need for a second dose of surfactant.
- Incidence of LISA procedures resulting in the INSURE procedure.
- Incidence of observed surfactant reflux.
- Incidence of observed injury to the upper airway.
- Incidence of observed injury to the lower airway.
- Incidence of invasive ventilation within 48 h after LISA.
- Cumulated duration of invasive ventilation during hospitalisation.
- Cumulated duration of any non-invasive respiratory support during hospitalisation.
- Cumulated duration of any respiratory support during hospitalisation.
- Procedural duration from the introduction of the laryngoscope blade over the lips to the removal of the catheter.
- Number of attempts to visualise vocal cords (laryngoscopy) where the laryngoscope is completely removed from the oral cavity between attempts.

Fig. 1 The Consolidated Standards of Reporting Trials (CONSORT) diagram of the NONA-LISA trial. Abbreviations: NONA-LISA NON-pharmacologic Approach Less Invasive Surfactant Administration, LISA Less Invasive Surfactant Administration, GA gestational age.

- Incidence of pneumothorax within 48 h after LISA.
- Incidence of massive pulmonary haemorrhage within 48 h after LISA (aspiration of haemorrhagic secretions from the trachea concurrent with the need for escalated respiratory support).²²
- Duration of hospitalisation.
- Morbidities in terms of necrotising enterocolitis (according to the radiographic signs of Bell's Staging Criteria),²³ treatment-demanding retinopathy of prematurity, intraventricular haemorrhage grade 3–4 and periventricular leukomalacia (according to the Papile classification)²⁴ as individual outcomes.

Data collection. Baseline characteristics will include infant gestational age at birth, delivery mode, singleton or multiple births, birth weight, sex, APGAR score (1, 5, and 10 min after delivery), resuscitation measures during the first 30 min after birth, first blood gas, umbilical arterial and venous pH, standard base excess, and lactate. Information on vital signs (oxygen saturation, FiO_2 , and heart rate) will be collected 15 min before

and after the procedure. Information on treatment with antibiotics, fluids, vasopressors, and early caffeine before the LISA procedure will be recorded. We will calculate the time from meeting the criteria for surfactant treatment until the procedure starts. We will also include maternal information regarding smoking status, diseases (diabetes mellitus, amnionitis as per the obstetrician, preeclampsia, and eclampsia), and antenatal administration of steroids, magnesium sulphate, indomethacin, and antibiotics, including timing.

A generic procedure description will be created for the clinician to use in the medical records to ensure that all information, including modified COMFORTneo score before the procedure, administration of atropine, early caffeine and naloxone, and indications for additional fentanyl administration and cumulated dosage, is recorded uniformly.

If the infant is discharged to a step-down unit, information will be retrieved from that unit.

Data management. Study data will be collected and managed using REDCap electronic data capture tools hosted at the Capital Region of

Denmark.²⁵ A password will protect access to the online forms and dataset, and infants will be identified by number only to protect confidentiality before, during, and after the trial. A clinical trial coordinator will be responsible for monitoring the study's progress and the data's completeness.

Patient and public involvement. A parent representative provided feedback resulting in minor revisions of the parent information material and consent forms before trial initiation (Online Supplement, Appendices B and C). A parent representative will also be involved in the dissemination plans of the trial. However, parents were not involved in the study design and will not be involved in recruiting or data collection during the study.

Sample size estimation and inclusion timeline. The sample size was calculated according to the primary outcome. Previous studies on preterm infants born before 30 gestational weeks report a frequency of invasive ventilation after the LISA procedure from 33%²⁶ and 41%²⁷ up to 75%.²⁸ Based on the incidence of invasive ventilation following LISA, we anticipate that the primary outcome will have an incidence of around 45% in the fentanyl group in our trial. Considering an alpha of 0.05 and a power of 0.8 to detect an anticipated incidence of about 30% for the saline group, this trial will enrol 324 infants in a 1:1 ratio. Based on an article by Wiingreen et al., ~123 infants are born before 30 gestational weeks each year in Denmark with the need for surfactant.²⁹ The inclusion will last three to four years, considering an expected inclusion rate of 80%.

Statistical methods. Baseline characteristics will be presented for each group in the trial population. Categorical variables will be presented as frequencies (counts and percentages). Continuous variables will be presented as medians with interquartile ranges [IQR] or as means with standard deviations [SD].

The primary analysis will use the intention-to-treat principle. A secondary analysis will use the per-protocol principle and exclude infants if they receive additional analgesics associated with the procedure.

The primary outcome will be reported as frequencies (counts and percentages) per treatment group with unadjusted absolute risk difference and relative risks with 95% confidence intervals (CI). The number needed to treat for benefit or harm will be reported if the results of the primary analyses show a statistically significant difference between the two exposure groups.

Secondly, a logistic regression model will be performed adjusting for inclusion site and gestational age (<28 weeks vs more than 28 weeks) and the following independent covariates, which are predictors of assisted ventilation and length of ventilation:³⁰ repeat doses of prenatal corticosteroids, 5-min APGAR scores, sex, admission illness severity (according to the Score for Neonatal Acute Physiology/SNAP score³¹), oxygenation index, and small-for-gestational-age status.³²

All secondary dichotomous outcomes will be described and analysed per the same strategy as the primary outcome. At the same time, mean and percentage differences will be calculated for continuous outcomes.

All analyses will be conducted by use of the statistical software R Studio. Two-sided P values less than 0.05 will be considered statistically significant.

DISCUSSION

This randomised controlled trial compares infants exposed to the LISA procedure with pre-procedure fentanyl or placebo (isotonic saline) by the risk of invasive ventilation, meaning mechanical or manual ventilation via an endotracheal tube, for at least 30 min (cumulated) within 24 h of the procedure. All infants will receive standardised non-pharmacological comfort care before and during the LISA procedure (Online Supplement, Appendix A). In this trial, we plan to test the hypothesis that there is no difference between the need for invasive ventilation within 24 h of the LISA procedure performed with or without pre-procedure analgesia (i.e., fentanyl).

The LISA procedure is performed worldwide without consensus regarding non-pharmacological and pharmacological approaches. There is clinical equipoise regarding the positive and negative effects of pharmacological analgesic treatment when performing the LISA procedure. There is a delicate balance between the desired effect of reduction in pain and discomfort and the risk of

over-sedation and apnoea requiring positive pressure ventilation.^{11,12} Comfort and pain relief using a non-pharmacological approach has yet to be thoroughly investigated in the context of LISA and how it compares with pharmacological analgesic treatment. Some studies indicate that a non-pharmacological approach, including facilitated tucking,³³ swaddling,³⁴ and skin-to-skin care³⁵ compared to pharmacological analgesic treatment, may reduce the incidence of apnoea and, ultimately, the use of invasive ventilation,^{20,21} while achieving the same level of comfort. Hence, some centres make the first LISA attempt without any premedication, as studies report that the LISA procedure is generally well tolerated without analgesia,^{1,36,37} especially in preterm infants.³⁸ Therefore, some studies advise using pharmacological agents only if non-pharmacological methods are insufficient to ensure patient comfort.³⁹ It is essential to investigate pharmacological and non-pharmacological approaches to reduce pain, discomfort, and adverse effects due to medication during neonatal procedures, including the LISA procedure, as the insertion of a laryngoscope and intratracheal administration of surfactant obviously contradicts the term "less invasive".⁴⁰

As a safety precaution in the NONA-LISA trial, the staff will continuously monitor the infant's level of discomfort or pain during the procedure by an objective score (modified COMFORTneo). The COMFORTneo score is the national standard for assessing pain and discomfort in newborns. Most NICU nurses are COMFORTneo certified. Previous studies have demonstrated the ability of the COMFORTneo score to assess pain and discomfort during the LISA procedure.^{20,21} However, the COMFORTneo score formally requires a two-minute assessment of the infant and was not designed for intra-procedure assessments as planned in the NONA-LISA trial. To avoid interrupting the procedure flow, performing the score over 2 min is not feasible. Thus, intra-procedure assessments of COMFORTneo in this trial will be based on the standard COMFORTneo items assessed faster than 2 min. The use of COMFORTneo in this trial is described in detail in Online Supplement, Appendix A. Importantly, if the modified COMFORTneo score is ≥ 14 during the procedure, the procedure may be paused, and non-pharmacological measures must be improved. If improved non-pharmacological measures are ineffective, the team may opt for open-label fentanyl administration. The infant will still be given the highest level of care and attention by the staff.

This trial has certain limitations. The pragmatic design of this trial allowing fentanyl dosages between 0.5–1.0 mcg/kg will imply difficulty interpreting the specific results, as this trial will not have the necessary power to determine causality between an exact dosage of fentanyl and adverse events (e.g., apnoea). Despite this, a pragmatic design was necessary to ensure participation from all feasible Danish trial sites. As the dosing interval reflects clinical practice, it ensures generalisability and relevance for neonatal intensive care outside trial settings.

Non-pharmacological measures in neonatal care are complex and multifactorial, where all factors are relevant for the potential success of the intervention. Several studies have shown synergy when combining several non-pharmacological measures. However, there is no evidence favouring one specific approach. This study will use a protocolised non-pharmacological approach to standardise the treatment across inclusion sites.

The incidence of invasive ventilation following LISA varies significantly in other studies, and the anticipated incidences in the fentanyl and saline groups may cause an inadequate sample size to achieve the necessary power. However, compared to ongoing clinical trials like PRELISA (NCT05065424), we expect to include more than five times as many infants in the NONA-LISA trial. Other trials like the PROLISA (NCT04016246) include more infants but compare propofol to placebo.

The NONA-LISA trial received approval for deferred consent, which may significantly improve the inclusion rates. Nevertheless, with all the Danish NICUS as inclusion sites, the inclusion period will last up to four years, making the NONA-LISA trial vulnerable to changes in best practices regarding surfactant treatment. We expect to include other trial sites.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the NONA-LISA trial has the potential to provide evidence for a standardised approach to relief from discomfort or pain in preterm infants during LISA (NONA-LISA) and to reduce the need for invasive ventilation during the first day after the procedure.

DATA AVAILABILITY

The datasets generated during and analysed during this trial are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

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AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS

N.B., M.G.T., T.B.H., and L.A. participated in the trial conception and design and constructed the first protocol draft. All authors revised the protocol critically for important content. All co-authors will be involved in the data acquisition, analysis, and interpretation. NB drafted the protocol and the protocol article. After revising them critically for important intellectual content, all co-authors approved the protocol and this manuscript. All co-authors read and approved this manuscript.

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COMPETING INTERESTS

The authors declare no competing interests.

CONSENT TO PARTICIPATE

Written informed consent will be sought from all participants' parents or legal guardians. All participants' parents or legal guardians will be presented with oral and written information by a member of the trial group at an appropriate time after enrolment. Any questions will be answered. Participation will be voluntary and unpaid. We respect the parents' decision to join or leave the study at any time. Important protocol modifications will be communicated to the relevant parties.

ADDITIONAL INFORMATION

Supplementary information The online version contains supplementary material available at <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41390-023-02998-0>.

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APPENDIX IV (PAPER IV)

1 **Can Non-pharmacological Comfort Care Replace Fentanyl in LISA? The NONA-LISA**
2 **Feasibility Study**

3
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19 **Short Title:** The NONA-LISA Feasibility Study

20
21 **Conflict of Interest Disclosures:** The authors have no conflicts of interest to declare.

22
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24
25 **Role of Funder:** The funder had no role in the study design, data collection, analysis,
26 interpretation, writing, or decision to submit the manuscript for publication.

27
28 **Clinical Trial Registration:** www.ClinicalTrials.gov, NCT05609877, released 18th October
29 2022

30
31 **Data Sharing Statement**

32 Deidentified individual participant data (including data dictionaries, study protocols, the
33 statistical analysis plan, and the informed consent form) will be made available upon
34 publication to researchers who provide a methodologically sound proposal for use in
35 achieving the goals of the approved proposal. Proposals should be submitted to
36 lise.aunsholt@regionh.dk.

37
38 **Abbreviations:** LISA = Less Invasive Surfactant Administration, NONA-LISA = NON-
39 pharmacological Approach to Less Invasive Surfactant Administration. RDS = Respiratory
40 Distress Syndrome, CONSORT = Consolidated Standards of Reporting Trials, EUROCAT =
41 European Surveillance of Congenital Anomalies, nCPAP = nasal Continuous Positive Airway
42 Pressure, IQR = Interquartile Range, FiO₂ = Fraction of inspired oxygen.

43
44 **Article Summary**

45 This feasibility study assesses if standardized non-pharmacological comfort care guided by
46 the modified COMFORTneo score is feasible during the Less Invasive Surfactant
47 Administration procedure.

49 **What's Known on This Subject**

50 The Less Invasive Surfactant Administration relies on regular spontaneous breathing to be
51 effective. Analgesic or sedating premedication and a painful or uncomfortable stimulus can
52 cause hypoventilation, which may prevent the LISA method from achieving its full potential.
53

54 **What This Study Adds**

55 Performing the Less Invasive Surfactant Administration procedure with saline and
56 standardized non-pharmacological comfort care guided by the modified COMFORTneo score
57 is feasible and safe. It is possible to blind the use of premedication, and inclusion via deferred
58 consent is feasible.
59

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60 **Contributors Statement Page**

61

62 Dr Niklas Breindahl, Prof Tine Brink Henriksen, and Ass Prof Lise Aunsholt made substantial
63 contributions to the conception and design, data acquisition, data analysis, and interpretation,
64 and drafted the initial manuscript.

65

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68 substantial contributions to the conception and design, acquisition of data, and critically
69 revised the manuscript for important intellectual content.

70

71 Prof Martin Grønnebæk Tolsgaard made substantial contributions to conception and design
72 and critically revised the manuscript for important intellectual content.

73

74 All authors approved the final manuscript as submitted and agreed to be accountable for all
75 aspects of the work.

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76 **ABSTRACT**

77

78 **Aim:** This feasibility study aimed to assess the feasibility of conducting the full-scale NONA-
79 LISA trial, including using a standardized approach to non-pharmacological comfort care
80 guided by the modified COMFORTneo score, using open-label fentanyl, blinding, and using
81 deferred consent as the recruitment strategy.

82 **Methods:** Infants born less than 30 weeks' postmenstrual age were randomized to receive
83 isotonic saline (saline group) or fentanyl 0.5-1 mcg/kg (fentanyl group) intravenously as
84 premedication for LISA. Both groups received a standardized approach to non-
85 pharmacological comfort care. The NONA-LISA trial was registered on
86 www.ClinicalTrials.gov (NCT05609877) on October 18, 2022.

87 **Results:** From September 2023 to May 2024, 17 infants were randomized (median gestational
88 age, 28 weeks; 77% male); eight and nine within the fentanyl and saline groups, respectively.
89 Modified COMFORTneo score ≥ 14 occurred in four of eight and three of nine in the fentanyl
90 and saline groups, most frequently during laryngoscopy, and most cases were alleviated with
91 improved non-pharmacological comfort care only. Two infants (saline group only) received
92 open-label 0.5 mcg/kg fentanyl intravenously. The clinical staff correctly identified fentanyl
93 in six of eight infants (administered naloxone to four) and saline in six of nine infants
94 (administered naloxone to five).

95 **Conclusions:** Performing the LISA procedure with saline and a standardized approach to non-
96 pharmacological comfort care guided by the modified COMFORTneo score was feasible.
97 Pausing the procedure and improving non-pharmacological comfort care was sufficient in
98 most cases with a modified COMFORTneo score ≥ 14 . It was possible to blind the use of
99 premedication, and inclusion via deferred consent was feasible.

100

101

102 **INTRODUCTION**

103 Neonatal respiratory distress syndrome (RDS) caused by surfactant deficiency usually
104 develops during the first 24 hours of birth despite optimized non-invasive ventilation,¹ and
105 remains a leading cause of mortality and morbidity in preterm infants.²

106 The concept of surfactant replacement therapy has been used for decades,³ and
107 according to the European Consensus Guidelines on Management of RDS,⁴ the Less Invasive
108 Surfactant Administration (LISA) procedure is the preferred method of surfactant treatment in
109 spontaneously breathing infants. This procedure involves placing a thin catheter using
110 laryngoscopy to administer surfactant intratracheally to a spontaneously breathing infant,
111 aiming to avoid endotracheal intubation and invasive ventilation.⁴⁻⁶

112 The need for analgesic or other sedating premedication in LISA is debated,^{7,8} as there is a
113 delicate balance between achieving acceptable comfort and the risk of over-sedation and
114 hypoventilation, including apnea and changes to the respiratory rate or tidal volumes.⁹⁻¹¹

115 Painful or uncomfortable stimuli caused by handling the laryngoscope may also cause similar
116 symptoms. Such complications may hinder the LISA procedure and necessitate positive
117 pressure ventilation, potentially detrimental to the surfactant-deficient lung.¹² In a recent study
118 of more than 150 LISA experts from 14 countries, 41% reported no routine use of analgesic
119 premedication,¹³ supported by other studies.^{12,14,15} However, some studies recommend the
120 routine use of premedication,¹⁶ and others suggest only using pharmacological agents if non-
121 pharmacological methods are insufficient^{7,17} or based on an individualized approach.^{9,18} While
122 not standardized, 98% of the LISA experts in the study agreed to use one or more non-
123 pharmacological measures such as facilitated tucking, swaddling, or oral sucrose,¹³ which
124 have been shown to improve procedural tolerance.¹⁹

125 The NONA-LISA trial (ClinicalTrials.gov, NCT05609877) compares LISA with saline to
126 LISA with 0.5–1 mcg/kg fentanyl intravenously in 324 infants born before 30 weeks'

127 postmenstrual age (PMA) and evaluates the need for invasive ventilation within 24 h of the
128 procedure.²⁰ As a necessary preparation for the NONA-LISA trial, this study assessed the
129 feasibility of using a standardized approach to non-pharmacological comfort care guided by
130 the modified COMFORTneo score, using open-label fentanyl, blinding, and using deferred
131 consent as the recruitment strategy.

132

133 **METHODS**

134 **Trial design**

135 The detailed protocol article was previously published.²⁰ Infants were included at two Danish
136 level-three NICUs in Copenhagen and Aarhus. The Committee on Health Research Ethics in
137 the Region of Southern Denmark approved the trial protocol for deferred consent (approval
138 number H-21078489),²⁰ and infants were enrolled in the NONA-LISA feasibility study using
139 deferred consent with an opt-out approach. Written informed consent was obtained from the
140 infant's legal guardians as soon as possible after enrolment.²⁰ The Danish Data Protection
141 Agency approved the study protocol (approval number P-2022-594). An independent Data
142 Management and Ethical Committee reviews the progression of the NONA-LISA trial for
143 safety and efficacy. This manuscript conforms with the Consolidated Standards of Reporting
144 Trials (CONSORT) Statement²¹ and was prospectively registered at www.ClinicalTrials.gov
145 (NCT05609877) on October 18, 2022.

146

147 **Participants**

148 Inborn preterm infants were eligible for inclusion if they were born before 30 weeks' PMA
149 and met the criteria for first-choice surfactant treatment by LISA;⁴ FiO₂ at 0.30 and increasing
150 while treated with continuous positive airway pressure (CPAP) ≥ 6 cm H₂O. The primary
151 respiratory support was CPAP in both NICUs. Exclusion criteria were previously described:²⁰

152 1) suspicion of lung hypoplasia, 2) endotracheal intubation at any time before randomization,
153 3) suspicion of pneumothorax, pulmonary hemorrhage, or pleural effusion before LISA, 4)
154 major congenital anatomical anomalies as described by the European Surveillance of
155 Congenital Anomalies (EUROCAT).²²

156

157 **Interventions**

158 The interventions were previously described.²¹ Preterm infants received a single dose of 200
159 mg/kg porcine surfactant intratracheally (Curosurf®, Chiesi Pharma AB, Italy) by the LISA
160 method and were randomized to premedication with intravenous isotonic saline (saline group)
161 or fentanyl 0.5-1 mcg/kg (fentanyl group). All LISA procedures were performed using a
162 dedicated surfactant catheter with a video laryngoscope and without McGills forceps.²³ A
163 loading dose of caffeine was administered as premedication in both NICUs.²⁴ Pre- and post-
164 procedural care, including administering atropine, and naloxone, was provided based on
165 clinical indication rather than as part of a standardized protocol. All infants received a
166 standardized approach to non-pharmacological comfort care and monitoring as described
167 previously.²⁰ This approach was developed in close inter-disciplinary collaboration between
168 neonatal nurses and neonatologists from the two participating NICUs, including team
169 members certified as trainers and professionals according to the Newborn Individualized
170 Developmental Care and Assessment Program (NIDCAP),²⁵ the Family Infant
171 Neurodevelopmental Education (FINE) education,²⁶ and COMFORTneo score²⁷ (teaching
172 video available at <https://youtu.be/I4gKTi-Jmi0> and clinical demonstration video available at
173 <https://youtu.be/7LyELgVecZ0>). Building on previous evidence,^{10,28} vital signs and the
174 modified COMFORTneo score were used before and during the procedure to assess the
175 infant's level of discomfort or pain at baseline and continuously during the procedure.^{17,20} The
176 modified COMFORTneo score involves all items of the original COMFORTneo score but

177 must be performed faster to avoid interrupting the procedure flow.²⁰ Additionally, the infant's
178 respiratory drive should be continuously monitored, allowing for timely stimulation in
179 response to any signs of insufficient respiratory drive during the procedure. Open-label
180 fentanyl could be administered at the neonatologist's discretion by indications of a modified
181 COMFORTneo score ≥ 14 despite pausing the procedure and improving non-pharmacological
182 comfort care.²⁰

183

184 **Variables**

185 The investigators extracted baseline data from the electronic health records as previously
186 described,²⁰ and the clinical staff completed a detailed procedure form after each LISA
187 procedure, including procedural and feasibility data. All variables were previously
188 described,²⁰ and entered in the Research Electronic Data Capture (REDCap) system hosted at
189 the Capital Region of Denmark.²⁹ An online survey was used to gather feedback from all
190 participating neonatologists and neonatal nurses on all intervention aspects to assess the
191 feasibility of conducting the full-scale NONA-LISA trial. Participation in the questionnaire
192 was anonymous and voluntary.

193

194 **Feasibility outcomes**

195 This feasibility study assessed the overall feasibility of conducting the full-scale NONA-LISA
196 trial at two neonatal intensive care units, where the clinical staff were accustomed to
197 administering fentanyl as premedication for LISA. This feasibility study focused on the
198 feasibility of performing non-pharmacological comfort care guided by the modified
199 COMFORTneo score in alignment with the study protocol²⁰ by reporting the incidence of
200 infants with a modified COMFORTneo score ≥ 14 during the procedure, the administration of
201 open-label fentanyl, and the clinical staff's feedback. Blinding was assessed by reporting the

202 incidence of procedures where the clinical staff could unblind the intervention medication
203 after the procedure, and the recruitment strategy was assessed by reporting the inclusion rates.

204

205 **Sample size**

206 In the context of the NONA-LISA feasibility study, the investigators did not perform a sample
207 size calculation. To ensure the timely progression of the NONA-LISA trial, the investigators
208 scheduled the transition from the feasibility study to the full-scale trial in May 2024. The
209 sample size calculation for the full-scale NONA-LISA trial was previously described.²⁰

210

211 **Randomization**

212 The randomization was previously described.²⁰ A person not involved in the trial constructed
213 computer-generated random allocation sequences with permuted blocks of varying sizes.
214 Infants were then randomly assigned in a 1:1 ratio to a blue or red syringe for premedication.
215 We chose block sizes of four and six to ensure proper allocation concealment. The
216 randomization sequence was stratified by trial site and gestational age at birth of less more or
217 than 28 weeks' PMA.

218

219 **Blinding**

220 The investigators, the clinical staff involved in patient care, and the legal guardians were
221 blinded to the treatment allocation. To assess the possibility of blinding the intervention, the
222 interventions (isotonic saline vs fentanyl) were randomly assigned to the blue or red syringe
223 by staff not involved in patient care every 24 hours. The syringes were sealed and identical in
224 weight and appearance except for the red or blue mark. This second randomization was
225 performed separately and only for the feasibility study, as it could result in an unequal
226 allocation of infants to the saline or fentanyl groups.

227

228 **Statistical methods**

229 This feasibility study assessed the overall feasibility of conducting the full-scale NONA-LISA
230 trial, and preliminary statistical analyses were conducted to support the evaluation of the
231 trial's overall feasibility. Analyses were conducted for all the randomized infants using the
232 intention-to-treat principle. Categorical and continuous variables were presented as
233 frequencies (counts and percentages) and using medians with interquartile ranges (IQR) due
234 to non-Gaussian distributions. In addition to the descriptive statistics, unadjusted relative risk
235 and 95% confidence intervals (CI) were calculated to summarize the observed data and assess
236 the feasibility outcomes. These interpretations should be cautious due to the small sample
237 size. All analyses were conducted using the statistical software R Studio version 4.3.1 (2023-
238 06-16 ucrt).

239

240 **RESULTS**

241 **Study inclusion**

242 From September 2023 to May 2024, 99 infants born before 30 weeks' PMA were screened,
243 20 were eligible for enrollment, and 18 were randomized (nine infants were allocated to each
244 intervention arm). All legal guardians, except one family, lacking proficiency in Danish or
245 English, provided positive responses when approached by investigators following
246 randomization (following ethical approval for deferred consent using an opt-out approach).
247 Data from all 17 included infants were analyzed, corresponding to an inclusion rate of 85%
248 (see Fig 1).

249

250 **Baseline data**

251 Table 1 displays the baseline characteristics of each group. Of the 13 infants in the total
252 population, most were male (77%). The median [interquartile range, IQR] postmenstrual age
253 was 28 [26, 29] weeks' PMA, birth weight was 950 [826-1055] g, and 5-minute Apgar score
254 was 10 [9-10].

255

256 **Procedure data**

257 Table 2 shows the procedure data for each group. The median [interquartile range, IQR] time
258 from birth until randomization was 5 [2-9] hours. Nine (53%) of the LISA procedures were
259 performed during night shifts from 19:00 to 07:00. The median [IQR] delay from the infant
260 fulfilling the inclusion criteria to starting the procedure was 30 [28-60] minutes, at which time
261 point the FiO₂ was 0.38 [0.35-0.45].

262 The modified COMFORTneo score immediately before the LISA procedure was high in both
263 groups, but between eight and 13 according to the standardized approach to non-
264 pharmacological comfort care described previously,²⁰ with no clinically relevant difference
265 between the groups.

266 The most frequent procedure-related short-term complications were desaturation with
267 preductal SpO₂ <85% and surfactant reflux (77% and 71%, respectively). Both groups
268 showed the same tendency regarding the incidence of short-term complications (desaturation,
269 surfactant reflux, prolonged apnea, bradycardia, and apnea requiring positive pressure
270 ventilation). There were no clinically relevant differences between the groups regarding the
271 highest modified COMFORTneo scores. The highest modified COMFORTneo scores were
272 most frequently reported during laryngoscopy (53%). Naloxone was administered to 50% and
273 56% of infants treated with fentanyl and saline, respectively.

274

275 **Feasibility outcomes**

276 Table 3 summarizes the outcomes supporting the feasibility assessment. The incidence of a
277 modified COMFORTneo score ≥ 14 during the LISA procedure was four out of eight infants
278 in the fentanyl group (50%) and three out of nine in the saline group (33%). The relative risk
279 of reaching a modified COMFORTneo score ≥ 14 during the LISA procedure in the fentanyl
280 group compared to the saline group was 1.5 (95% CI: 0.47, 4.76).
281 Zero infants in the fentanyl group compared to two infants in the saline group received open-
282 label 0.5 mcg/kg fentanyl intravenously, meaning that pausing the procedure and improving
283 non-pharmacological comfort care were sufficient in four out of four infants in the fentanyl
284 group and one out of three infants in the saline group with modified COMFORTneo scores
285 above the cut-off. The relative risk of receiving open-label fentanyl in the fentanyl group
286 compared to the saline group was 0.22 (95% CI: 0.01, 4.04).
287 Post-procedure, the clinical staff correctly unblinded fentanyl in six out of nine infants (67%)
288 and saline in six out of eight infants (75%). The relative risk of unblinding the intervention in
289 the fentanyl group compared to the saline group was 1.13 (95% CI: 0.61, 2.07).

290

291 **Questionnaire outcomes**

292 The questionnaire was completed by 15 neonatologists and seven neonatal nurses for 13
293 (81%) of the included infants (Table 4). A recurring theme in the feedback was the time
294 required for non-experienced users to randomize the infant in the REDCap system, as this
295 system demands two-factor authentication. One neonatologist commented, “It is time-
296 consuming in a situation where quick action is needed.” This concern was mentioned by five
297 out of 15 (33%) of the neonatologists responsible for randomizing the infants, indicating a
298 significant area for improvement. Additionally, the respondents reported varying experiences
299 with providing the standardized approach to non-pharmacological comfort care. One neonatal
300 nurse elaborated, “There were many disruptions - possibly because it was the first time for

301 many of us participating in NONA-LISA. Next time, we will be better prepared and can thus
302 optimize the non-pharmacological comfort care.”

303

304 **Harms**

305 No serious adverse events related to the trial intervention, harms, or unintended effects were
306 reported in either group.

307

308 **DISCUSSION**

309 This study was designed to assess the feasibility of the full-scale NONA-LISA trial, which
310 involves a standardized approach to non-pharmacological comfort care, guided by the
311 modified COMFORTneo score, for infants receiving either fentanyl or saline as
312 premedication for LISA. The strengths and limitations of the NONA-LISA trial design have
313 been discussed previously.^{20,30,31}

314

315 Previously, two smaller trials have investigated the effect intravenous fentanyl and propofol
316 as premedication for LISA.^{10,11} Dekker et al. (2018)¹⁰ randomised 78 infants to receive
317 propofol 1 mg/kg intravenously compared to no premedication and evaluated COMFORTneo
318 score as the primary outcome. In the propofol group, 10/42 (24%) compared to 28/36 infants
319 (78%) in the control group had increased COMFORTneo scores, assessed post-procedure
320 using video recordings of the infant.¹⁰ Both studies reported higher rates of desaturation
321 during the LISA procedure for premedication vs no premedication (fentanyl vs saline: 91% vs
322 69%) and need for invasive ventilation within 24 hours (24% vs 17%).¹⁰ In this feasibility
323 study, 4/8 infants (50%) in the fentanyl group compared to 3/9 (33%) in the saline group had
324 increased COMFORTneo scores. These preliminary results indicate that performing the LISA
325 procedure with standardized non-pharmacological comfort care guided by the modified

326 COMFORTneo score is safe and feasible. However, the wide confidence intervals suggest
327 uncertainty around these estimates, likely resulting from the small sample size. As a safety
328 precaution, the NONA-LISA trial will continue to use an individualized approach to
329 administering open-label fentanyl if pausing the procedure and improving non-
330 pharmacological comfort care is insufficient to manage a modified COMFORTneo score ≥ 14
331 during the procedure,²⁰ which is in line with previous recommendations.^{4,9,17}

332

333 Blinding the use of premedication (i.e., fentanyl and saline) is crucial to avoid performance
334 and detection bias. This feasibility study demonstrated that the clinical staff was able to
335 unblind fentanyl in 2/3 infants and saline in 3/4 infants after the procedure, which may
336 indicate that blinding the use of premedication for LISA was not entirely possible.

337 Importantly, the frequent use of naloxone in the saline group indicates that the clinical staff's
338 treatment decisions were unbiased. Hence, a correct guess may likely result from hindsight. It
339 will be essential to monitor the blinding aspect during the NONA-LISA trial to ensure that the
340 findings are attributable to the intervention.

341

342 Another important observation in the NONA-LISA feasibility study was the relatively high
343 modified COMFORTneo scores in both groups immediately before the LISA procedure. Yet,
344 the pre-procedure scores remained between eight and 13 in both groups according to the
345 protocol.²⁰ Prioritizing the optimization of comfort care before the procedure is crucial and
346 should be effectively communicated to the clinical staff. It will be essential to monitor the
347 modified COMFORTneo scores before the LISA procedure during the trial period, as an
348 elevated modified COMFORTneo score before the procedure may be associated with
349 increased pain levels during the procedure. This can potentially cause apnea directly or

350 indirectly through the administration of open-label fentanyl, leading to failure to maintain the
351 concept of spontaneous breathing.

352

353 As more than half of the LISA procedures were performed during nighttime across both
354 groups, it is paramount that the clinical staff can autonomously perform the procedure,
355 including the standardized non-pharmacological comfort care, without the investigators
356 present. While some studies on LISA demonstrate the success of applying various non-
357 pharmacological measures to complete the procedure,^{10,19,32} we suggest carefully
358 implementing a standardized approach to non-pharmacological comfort care guided by the
359 modified COMFORTneo score.²⁰ Improving operator competence to ensure clinical
360 proficiency in the LISA procedure is important,^{17,33} but team-based interdisciplinary LISA
361 training may be required, even for experienced LISA operators, as these aspects are crucial
362 for the successful performance of the LISA procedure, including non-pharmacological
363 comfort care.^{6,13}

364

365 The included infants were randomized within a median of five hours after birth, with a
366 median delay of 30 minutes from meeting the inclusion criteria. These results highlight that
367 surfactant treatment in infants often needs to be initiated within a short time frame and
368 demonstrate the importance and feasibility of enrollment via deferred consent using an opt-
369 out approach. The complete justification for inclusion via deferred consent is publicly
370 available.²⁰ Importantly, all legal guardians gave written informed consent and responded
371 positively to the trial. One family was not proficient in Danish or English and could not
372 provide written informed consent. However, with only 17 infants included within nine
373 months, involving more trial sites to achieve our inclusion target within a reasonable time
374 frame remains essential.³¹

375

376 **Conclusion**

377 It was feasible to perform the standardized non-pharmacological comfort care guided by the
378 modified COMFORTneo score during the LISA procedure according to the protocol. Similar
379 incidence rates of modified COMFORTneo scores ≥ 14 were observed in the fentanyl and
380 saline groups, and few infants required open-label fentanyl. These results indicate that a
381 modified COMFORTneo score ≥ 14 was often manageable by pausing the procedure and
382 improving non-pharmacological comfort care. Hence, we believe performing the LISA
383 procedure without premedication is safe and feasible. It was possible to blind the clinical staff
384 towards the interventions (i.e., saline versus fentanyl) to an extent where their treatment
385 decisions were unbiased. Enrollment via deferred consent using an opt-out approach was
386 feasible. The full-scale randomized controlled trial is warranted to assess the potential clinical
387 benefit of performing LISA without analgesic or sedating premedication.

388

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390

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FIGURES

Figure 1. CONSORT inclusion flowchart for the NONA-LISA feasibility study

Legend: The Consolidated Standards of Reporting Trials (CONSORT) diagram of the NONA-LISA feasibility study. Abbreviations: NONA-LISA = NON-pharmacologic Approach Less Invasive Surfactant Administration; LISA = Less Invasive Surfactant Administration; GA = gestational age.

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TABLES

Table 1. Baseline Characteristics

	Fentanyl (N = 8)	Saline (N = 9)	Total (N = 17)
Demographic characteristics			
Gestational age, weeks' PMA, median [IQR]	29 [26-29]	28 [27-28]	28 [26-29]
Birth weight, g, median [IQR]	956 [838-1052]	950 [826-1055]	950 [826-1055]
Sex, n (%)			
Male	5 (63)	8 (89)	13 (77)
Female	3 (38)	1 (11)	4 (24)
Multiple birth, n (%)	3 (38)	3 (33)	6 (35)
Peripartum characteristics			
Exposure to antenatal glucocorticoids, doses prior to delivery, n (%)			
2 or more	6 (75)	7 (78)	13 (77)
1	2 (25)	1 (11)	3 (18)
No	0 (0)	1 (11)	1 (6)
Delivery mode, n (%)			
Cesarean section	6 (75)	8 (89)	14 (82)
Vaginal	2 (25)	1 (11)	3 (18)
Apgar score at 5 min, median [IQR]	10 [10-10]	10 [8-10]	10 [9-10]

Legend: Baseline characteristics stratified for saline or fentanyl as premedication for LISA and for the total population included in the NONA-LISA feasibility study. Abbreviations: IQR = Interquartile range, NONA-LISA = NON-pharmacological Approach to Less Invasive Surfactant Administration.

Table 2. Procedure Data

	Fentanyl (N = 8)	Saline (N = 9)	Total (N = 17)
Pre-procedure characteristics			
Age at time of randomization, h, median [IQR]	(n = 6) 5 [2-11]	(n = 9) 5 [2-8]	(n = 15) 5 [2-9]
Nighttime at randomization, n (%) ^a	4 (50)	5 (56)	9 (53)
Delay from fulfilling the inclusion criteria until the start of the procedure, minutes, median [IQR]	30 [25-60]	38 [30-60]	30 [28-60]
nCPAP as respiratory support at randomization, n (%)	8 (100)	9 (100)	17 (100)
Fio2 before the procedure, median [IQR]	0.43 [0.36-0.46]	0.35 [0.35-0.40]	0.38 [0.35-0.45]
Atropine as premedication, n (%)	1 (13)	0 (0)	1 (6)
Caffeine as premedication, n (%)	6 (75)	8 (89)	14 (82)
Total modified COMFORTneo score before the procedure, median [IQR]	(n = 7) 11 [10-11]	(n = 6) 12 [12-13]	(n = 13) 11 [10-12]
Procedure characteristics			
No. of laryngoscope attempts, median [IQR]	1 [1, 1]	1 [1, 2]	1 [1, 2]
Apnea 20 seconds or more, n (%)	4 (50)	4 (44)	8 (47)
Apnea requiring positive pressure ventilation, n (%)	2 (25)	0 (0)	2 (12)
Desaturation with preductal saturation <85%, n (%)	6 (75)	7 (78)	13 (77)
Bradycardia <100 BPM, n (%)	4 (50)	3 (33)	7 (41)
Observed surfactant reflux, n (%)	5 (62)	7 (78)	12 (71)
Naloxone to reverse apnea, n (%) ^b	4 (50)	5 (56)	9 (53)
Highest modified COMFORTneo score during the procedure, median [IQR]	(n = 8) 14 [12-16]	(n = 7) 12 [11-16]	(n = 15) 13 [11-16]
During laryngoscopy, n (%)	2 (25)	7 (78)	9 (53)
During catheterization, n (%)	3 (38)	0 (0)	3 (18)
During surfactant administration, n (%)	2 (25)	1 (11)	3 (18)
During the entire procedure, n (%)	1 (13)	0 (0)	1 (6)
Post-procedure characteristics			
FiO2 after the procedure, median [IQR]	(n = 8) 0.21 [0.21-0.29]	(n = 8) 0.21 [0.21-0.30]	(n = 16) 0.21 [0.21-0.29]

Legend: Procedure data stratified for saline or fentanyl as premedication for LISA and for the total population included in the NONA-LISA feasibility study. Abbreviations: FiO2 = Fraction of inspired oxygen, IQR = Interquartile range, nCPAP = nasal Continuous Positive Airway Pressure, NONA-LISA = NON-pharmacological Approach to Less Invasive Surfactant Administration. Footnotes: ^a = nighttime was between 19:00 to 07:00, and daytime was between 07:00 to 19:00. ^b = Fentanyl group: the staff expected saline in one out of four

infants treated with naloxone. Saline group: the staff expected saline in all five infants treated with naloxone.

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Table 3. Feasibility Outcomes

	No./total (%)		Relative risk (95% CI)
	Fentanyl	Saline	
Modified COMFORTneo score ≥ 14	4/8 (50)	3/9 (33)	1.5 (0.47, 4.76)
Administration of open-label fentanyl during the procedure ^a	0/8 (0)	2/9 (22)	0.22 (0.01, 4.04)
Expected intervention true	6/8 (75)	6/9 (67)	1.13 (0.61, 2.07)

Legend: Feasibility outcomes of the NONA-LISA feasibility study, including 17 infants from two Danish neonatal intensive care units from September 2023 to May 2024. Abbreviations: CI = Confidence Interval, NONA-LISA = NON-pharmacological Approach to Less Invasive Surfactant Administration. Footnotes: ^a = relative risk was calculated after applying a continuity correction involving adding the value '0.5' to all cells in this row to avoid division by zero.

Table 4: Feedback Data from the Clinical Staff

	n (%) [*]		Total (N = 22)
	Neonatologist (N = 15)	Neonatal nurse (N = 7)	
Responsibilities during the procedure			
Observed the intervention	1 (7)	1 (14)	2 (9)
Performed the laryngoscopy	14 (93)	0 (0)	14 (64)
Administered drugs	1 (7)	1 (14)	2 (9)
Provided non-pharmacological comfort care	2 (13)	5 (71)	7 (32)
Evaluated the modified COMFORTneo score during the procedure	1 (7)	3 (43)	4 (18)
Suggestions for improvement			
Randomization procedure	5 (33)	0 (0)	5 (23)
Protocolized non-pharmacological comfort care	1 (7)	1 (14)	2 (9)
Drug administration	1 (7)	0 (0)	1 (5)
Modified COMFORTneo scoring	3 (20)	2 (29)	5 (23)

Legend: An online survey questionnaire was forwarded to all neonatologists and neonatal nurses who participated in the intervention. Participants answered baseline information and indicated if they had suggestions for improvement regarding any aspects of the NONA-LISA feasibility study. Abbreviations: NONA-LISA = NON-pharmacological Approach to Less Invasive Surfactant Administration. Footnotes: ^{*}A respondent with two or more responsibilities or suggestions for improvements will appear more than once in a column but only once in a row.

Assessed for eligibility at two study centers (n = 99)

Excluded (n = 79)

- Not inborn at a study center (n = 29)
- Did not require exogenous surfactant (n = 31)
- Suspicion of lung hypoplasia (n = 1)
- Intubation at any time before randomization (n = 11)
- Suspicion of pneumothorax, pulmonary hemorrhage, or pleural effusion before LISA (n = 1)
- Major congenital anomalies (n = 0)
- Exogenous surfactant at any time before randomization (n = 6)

Eligible for enrollment (n = 20)

Eligible, not randomized (n = 2)

- Trial medication not prepared (n = 1)
- Missed inclusion (n = 1)

Randomized (n = 18)

Allocated to fentanyl (n = 9)
• Received additional analgesics (n = 0)

Allocated to isotonic saline (n = 9)
• Received additional analgesics (n = 2)

Written consent obtained (n = 8)
• Did not understand English or Danish (n = 1)

Written consent obtained (n = 9)

Follow-up completed (n = 8)

Follow-up completed (n = 9)

Analysed (n = 8)

Analysed (n = 9)